

METADATA OF THE STUDY:

Developmental and Environmental Trajectories from Infancy to School Age A Longitudinal Study from Pregnancy to 9 Years of Age

FinnBrain Birth Cohort Study InterLearn Centre of Excellence

Riikka Korja & Elina Mainela-Arnold, Eeva Eskola, Saara Nolvi, Eeva-Leena Kataja,
Anniina Karonen, Hetti Lahtela, Elisabeth Nordenswan, Denise Ollas-Skogster, Essi
Saloranta, Aura Yli-Savola, Fiia Takio, Pauliina Juntunen, Pihla Saaristo, Venla Huovinen,
Kii Kurila, Aino Luotola, Katja Tervahartiala, Satu Savo, Tuomo Häikiö, Minna Vanhala,
Hasse Karlsson, Linnea Karlsson

University of Turku

About this metadata

The researchers of the FinnBrain Birth Cohort Study and InterLearn Centre of Excellence are aiming for active collaboration with individual researchers and study groups. Investigators interested in research collaboration and obtaining access to the data are encouraged to contact FinnBrain board (finnbrain-board@lists.utu.fi).

Contact information of the study: info@finnbrain.fi

Websites: www.finnbrain.fi; www.interlearn.fi

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1 Description of the Study: Developmental and Environmental Trajectories from Pregnancy to School Age

The aim of our study, “Developmental and Environmental Trajectories from Infancy to School Age”, is to advance understanding of how multiple environmental and biological processes contribute to children’s development and, consequently, to the early origins of psychopathology and learning difficulties. Specifically, the project investigates the early development of socio-emotional functioning, language, cognition, temperament, and executive functioning and their modulation by environmental antecedents, with particular emphasis on the role of early-life stress exposure in shaping these trajectories (Figure 1).

The study follows children’s longitudinal developmental trajectories from infancy through school age. Particular attention is given to the individual variability in the domains of self-regulation, executive functions, language, and social and emotional competence. We examine how these developmental factors influence children’s mental health, learning, well-being, and overall psychological functioning during later childhood and adolescence.

Furthermore, we examine children’s development within their primary growth environments, including the family, day care, school, peer relationships, and digital contexts. Through this multidimensional approach, the project aims to elucidate the complex interplay between psychological and environmental factors that shape children’s developmental outcomes.

This study is a sub-study of the FinnBrain Birth Cohort Study (n = 3,808; www.finnbrain.fi), which was founded in 2011 by Prof. Hasse Karlsson (Founder of the project) and Prof. Linnea Karlsson (Principal Investigator). The FinnBrain project aims to investigate child brain development and how it is shaped by genetic and environmental influences, and how this development is intertwined with other domains of child development and health across the lifespan.

A sub-study presented in this document originally aimed to examine the effects of early-life stress, and particularly prenatal stress exposures, on child development. Therefore, a specific Focus Cohort was drawn from the broader FinnBrain cohort. The Focus Cohort constitutes a nested case–control study within the main cohort, and the case and control groups were formed based on the level of maternal distress (depressive, anxiety and pregnancy-related anxiety symptoms) during pregnancy. Eventually, these children and their parents were invited to visits when the children were 8 months, 2.5 years, 5 years, and 9 years of age. In this document, we present data from this follow-up spanning infancy to 9 years of age. Additionally, the children are participating in a subsequent follow-up in the 5th grade (11 to 12 years of age). Metadata including this later ongoing assessment point will be published once the data collection has been completed.

This study is carried out at the Department of Psychology and Speech Pathology and at the Department of Clinical Medicine at the University of Turku. The Principal Investigators of this study are Prof. Riikka Korja and Prof. Elina Mainela-Arnold. The study is also part of the Centre of Excellence for Learning Dynamics and Intervention Research (InterLearn) funded by the Research Council of Finland. InterLearn was set up to examine the dynamic processes linking children’s learning and mental health, risk and resilience factors underlying learning problems and well-being, and interindividual variability in response to interventions and the development of novel interventions. The InterLearn Centre of Excellence (CoE) is carried out in collaboration with the Departments of Psychology and Education at the University of Jyväskylä (PI Prof. Paavo Leppänen and Co-PI Prof. Mikko Aro). Riikka Korja leads the team located at the University of Turku within this CoE.

Figure 1. Timeline for the Study “Developmental and Environmental Trajectories from Infancy to School Age”

1.1 Funding

Overall Funding of the Study

Finnish State Grants for Clinical Research (Hasse Karlsson, Linnea Karlsson, Riikka Korja, Saara Nolvi, Eeva-Leena Kataja, Katja Tervahartiala)

Signe and Ane Gyllenberg Foundation (Hasse Karlsson, Linnea Karlsson)

Study During Pregnancy

Research Council of Finland (Hasse Karlsson #253270 & 134950)

Jalmari and Rauha Ahokas Foundation (Hasse Karlsson)

Finnish Medical Foundation (Linnea Karlsson)

Study Visit at 8 Months

Research Council of Finland (Hasse Karlsson #253270 & 264363; Linnea Karlsson #308176; Riikka Korja #286829 & #308252)

Study Visit at 2.5 Years

Research Council of Finland (Riikka Korja #286829, Riikka Korja #308252, Hasse Karlsson #264363)

Jane and Aatos Erkko Foundation (Hasse Karlsson)

Signe & Ane Gyllenberg Foundation (Riikka Korja)

Finnish Cultural Foundation (Riikka Korja, Linnea Karlsson)

Study Visits at 5 Years

Research Council of Finland (Riikka Korja #286829, Riikka Korja #308252, Linnea Karlsson #308589, Hasse Karlsson #314390, #332444)

Jane and Aatos Erkko Foundation (Hasse Karlsson)

Stiftelsen Eschnerska Frilasarettet sr (Hasse Karlsson)

Anonymous Endowed Found to University of Turku Speech-Language Pathology

Signe & Ane Gyllenberg Foundation (Riikka Korja, Saara Nolvi)

Finnish Cultural Foundation (Riikka Korja)

Study Visits at 9.5 Years

Research Council of Finland (Riikka Korja #346121 Centre of Excellence in Learning Dynamics and Intervention Research, Linnea Karlsson #342748, Hasse Karlsson #332444)

Signe & Ane Gyllenberg Foundation (Riikka Korja, Saara Nolvi, Hasse Karlsson)

Stiftelsen Eschnerska Frilasarettet sr (Hasse Karlsson, Linnea Karlsson)

Kommunalrådet C. G. Sundells stiftelse sr (Hasse Karlsson, Linnea Karlsson)

Anonymous Endowed Found to University of Turku Speech-Language Pathology

Juho Vainio Foundation (Katja Tervahartiala)

1.2 Publications

A list of publications in which the data were used can be found on the website of the FinnBrain Study: www.finnbrain.fi.

1.3 Principal Investigators and Research Groups

Study Visit at 8 Months (2013–2016)

Principal Investigators

- Linnea Karlsson, Hasse Karlsson, and Riikka Korja

The Core Research Group (in alphabetical order):

- Eeva-Leena Kataja and Saara Nolvi

Coordinators

- Eija Jossandt and Katja Tervahartiala

Data Managers

- Teemu Kemppainen

Study Visit at 2.5 Years (2015–2018)

Principal Investigators

- Riikka Korja and Linnea Karlsson

The Core Research Group (in alphabetical order):

- Eeva Eskola, Eeva Holmberg, Anniina Karonen, Hasse Karlsson, Hetti Lahtela, Eeva-Leena Kataja, Paula Mustonen, Anna Nieminen, and Saara Nolvi

Coordinators

- Eija Jossandt and Katja Tervahartiala

Data Managers

- Teemu Kemppainen

Study Visits at 5 Years (2017–2021)

Principal Investigators

- Riikka Korja (Child Development and Parenting), Elina Mainela-Arnold (Speech and Language)

The Core Research Group (in alphabetical order):

- Eeva Eskola, Eeva Holmberg, Eeva-Leena Kataja, Hetti Lahtela, Saara Nolvi, Elisabeth Nordenswan, Aura Yli-Savola, Linnea Karlsson, and Hasse Karlsson

Coordinators

- Eija Jossandt, Katja Tervahartiala, Essi Saloranta, and Satu Savo

Data Managers

- Teemu Kemppainen and Tuomo-Artturi Autere

Study Visits at 9.5 Years (2021–2025)

Principal Investigators

- Riikka Korja and Saara Nolvi (Child development & parenting), Elina Mainela-Arnold (Speech and Language)

The Core Research Group (in alphabetical order):

- Venla Huovinen, Pauliina Juntunen, Kiia Kurila, Aino Luotola, Pihla Saaristo, Katja Tervahartiala, Eeva-Leena Kataja

Coordinators

- Eija Jossandt, Satu Savo and Saija Tarro

Data Managers

- Teemu Kemppainen and Tuomo-Artturi Autere

1.4 Access to Data

Current EU and national legislation on the protection of personal data including sensitive data, as well as the informed consents provided by the study participants, do not permit open data sharing. Investigators interested in research collaboration and in obtaining access to the data are encouraged to contact FinnBrain Board (finnbrain-board@lists.utu.fi). Contact

information for the board members and FinnBrain's Principal Investigators is available on the project website: <https://sites.utu.fi/finnbrain/en/contact/>.

Researchers working in the project:

Researchers submit abstracts and data requests through a browser-based data request system. The abstracts are reviewed at a board meeting, and once approved, the data managers prepare the requested data file for the researcher. The researcher must sign a data agreement before the data can be released. Data files are provided securely to researchers via the university's Seafire service.

2 Ethical Considerations

The Ethics Committee of the Hospital District of Southwestern Finland has granted ethical approval for all parts of the study. The dates and reference numbers of the existing approvals are as follows:

Whole Cohort

FinnBrain Birth Cohort Study (general approval) 14.6.2011 ETMK: 57/180/2011

FinnBrain Birth Cohort Study (updated general approval) 13.2.2024
VARHA/18203/13.02.02/2023

Child Development and Speech and Language Study Visits at 8 Months, 2.5 Years, 5 Years and 9.5 Years

Child's temperament and EF, ETMK:59/1801/2013, 16.4.2013, 17.2.2015, 21.2.2017, 23.11.2021

Eye-movement tracking, ETMK: 107/180/2012, 20.11.2012, 17.2.2015, 21.2.2017, 23.11.2021

Mother-infant interaction, ETMK:103/1801/2014, 28.8.2014, 17.2.2015, 21.2.2017, 23.11.2021

Mental development, ETMK:26/1801/2015, 27.1.2015, 21.2.2017, 23.11.2021

Child's hair sample, 14.6.2011 ETMK: 57/180/2011

Study visits of Speech and Language Development at 5 years 20.6.2017 63/1801/2017 and at 9 years 23.11.2021 70/1801/2021

Each participant provided written informed consent. For children under the age of 9, the consent was given by their parents. At 9 years of age, children provided their own assent at

the study visit. All participants were informed that participation was voluntary and that they could withdraw from the study at any time without any effect on current or future treatment or services. Consent was obtained separately for each type of data collection, and recruitment was carried out through personal contact (researcher, research nurse, research assistant, or project researcher).

3 Data Management Principles

The University of Turku acts as the data controller in this study. Current EU and national legislation on the protection of personal data including sensitive data, and the informed consents given by the study participants do not permit open data sharing, but data can be shared as part of research collaboration only. Investigators interested in research collaboration and obtaining access to the data are encouraged to contact the FinnBrain Board (finnbrain-board@lists.utu.fi). Contact information for the board members and FinnBrain's Principal Investigators is listed on the project website: <https://sites.utu.fi/finnbrain/en/contact/>. Ethical approvals have been obtained from the Ethics Committee of the Southwest Finland Welfare County (VARHA).

Data managers have been actively involved in developing the data architecture, data scoring and entry procedures, and data management protocols to ensure the consistency and quality of the dataset. They act as gatekeepers of the data and, upon request and according to agreements within the research group, compile the pseudonymized datasets for analyses. To prevent data corruption through accidental alterations or other errors, a separate, unaltered master copy of the raw recordings is maintained in secure storage.

Data requests along with a research abstract are required to be submitted to a browser-based data request system tailored for the FinnBrain Study. Each abstract is reviewed at a board meeting, and once approved, the data managers prepare the requested data file for the researcher. The researcher must sign a data agreement before the data can be released. Data files are delivered securely to researchers via the university's Seafire service.

We have ensured the quality of the data by training the research personnel in standardized data collection and scoring practices, including the assessment of inter-rater reliability when applicable. Data reliability and validity are further supported through the use of well-validated and widely studied research methods, implemented by personnel with appropriate training and relevant clinical experience. In addition, the methods were piloted in the target population prior to the onset of the study. We have mitigated—and will continue to mitigate—the challenges associated with missing data by designing data collection sessions to be appropriately paced and not overly lengthy, including age-appropriate breaks when necessary. For missing data (e.g., questionnaire items or test data), we examine whether the data are missing at random and account for this in the analyses. When warranted and applicable, we will also use statistical data imputation methods, and statisticians are consulted in such cases.

The implementation of the project adheres to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and to the Finnish (TENK) and European (ALLEA) guidelines on research integrity, as well as to the ethical guidelines for conducting research in child populations.

All pseudonymized digital data are processed and stored within institutional IT systems that require user authentication (username and password) and are protected by state-of-the-art firewalls and antivirus software (e.g., the university's network drives). All online data transfers are carried out using encrypted and secure connections (VPN portal, SSH/SFTP servers, encrypted e-mail). Backup copies of the data are stored on a network-attached storage (NAS) system at the host institution that owns the data, which is designed for handling sensitive data.

All non-digital data (as well as computers and external hard drives containing digital data) are housed in buildings equipped with appropriate physical security safeguards (e.g., perimeter security and access control). Within these buildings, non-digital data are stored in double-locked facilities (locked boxes or cabinets located within locked rooms). All data containing identifiers—including demographic and contact information forms, signed informed consent forms, medical records, audio and video recordings, and the ID-code key—are stored separately from the rest of the data. The ID-code key itself is stored in a distinct location from other materials containing identifiers. Data files containing identifiers are password-protected. Backup copies of these data are stored using the same procedures described above.

In the event of any physical or technical incident, the data can be restored in a timely manner from the backup copies described above.

Data access is managed responsibly, taking into account both the need to make data available to the scientific community and the requirements related to participant consent, the GDPR, and IP rights pertaining to the exploitation of results. All access to the data—particularly to personal or sensitive data—is controlled by the data managers, the PIs of the project, and the FinnBrain Board. Members of the research team responsible for data security also sign a data protection agreement. Participants are asked in the consent forms for permission to share pseudonymized data within the consortium and, upon request, with collaborators. The data are shared through formal collaboration mechanisms, such as visiting researcher programs or bilateral institutional Material Transfer Agreements (MTAs). Only pseudonymized data are shared, with no sensitive or personal information included, and using ID codes only. This excludes sharing of certain data types, such as audio recordings or visual material (e.g., video recordings) of participants.

4 Data Collection

4.1 Recruitment and Participants

4.1.1 Whole Cohort

Participants

The participants of these studies are part of the larger FinnBrain Birth Cohort Study ($n = 3,808$; www.finnbrain.fi), which investigates genetic and environmental influences on child development and health. The cohort sample represents the source population of Finland well (Karlsson et al., 2018). Participants in the main cohort were recruited from the South-Western Hospital District and the Åland Islands in Finland between December 2011 and April 2015. A study nurse invited the mothers and their spouses to participate in this longitudinal study during the first-trimester ultrasound visit at gestational week 12. Verified pregnancy and sufficient proficiency in either Finnish or Swedish were required for participation.

Questionnaire data were collected from the parents of the whole cohort at gestational weeks 14, 24, and 34, and when the participating child was 3 and 6 months and, subsequently, 1, 2, 4, 5, and 9 years of age.

To examine the effects of early-life distress on child development in more detail, a Focus Cohort was drawn from the main cohort. The Focus Cohort constitutes a nested case–control study within the main cohort. The Focus Cohort criteria were based on preliminary analyses of questionnaire data from the first 500 participating mothers, assessing depressive, general anxiety and pregnancy-related anxiety symptoms at gestational weeks 14, 24, and 34. The Focus Cohort consisted of mothers reporting elevated distress symptoms in at least two different assessments (approximately the highest 25th percentile), and their controls who reported consistently low levels of distress across all assessments. A more detailed description of the FinnBrain sample and the Focus Cohort criteria is provided in the Cohort Profile by Karlsson et al. (2018).

Children and their parents in the Focus Cohort were invited to the Child Development and Parental Functioning Lab study visits at the age of 8 months, 2.5 years, 5 years, and 9.5 years. When resources allowed for additional study visits, families from the whole cohort were also invited to enrich the sample. These families have actively participated in other study visits within the FinnBrain Birth Cohort Study. In addition, the children were invited to the Speech and Language study visits at the age of 5 and 9 years.

The Child Development study visits at 8 months were conducted between March 2013 and June 2016, the 2.5-year follow-up between April 2015 and June 2018, the 5-year follow-up between October 2017 and December 2021, and the 9.5-year follow-up from March 2022 to June 2025. The Speech and Language study visits were carried out at age 5 years between November 2017 and February 2021 and at age 9.5 years between March 2022 and May 2025. The visits were conducted in the FinnBrain laboratories or in the laboratory facilities in the Department of Psychology and Speech-Language Pathology or the Interdisciplinary Clinic at

the University of Turku by clinical psychologists, speech pathologists, or advanced psychology or speech-language pathology students who received supervision. More detailed recruitment and consent protocols are described in the sections below.

References

Karlsson, L., Tolvanen, M., Scheinin, N. M., Uusitupa, H., Korja, R., Ekholm, E., Tuulari, J. J., Pajulo, M., & Huotilainen, M. (2018). Cohort profile: The FinnBrain Birth Cohort Study (FinnBrain). *International Journal of Epidemiology*, 47(1), 15–16. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyx173>

4.1.2 Child Development Study Visit at 8 Months

Participants

Participants comprised a total of 449 mothers and infants (212 girls and 237 boys), of whom 391 belonged to the FinnBrain Focus Cohort. In total, 157 mothers belonged to the case group with elevated psychological distress during pregnancy, and 234 mothers belonged to the control group with low levels of psychological distress. In addition, 58 mother–infant pairs in which the mothers did not represent the low or high ends of distress during pregnancy were invited to the visit to enrich the sample. These families had actively participated in other study visits within the FinnBrain Birth Cohort Study. The recruitment target age for the study visit was 8 months from the due date. The mean age of the infants at the visit was 8.1 months from the due date ($SD = 0.2$; $min. = 7.2$; $max. = 9.1$).

Recruitment and Consent Protocols

Recruitment took place between May 2013 and June 2016. Families were contacted by trained recruiters, who were clinical psychologists, study nurses, or advanced psychology students. A total of 908 families were reached by phone and informed about the study. In total, 449 (49% of those contacted) families participated in the laboratory visit, and 434 eye-tracking assessments and 428 measurements of temperament and executive functions were completed. A mother–infant interaction task was added to the study protocol in October 2014. During this later phase of the data collection, 354 mothers were contacted, and 197 (56%) mother–infant free-play situations were conducted.

Written informed consent forms were obtained from the parents at the beginning of the visit by the researcher or research assistant conducting the visit. Parents signed the consent on behalf of their infant. Families received a small reward (e.g., an infant toy) after the study visit.

4.1.3 Child Development Study Visit at 2.5 Years

Participants

Participants were 474 children (240 girls and 264 boys), of whom 342 belonged to the Focus Cohort: 124 mothers belonged to the case group with elevated psychological distress during pregnancy, and 218 mothers belonged to the control group with low levels of psychological distress. An additional 132 families were invited to enrich the sample; in these families, the mothers did not represent the extreme ends of psychological distress symptoms during pregnancy. These families had actively participated in other study visits within the FinnBrain

Birth Cohort Study. The mean age of the children at the visit was 30.6 months ($SD = 0.5$; $min. = 29.4$; $max. = 32.7$).

Recruitment and Consent Protocols

Recruitment took place between April 2015 and June 2018. Families were contacted by a psychologist, a study nurse, or a psychology student supervised by a psychologist. We attempted to contact 1,042 families by phone (via text message and/or phone call). A total of 525 (50% of those contacted) families agreed to participate and booked a study visit, and 51 (10% of those who agreed) families later cancelled without rebooking. Ultimately, 474 (45% of those contacted) families participated in the study visit.

Written informed consent forms were obtained from the parents at the beginning of the study visit by the researcher or research assistant conducting the visit. Parents signed the consent on behalf of their children. The children received a small reward (a toy, e.g., a ball) after the study visit.

4.1.4 Child Development Study Visit at 5 Years

Participants

Participants were 545 children (241 girls and 304 boys). The children's mean age at the time of the study visit was 5.0 years ($SD = 0.18$; $min. = 4.9$; $max. = 5.4$). Of these families, 341 belonged to the Focus Cohort: 126 mothers belonged to the case group with elevated maternal psychological distress during pregnancy, and 215 mothers belonged to the control group with low levels of maternal psychological distress during pregnancy. An additional 204 families were invited to enrich the sample or based on their prior participation in earlier visits of the cohort; in these families, the mothers did not represent the extreme ends of psychological distress symptoms during pregnancy but had other relevant data.

Recruitment and Consent Protocols

Recruitment took place between October 2017 and December 2021. Primarily, the families who had participated in the previous 2.5-year study visit were recruited for the 5-year visit. Recruitment was conducted by a psychologist, a study nurse, or a psychology student. We attempted to contact 1,288 families by phone (via text message and/or phone call). Of these, 966 families were reached; 617 (48% of those contacted) families agreed to participate and booked a study visit; and 545 (42% of those contacted) families ultimately completed a study visit. Written informed consent forms were obtained from the parents at the beginning of the study visit by the researcher or research assistant conducting the visit. Parents signed the consent on behalf of their children. Children received a small reward (a toy, e.g., magnetic sand) after the study visit.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, protective face masks were used during the final part of the data collection period ($n = 17$).

4.1.5 Speech and Language Study Visit at 5 Years

Participants

The participants were 394 children (169 girls and 225 boys), of whom 245 belonged to the Focus Cohort, with 83 children belonging to the case group with elevated maternal psychological distress during pregnancy, and 162 belonging to the control group with low levels of maternal psychological distress during pregnancy. Additionally, 149 children from families not belonging to these groups participated in the study based on the enrichment criteria (e.g., prior participation in other visits of the cohort). The mean age at the time of participation was 5.1 years ($SD = 0.13$; $min. = 4.9$; $max. = 5.6$).

Recruitment and Consent Protocols

Recruitment took place between November 2017 and February 2021 and was conducted by a research assistant, a project researcher, or a speech-and-language-pathology student. We attempted to contact 546 families by phone (via text message and/or phone call). A total of 418 (77% of those contacted) families agreed to participate and booked a study visit, and 24 (6% of those who agreed) families later cancelled without rebooking. Finally, 394 (72% of those contacted) families participated in the study visit.

Written informed consent forms were obtained from the parents at the beginning of the study visit by the researcher or research assistant conducting the visit. Parents signed the consent on behalf of their children. Children received a small reward (a toy, e.g., a ball) after the study visit.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, protective face masks were used during the final part of the data collection period ($n = 20$).

4.1.6 Child Development Study Visit at 9.5 Years

Participants

Participants were 533 children (255 girls and 278 boys), of whom 248 belonged to the Focus Cohort: 87 mothers belonged to the case group with elevated psychological distress during pregnancy, and 163 mothers belonged to the control group with low levels of psychological distress. An additional 283 families were invited to enrich the sample; in these families, the mothers did not represent the extreme ends of psychological distress symptoms during pregnancy but were invited based on, e.g., participation in other prior visits in the cohort study. These families had actively participated in other study visits within the FinnBrain Birth Cohort Study. The mean age of the children at the visit was 9.5 years ($SD = 0.11$; $min. = 8.9$; $max. = 10.5$).

Recruitment and Consent Protocols

Recruitment took place between March 2022 and May 2025 and was conducted by a research assistant or a project researcher. We attempted to contact 1,303 families by phone. Of these, 557 (43% of those contacted) families agreed to participate and booked a study visit, and 24 (4% of those who agreed) families later cancelled without rebooking. Finally, 533 (41% of those contacted) families participated in the study visit. During the early phase of the study

period, protective face masks were used due to the COVID-19 pandemic ($n = 6$). The pandemic did not have an impact on recruitment for this study visit.

Written informed consent forms were obtained from both parents and the child themselves at the beginning of either the Child Development study visit or the Speech and Language study visit (whichever occurred first at the 9.5-year timepoint). The forms were given by the researcher or research assistant conducting the visit. Parents signed the consent on behalf of their children, and the child provided consent for themselves. The children received a small reward (a toy, e.g., a ball) after the study visit.

4.1.7 Speech and Language Study Visit at 9.5 Years

Participants

Participants were 537 children (260 girls and 277 boys), of whom 254 belonged to the Focus Cohort: 88 belonged to the case group with elevated maternal psychological distress during pregnancy, and 166 belonged to the control group with low levels of maternal psychological distress during pregnancy. An additional 283 children were included as an enrichment group; in these families, the mothers did not represent the extreme ends of psychological distress during pregnancy, but were invited based on, e.g., participation in other prior visits in the cohort study. The mean age of the children was 9.5 years ($SD = 0.11$, $min. = 9.3$; $max. = 9.9$).

Recruitment and Consent Protocols

Recruitment took place between March 2022 and May 2025 and was conducted by a project researcher or by speech-language pathology or psychology students supervised by the project researcher. We attempted to contact 1,301 families by phone (via text message and/or phone call) and/or email. Out of these families, 1,069 (82%) were successfully reached. A total of 557 (52% of those contacted) agreed to participate and booked a study visit, and 20 (4% of those who agreed) families later cancelled without rebooking. Finally, 537 (41% of those contacted) families participated in the study visit.

Written informed consent forms were obtained from both parents and children at the beginning of either the Child Development study visit or the Speech and Language study visit (whichever occurred first at the 9.5-year timepoint). The forms were given by the researcher or research assistant conducting the visit. Parents signed the consent on behalf of their children, and children provided consent for themselves. The children received a small reward (a toy, e.g., a squishy) after the study visit.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, protective face masks were used during the early part of the study period ($n = 12$). The pandemic did not affect recruitment for this study visit.

4.2 Procedures

4.2.1 Child Development Study Visit at 8 Months

Assistants were trained by clinical psychologists who were also in charge of coordinating the visit procedures. The research assistants were trained to conduct the visits in a stepwise manner: they first followed visits conducted by the coordinating researchers, then learned the methods by reading the detailed written instructions, and then conducted the visits themselves under the supervision and presence of the coordinating researcher. Once they were able to independently conduct the visits, they also had access to consultation by the coordinating researcher. The visits were conducted in the research facilities of the Department of Psychology and Speech and Language Pathology in the Publicum building, or in FinnBrain's research facilities in the Teutori building at the University of Turku. Each study visit lasted approximately 60 to 75 minutes and was led by two or three clinical psychologists or advanced psychology students supervised by psychologists. At the beginning of each visit, parents were informed about the content of the study visit and their right to withdraw from the testing at any time without providing a specific reason. They signed a written informed consent on behalf of themselves and their infant.

Then, the eye-tracking measurement was conducted in a dimly lit room with plain furnishings. Infants were seated on their parents' lap at a distance of 50–70 cm from the eye tracker (Desktop Mount, EyeLink1000+, SR Research Ltd., Toronto, Ontario, Canada). Infants viewed the stimuli on a screen (19" CRT monitor) placed 15 cm behind the tracker. The researcher conducted the measurement using a host computer in the same room behind a curtain. A five-point calibration routine was performed followed by a validation procedure, which was repeated during the experiment if needed. The x- and y-coordinates for the estimated gaze location were recorded at a frequency of 500 Hz. In addition, children's eye movements were recorded with a regular video camera placed next to the screen. The eye-tracking measurement included a social-emotional overlap task with 48 trials (Kataja et al., 2020). If the infant was restless, short breaks were provided during the measurement. The researcher terminated the experiment if the infant became inattentive or fussy. The eye-tracking measurement took about 15–20 minutes to complete.

After that, the following laboratory temperament and executive function assessments were conducted: the episodes *Blocks*, *Masks* and *Gentle Arm Restraint by Parent* from the *Laboratory Temperament Assessment Battery Prelocomotor (Lab-TAB Prelocomotor*; Goldsmith & Rothbart, 1999), and the modified *A-not-B* task (Nolvi et al., 2018). The first episode was the *Blocks* assessment for infant attentiveness and persistence and was conducted in the primary experiment room with a duration of 4 minutes. The infant was sitting in a highchair at the table, with the parent sitting slightly behind and on the left side of the infant. Next, the infant and the parent were moved to another experiment room, where the episode *Masks*, designed to elicit fear responses, was conducted, with a duration of 1.5 to 2 minutes. After this episode, there was a 5-minute break for the infant to calm down. Next, the parent and the infant were again moved to the primary temperament experiment room, where the modified *A-not-B* task to assess executive functions was conducted. In this task, the infant sat in the mother's lap at the table while attending to the experimenter leading the task from the other side of the table. The task duration varied from 5 to 15 minutes depending on infant

performance. Fourth, the infants participated in the Lab-TAB episode Gentle Arm Restraint by Parent. In this episode, the infant was again placed in a highchair, with the parent sitting very close and almost behind the infant. The duration of this episode was 3 minutes altogether.

Before the inclusion of the mother-infant free play situation, the visit ended here and the infant was given a small toy. After October 2014, the visit also included a 20-minute mother–infant free play situation that was conducted in the third room, and the toy gift was given after the free play period. All tasks and the free-play situation were video-recorded and stored in .avchd format. Scoring of the tasks were conducted afterwards using the video-recordings.

Any deviations from the study protocol or events during the study visit that could affect the reliability of the data collection were written down in the study log. If any concerns for the family or the child were observed during the study visit, feedback and advice were given by a researcher-psychologist at the end of the study visit or by a phone call afterwards, if the study visit was conducted by a student.

References

- Goldsmith, H. H., & Rothbart, M. K. (1999). *The Laboratory Temperament Assessment Battery (LAB-TAB, Prelocomotor Version, Edition 3.1)*. Madison, Wisconsin: University of Wisconsin Press.
- Kataja, E.-L., Karlsson, L., Leppänen, J. M., Pelto, J., Häikiö, T., Nolvi, S., Pesonen, H., Parsons, C. E., Hyönä, J., & Karlsson, H. (2020). Maternal depressive symptoms during the pre- and postnatal periods and infant attention to emotional faces. *Child Development, 91*, e475–e490. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.13152>
- Nolvi, S., Pesonen, H., Bridgett, D. J., Korja, R., Kataja, E.-L., Karlsson, H., & Karlsson, L. (2018). Infant Sex Moderates the Effects of Maternal Pre- and Postnatal Stress on Executive Functioning at 8 Months of Age. *Infancy, 23*(2), 194–210. <https://doi.org/10.1111/inf.1220>

4.2.2 Child Development Study Visit 2.5 Years

Assistants attended a three-hour training that included the introduction to study protocols and training for assessing toddlers and interacting with families. In addition, the research assistant spent about 20 hours practising the study visit using a written manual of the visit and training videos made by the study group. They studied the *INTER-NDA* (Fernandes et al., 2014) using the manual and training videos for this assessment method.

The study visits were conducted in FinnBrain’s research facilities in the Teutori building at the University of Turku. Every study visit took approximately 90 minutes, and each was led by two psychologists or psychology students supervised by psychologists. First, parents were informed about the content of the study visit and they signed a written informed consent. Parents were present throughout the entire study visit. Then, the eye-tracking measurement was conducted in a dimly lit room with plain furnishings. Children were seated on one of

their parents' lap at a distance of 50–70 cm from the eye tracker (Desktop Mount, EyeLink1000+, SR Research Ltd., Toronto, Ontario, Canada). Children viewed the stimuli on a screen (19" CRT monitor) placed 15 cm behind the tracker. The researcher conducted the tracking using a host computer in the same room behind a curtain. A five-point calibration routine was performed followed by a validation procedure, which was repeated during the experiment if needed. The x- and y-coordinates for the estimated gaze location were recorded at a frequency of 500 Hz. In addition, children's eye movements were recorded with a regular video camera placed next to the screen. The eye-tracking measurement included a social-emotional overlap task with 24 trials (Kataja et al., 2022) and a free viewing of paired faces task with 36 trials (Eskola et al., 2023). If the child was restless, short breaks were provided during the measurement. The researcher terminated the experiment if a child verbally or behaviorally indicated a willingness to stop despite the researcher's or the parent's gentle encouragement to continue. The experiment was also terminated if a child became seemingly inattentive or upset. The eye-tracking measurement took about 15–20 minutes to complete.

Other tasks of the study visit were conducted in another room with child-friendly furnishings. The entire study visit was video recorded. The *INTER-NDA* (Fernandes et al., 2014) was conducted at the higher table. The person conducting the study visit marked the scores on a paper sheet or on an application on a tablet computer. Children were seated on their own chairs or on their parents' lap. The administration took about 15 to 20 minutes. After the children's tasks, some snacks were provided while the caregiver was interviewed with questions related to attention.

Next, the EF tasks *Spin the Pots* (Hughes & Ensor, 2005), *Snack Delay* (Kochanska et al., 2000), and *Day and Night* (Gerstadt et al., 1994) were administered, also at the higher table. *Day and Night* appeared to be too difficult for our sample; therefore, it was removed from the study protocols after 38 administrations. The scores were recorded on paper sheets. After that, two temperament observation tasks from the *Lab-TAB* (Goldsmith et al., 1999) were administered. The task *Attractive Toy in a Transparent Box* was administered at the lower table, and *Popping Bubbles* was administered on the floor. The EF and temperament tasks took about 30 minutes altogether. Finally, the parent–child interaction situation was conducted, which took about 20 minutes.

After the tasks, hair samples were collected for another substudy of FinnBrain. Additionally, some background information was requested from the parent:

- “Was there anything special during the study visit that we need to consider?”
- “Lately, have you been worried about your child's development, behaviour, or overall well-being?”
- “Have you sought help for your family or for your child during the past two years?”

In addition, the parent's overall grade for the Matriculation Examination Certificate (ylioppilastutkintotodistus) or the Basic Education Certificate (peruskoulun päättötodistus) was recorded.

Any deviations from the study protocol or events during the study visit that could affect the reliability of the data collection were written down. If any concerns for the family or the child were observed during the study visit, feedback and advice were given by a researcher-psychologist at the end of the study visit or by a phone call, if the study visit was conducted by a student.

References

- Eskola, E., Kataja, E.-L., Pelto, J., Tuulari, J. J., Hyönä, J., Häikiö, T., Hessels, R. S., Holmberg, E., Nordenswan, E., Karlsson, H., Karlsson, L., & Korja, R. (2023). Attention biases for emotional facial expressions during a free viewing task increase between 2.5 and 5 years of age. *Developmental Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/dev0001598>
- Fernandes, M., Stein, A., Newton, C. R., Cheikh-Ismail, L., Kihara, M., Wulff, K., De León Quintana, E., Aranzeta, L., Soria-Frisch, A., Acedo, J., Ibanez, D., Abubakar, A., Giuliani, F., Lewis, T., Kennedy, S., Villar, J., & for the International Fetal and Newborn Growth Consortium for the 21st Century (INTERGROWTH-21st). (2014). The INTERGROWTH-21st Project Neurodevelopment Package: A novel method for the multi-dimensional assessment of neurodevelopment in pre-school age children. *PLoS ONE*, 9(11), e113360. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0113360>
- Gerstadt, C. L., Hong, Y. J., & Diamond, A. (1994). The relationship between cognition and action: performance of children 312–7 years old on a stroop- like day-night test. *Cognition*, 53, 129–153. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0277\(94\)90068-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-0277(94)90068-X).
- Goldsmith, H.H., Reilly, J., Lemery, K.S., Longley, S., & Prescott, A. (1999). *The Laboratory Temperament Assessment Battery Preschool (Version 0)*.
- Hughes, C., & Ensor, R. (2005). Executive Function and Theory of Mind in 2 Year Olds: A Family Affair? *Developmental Neuropsychology*, 28(2), 645–668. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15326942dn2802_5
- Kataja, E. L., Eskola, E., Pelto, J., Korja, R., Paija, S. P., Nolvi, S., Häikiö, T., Karlsson, L., Karlsson, H., & Leppänen, J. M. (2022). The stability of early developing attentional bias for faces and fear from 8 to 30 and 60 months in the FinnBrain Birth Cohort Study. *Developmental psychology*, 58(12), 2264–2274. <https://doi.org/10.1037/dev0001432>
- Kochanska, G., Murray, K. T., & Harlan, E. T. (2000). Effortful control in early childhood: continuity and change, antecedents, and implications for social development. *Developmental psychology*, 36(2), 220–232.

4.2.3 Child Development Study Visit at 5 Years

The study visits for 5-year-old children were conducted by research assistants who were psychology students, worked in pairs, and were supervised by psychologists/PhD students. The research assistants received 20 hours of training prior to conducting study visits. The training included observing a study visit, getting acquainted with the study visit's manual (a 38-page-long document describing e.g., the study visit's structure, the administration of the study tasks, how to use the technical equipment, how to interact with the study families, how to store data after the study visits, and how to write feedback summaries), practising conducting the study visit on a fellow research assistant, practising conducting the study visit on a child who was not a study participant, and conducting an actual study visit with a supervisor present. While working with the data collection, the

research assistants were encouraged to consult their supervisors concerning any questions related to the data collection, and regular meetings with supervisors were organized to discuss questions related to how to conduct the study visits.

The study visits for the 5-year-old children were conducted at FinnBrain's research facilities in the Teutori building and took approximately 2 hours. After a brief introductory discussion with the parent and child about the upcoming study visit's components in the waiting room of the research facility (during which written informed consent was collected from the parent), the study visit began with an eye-tracking measurement of emotional attention. This measurement was conducted in a small, dimly lit room with plain furnishings. Children were seated at a distance of 50–70 cm from the eye tracker (Desktop Mount, EyeLink1000+, SR Research Ltd., Toronto, Ontario, Canada). Children viewed the stimuli on a screen (19" CRT monitor) placed 15 cm behind the tracker. The parent was seated behind the child. The researcher conducted the tracking using a host computer in the same room behind a curtain. A five-point calibration routine was performed followed by a validation procedure, which was repeated during the experiment if needed. The x- and y-coordinates for the estimated gaze location were recorded at a frequency of 500 Hz. In addition, children's eye movements were recorded with a regular video camera placed next to the screen. The eye-tracking measurement included a social-emotional overlap task with 24 trials (Kataja et al., 2022), a free-viewing of paired faces task with 32 trials (Eskola et al., 2023) and the *Always Look at the Happy Face* task with 36 trials (Lagattuta & Kramer, 2017). If the child was restless, short breaks were provided during the measurement. The researcher terminated the experiment if a child verbally or behaviorally indicated a willingness to stop despite the researcher's or the parent's gentle encouragement to continue. The experiment was also terminated if a child became seemingly inattentive or upset. The eye-tracking measurement took about 20 minutes to complete.

After the eye-movement measurement was completed, the child and parent were accompanied to a separate room, in which the rest of the study visit's tasks were administered. The room was well lit and colorfully yet serenely decorated in order to make the child feel welcome while not becoming distracted during the tasks. The child sat at a white desk while working with the tasks, and the research assistant was either seated next to the child (for the EF Touch tasks), behind a curtain observing the child through a video link (Forbidden Toy), or on the other side of the table (all other tasks). After the parent and child had familiarized themselves with the room, the parent was handed questionnaires to fill out (*CBCL*, Achenbach & Rescorla, 2001; *BRIEF2*, Gioia et al., 2015; *CBQ*, Rothbart et al., 2001; *MASCS*, Junttila et al., 2006) and guided to take a seat in the waiting area while the child worked independently with the study tasks. If the child felt too anxious without the parent, the parent was allowed to stay in the room, seated approximately 2 m from the child, and asked to fill out the questionnaires to limit interactions with the child during the tasks.

To provide a calm working environment for the child, only the research assistant conducting each task was present in the space visible to the child. There was a structuring map on the wall next to where the child was sitting to help the child track how many tasks remained.

Every task was represented by a picture attached to the structuring map. As the tasks were completed, their pictures were taken off the structuring map to show the child how their work progressed. Children were instructed that they could ask for breaks if needed, and children who wished to do so could visit their parents in the waiting room during a break between tasks. The tasks for the child were administered in the following order: *WPPSI (Blocks, Matrix Reasoning, Similarities; Wechsler, 2009)*, *Spin the Pots (Hughes & Ensor, 2005)*, *Delay of Gratification (Beck et al., 2011)*, *Forbidden Toy* and *EF Touch (Arrows, Pig, Farmer; Willoughby et al., 2017)*.

After the child's individual tasks were completed, the child and the research assistant together fetched the parent from the waiting room and returned to the test room. The child and parent were asked to sit on a comfortable carpet on the floor and engage in a free-play situation. The free-play situation included a maze game, playing with Playmobil toys, and a small snack (juice and cookies).

After the free-play situation, a hair sample was collected from the child for another FinnBrain sub-study. Additionally, background information was collected from the parent by asking the following questions:

1. Have you been concerned about your child's growth, development, or well-being?
2. Have you sought help concerning your child during the past two years?

Next, the parent and child together completed a feedback questionnaire about how they experienced the study visit. Finally, the child was given a diploma for completing the study visit and a small present (kinetic sand) to thank the child for participating in the study visit.

The whole study visit was video recorded. The free-play situation was additionally audio recorded with a Sennheiser AVX lavalier microphone and saved in WAV format with a 1,411 kbps bit rate. During the study visit, the research assistant marked task scores on a paper sheet or on an application on a tablet computer. After the study visit, the research assistants filled out a questionnaire rating the child's activity level, attentiveness, emotional state, and ability to cooperate before the study visit, during the study visit when the parent was present, and during the study visit when the parent was not present. Any deviations from the study protocol or events during the study visit that could affect the reliability of the data collection were noted.

After the study visit, written feedback was sent home to the families regarding the child's performance on tasks for which Finnish norm material was available (i.e., the *WPPSI-III* tasks), along with a description of the child's ability to concentrate on and cooperate with the study tasks. The feedback letters also included a description of the kind of other tasks that were completed during the study visits and how the data collection enables research on child development and well-being. The feedback letters also contained information on authorities to contact if the parents were concerned about their child's development or well-being. If a child's *WPPSI-III* performance was clearly below average (ss 1–5), or if some other concern about the child's development/well-being arose in connection with the study visit, then one of

the psychologists/PhD students who supervised the research assistants' work called the parents. During this phone call, the child's task performance and general functioning during the study visit were described, potential confounders were discussed that might have influenced the task performance (e.g., the child being tired/nervous/not understanding the instructions), and the parent was asked about the child's everyday functioning in areas related to the low task score/topic of concern. If concern about the child's development/well-being remained after this discussion, and if the family had not already contacted the health care system regarding this topic of concern, then suitable ways of contacting healthcare professionals were discussed with the parent.

References

- Achenbach, T. M., & Rescorla, L. A. (2001). Manual for the ASEBA School-Age Forms & Profiles. Burlington, VT: University of Vermont, Research Center for Children, Youth, and Families.
<https://www.nctsn.org/measures/child-behavior-checklist-ages-6-18>
- Beck, D. M., Schaefer, C., Pang, K., & Carlson, S. M. (2011). Executive Function in Preschool Children: Test-Retest Reliability. *Journal of Cognition and Development: Official Journal of the Cognitive Development Society*, 12(2), 169–193. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15248372.2011.563485>
- Eskola, E., Kataja, E.-L., Pelto, J., Tuulari, J. J., Hyönä, J., Häikiö, T., Hessels, R. S., Holmberg, E., Nordenswan, E., Karlsson, H., Karlsson, L., & Korja, R. (2023). Attention biases for emotional facial expressions during a free viewing task increase between 2.5 and 5 years of age. *Developmental Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/dev0001598>
- Gioia, G. A., Isquith, P. K., Guy, S. C., & Kenworthy, L. (2015). *Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function, Second Edition (BRIEF®2) Parent Form* [Assessment instrument]. PAR.
- Hughes, C., & Ensor, R. (2005). Executive Function and Theory of Mind in 2 Year Olds: A Family Affair? *Developmental Neuropsychology*, 28(2), 645–668. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15326942dn2802_5
- Junttila, N., Voeten, M., Kaukiainen, A., & Vauras, M. (2006). Multisource assessment of children's social competence. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 66(5), 874–895.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0013164405285546>
- Kataja, E. L., Eskola, E., Pelto, J., Korja, R., Paija, S. P., Nolvi, S., Häikiö, T., Karlsson, L., Karlsson, H., & Leppänen, J. M. (2022). The stability of early developing attentional bias for faces and fear from 8 to 30 and 60 months in the FinnBrain Birth Cohort Study. *Developmental psychology*, 58(12), 2264–2274.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/dev0001432>
- Lagattuta, K. H., & Kramer, H. J. (2017). Try to look on the bright side: Children and adults can (sometimes) override their tendency to prioritize negative faces. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 146(1), 89–101. <https://doi.org/10.1037/xge0000247>
- Rothbart, M. K., Ahadi, S. A., Hershey, K. L., & Fisher, P. (2001). Investigations of temperament at 3-7 years: The Children's Behavior Questionnaire. *Child Development*, 72, 1394-1408.
- Wechsler, D. (2009). *Wechsler Preschool and Primary Scale of Intelligence - Third Edition (WPPSI-III)*. New York: Pearson.
- Willoughby, M. T., Kuhn, L. J., Blair, C. B., Samek, A., & List, J. A. (2017). The test-retest reliability of the latent construct of executive function depends on whether tasks are represented as formative or reflective indicators. *Child Neuropsychology: A Journal on Normal and Abnormal Development in Childhood and Adolescence*, 23(7), 822–837. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09297049.2016.1205009>

4.2.4 Speech and Language Study Visit at 5 Years

The speech and language (SLP) students conducting the sessions attended an initial four hours of familiarization with the study protocol as well as ten hours of practicing the study visits according to written manuals, training videos, and peer group practice supervised by a

speech and language pathologist/clinical teacher. The entire visit usually lasted approximately 1.5–2 hours.

The study visits were conducted in the interdisciplinary teaching clinic in the Publicum building at the University of Turku. Each study visit was led by one or two SLP students or a research assistant supervised by a speech and language pathologist/clinical teacher. First, parents were informed about the content of the study visit and they signed a written informed consent. Parents were present in the building, in most cases in a different

room, throughout the entire study visit.

Then, the child underwent a hearing test. Each ear was tested separately, one at a time. The presented sounds lasted for 1–2 seconds. The child passed the screening if they heard the tones of 500, 1000, 2000, and 4000 Hz at 20 dB in both ears.

After the hearing screening, the child completed the *Finnish adaptation of the Reynell Developmental Scale III (RDLS III)* (Kortesmaa et al., 2001) assessment at a table, following the test manual. After that, the child repeated nonwords presented via an audio recording. Finally, they completed the *Phonology Test* (Kunnari et al., 2012).

Speech samples were collected during a play session with various toys available. The play session took about 20 minutes. The researchers encouraged the child to talk by using open-ended questions and comments about the play. At the end of the play session, the researcher increased communicative pressure by prompting the child to quickly describe something enjoyable. The aim was to elicit speech disfluencies in children who were prone to them.

The tasks were scored based on answers written on paper sheets (*RDLS III* and *Phonology Test*) or coded afterwards from audio recordings (*Nonword Repetition*, *Speech Sample*). Any deviations from the study protocol or events during the study visit that could affect the reliability of the data collection were noted.

After the study visit, written feedback on the child's performance was sent to the families for those tasks for which Finnish normative data were available (i.e., *RDLS III*), along with a description of the child's cooperation during the study tasks. The feedback letters also included a description of the other tasks completed during the study visits, as well as information on which service providers to contact if parents were concerned about their child's development or well-being.

If a child's *RDLS III* performance was significantly below average, or if another concern regarding the child's development arose in connection with the study visit, a supervising speech and language pathologist called the parents. During the phone call, the child's task

performance and general functioning during the study visit were described, potential confounding factors that might have influenced performance (e.g., the child being tired, nervous, or not understanding the instructions) were discussed, and the parent was asked about the child's everyday functioning in areas related to the low task score or the topic of concern. If concerns about the child's development or well-being remained after this discussion, and if the family had not already contacted the health care provider regarding the concern, appropriate ways of contacting health care professionals were discussed with the parent.

References

- Kortesmaa, K., Merikoski, H., Warma, M.-L., & Varpela, V. (2001). *Reynellin kielellisen kehityksen testi [Reynell Developmental Language Scales]*. Psykologien Kustannus Oy.
- Kunnari, S., Savinainen-Makkonen, T., & Saaristo-Helin, K. (2012). *Fonologiatesti*. Jyväskylä: Niilo Mäki Instituutti

4.2.5 Child Development Study Visit at 9.5 Years

Assistants attended eight hours of training, including an introduction to study protocols and training for assessing children and interacting with families. In addition, the research assistants spent about 30 hours practicing the study visit using a written manual for the visit. They practiced administering the *WISC-IV* (Wechsler, 2010) and the executive function tasks first among themselves and then with a child before starting to conduct the visits. The assistants conducted visits in pairs for several months before beginning to conduct visits independently. Continued training was organized for the assistants as necessary.

The study visits were conducted in the FinnBrain research facilities in the Medisiina building at the University of Turku. Every study visit was led by a psychologist or one or two psychology students. Altogether, the visit lasted three hours. The study visit started with parents and the children signing a written informed consent. Additionally, the parents and the children were informed about the content of the study visit verbally, and the information was supported with a visualization of the visit structure. At this point, families were also informed about the video recording of the study visit, for which separate consent was obtained in the consent form. At this stage, parents were asked if their children had any difficulties with reading and if they should listen to recorded questionnaire questions rather than reading them from a tablet. Then, parents were guided to a separate room where they were asked to wait and fill in questionnaires. At this point, when the researcher was alone with the parent, the researcher asked the following questions:

1. Has the parent been concerned regarding the child's development, growth, well-being, or the family situation?

2. Have they sought help in matters related to the child during the last two years?

If the parent had significant concerns, they were asked if they wanted to be contacted via a phone call by a psychologist after the visit, and the researcher passed this information along to the researcher-psychologists in charge of the visit.

Then, the researcher returned to the examination room, where they began conducting the *WISC-IV* (Wechsler, 2010) tasks with the child. Children were seated at the table opposite the researcher on a child-sized chair. The completion of the three *WISC-IV* tasks (*Block Design*, *Similarities*, *Matrix Reasoning*) took approximately 20 minutes. Afterwards, children completed questionnaires on the iPad (*HSC-C*; Pluess et al., 2018, and *MASCS*; Junttila et al., 2006). Children were offered the choice of filling them either while sitting at the table or while sitting in a bean bag chair with pillows. Based on the child's reading skills assessed by the parent and the child, they either read the questions and answered options or listened to them as recordings. The instructions for each questionnaire were read to the children by the researcher, and the children were advised to ask the researcher if any of the questions were unclear. After completing one questionnaire, the children were asked if they had any trouble understanding any of the questions. The same protocol was followed for all questionnaires.

After completing the questionnaires, children completed four *CANTAB* executive functioning tasks (Sandberg, 2011) on an iPad, while sitting by the table. The administration took approximately 25 minutes, after which there was a ten-minute break during which the child was encouraged to move around and use the available basketball and hoop, trampoline, and balance boards. Then, the *Eveli* virtual reality game assessing executive functioning (Seesjärvi et al., 2023) was conducted using a Pico Neo 3 Pro Eye headset and a Samsung tablet. *Eveli* administration took approximately 20 minutes, after which children completed more questionnaires (SS; Kerns et al., 1996, previous-game-experience questions, Feel-KJ 2; Cracco et al., 2015). Then, children were guided back to the table for the *Emotional Go/No-Go* task (Tottenham et al., 2011), which was completed on a Dell computer twice (with the parent present and with the parent absent), and lasted approximately 15 minutes. Following this, there was a 10-minute snack break during which the parent was alone with the child in the room. The last section of the visit was the recording of the child-parent interaction, lasting approximately 15 minutes. During the interaction, the child and parent were seated at the table.

After each completed section of the visit, the child received a piece of code from the visit structure on the tablet. At the end of the visit, the code was used to open a treasure chest, inside which there were two toys from which the child could pick one to take home. Any deviations from the study protocol or events during the study visit that could affect the reliability of the data collection were noted. If any concerns for the family or the child were observed during the study visit, feedback and advice were given by a researcher-psychologist at the end of the study visit or by a phone call, if the study visit was conducted by a student.

References

- Cracco E, Van Durme K, & Braet C (2015). Validation of the FEEL-KJ: An instrument to measure emotion regulation strategies in children and adolescents. *PLoS ONE*, *10*(9), e0137080. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0137080>
- Junttila, N., Voeten, M., Kaukiainen, A., & Vauras, M. (2006). Multisource assessment of children's social competence. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, *66*(5), 874–895. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013164405285546>
- Kerns, K. A., Klepac, L., & Cole, A. (1996). Security Scale. *APA PsycTests*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/t17560-000>
- Pluess, M., Assary, E., Lionetti, F., Lester, K. J., Krapohl, E., Aron, E. N., & Aron, A. (2018). Environmental sensitivity in children: Development of the Highly Sensitive Child Scale and identification of sensitivity groups. *Developmental Psychology*, *54*(1), 51–70. <https://doi.org/10.1037/dev0000406>
- Rieffe, C., Oosterveld, P., & Terwogt, M.M (2006). An alexithymia questionnaire for children: Factorial and concurrent validation results. *Personality and Individual Differences*, *40*(1), 123-133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2005.05.013>.
- Sandberg, M. A. (2011). Cambridge Neuropsychological Testing Automated Battery. In *Encyclopedia of Clinical Neuropsychology* (pp. 480–482). Springer, New York, NY. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-79948-3_169
- Seesjärvi, E., Puhakka, J., Aronen, E. T., Hering, A., Zuber, S., Merzon, L., Kliegel, M., Laine, M., & Salmi, J. (2023). EPELI: A novel virtual reality task for the assessment of goal-directed behavior in real-life contexts. *Psychological Research*, *87*(6), 1899–1916. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00426-022-01770-z>
- Tottenham, N., Hare, T. A., & Casey, B. J. (2011). Behavioral assessment of emotion discrimination, emotion regulation, and cognitive control in childhood, adolescence, and adulthood. *Frontiers in Psychology*, *2*(MAR), 39. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2011.00039>
- Wechsler, D. (2010). *WISC-IV - Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children—IV* Hogrefe.fi. https://www.hogrefe.fi/tuote?product_id=250

4.2.6 Speech and Language Study Visit at 9.5 Years

The research assistants conducting the visits attended introductory training sessions, totaling eight hours, including an introduction to study protocols and training for meeting the families during study visits, as well as assessing children. After the initial training session, the research assistants practiced the eye-tracking and hearing screening protocols during a three-hour training session. In addition, the research assistants spent

about 20 hours practicing the study visit protocol using a written manual. The research assistants conducted the first study visit under the supervision of a speech-language pathologist/researcher. After the first visit, the assistants conducted five more visits in pairs before starting to conduct the visits independently. Continued training was organized for the research assistants if necessary.

The study visits were conducted in FinnBrain's research facilities in the Medisiina building at the University of Turku. The study visits were conducted by a speech-language pathologist or one or two speech-language pathology master's students. Altogether, one visit took approximately three hours. The study visit started with parents and the children signing a written informed consent. Additionally, the parents and the children were informed about the

content of the study visit verbally, and the information was supported with a visualization of the visit structure. Then, the parents were guided to a separate room where they were asked to fill in questionnaires.

The study visit was video- and audio-recorded except for the tasks that used eye-tracking equipment, which were audio-recorded only. Audio was recorded at a 44.1 kHz/32-bit (WAV) rate, and video at 1080/25-fps. At the beginning of the study visit, a hearing screening was conducted according to the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare's hearing screening guidelines using a screening audiometer (AS608 by Interacoustics). If the children did not pass the hearing screening, the screening was repeated at the end of the visit. If the hearing screening was not passed on the second attempt, the children and the parents were asked if the child had a history of hearing loss or had recently had an illness causing ear congestion prior to the study visit. The hearing screening took approximately five minutes.

After the hearing screening, the children completed eye-tracking measurements in a designated room. Children were seated at a distance of 50–70 cm from the eye tracker (Desktop Mount, EyeLink1000+, SR Research Ltd., Toronto, Ontario, Canada). Children viewed the stimuli on a screen (19" CRT monitor) placed 15 cm behind the tracker. The researcher conducted the tracking using a host computer in the same room. A nine-point calibration routine was performed, followed by a validation, which was repeated during the experiment if needed. The x- and y-coordinates for the estimated gaze location were recorded at a frequency of 500 Hz. The eye-tracking measurement included a social-emotional overlap task with 60 trials and a free-viewing of paired-faces task with 32 trials. If the child was restless, short breaks were provided during the measurement. The researcher terminated the experiment if a child verbally or behaviorally indicated a willingness to stop despite the researcher's or the parent's gentle encouragement to continue. The administration of the eye-tracking protocol took approximately 20 minutes.

Then, the children were guided to the laboratory room, where the oral and written language, and arithmetic assessments took place. The children wore a lavalier microphone throughout the assessment to ensure good audio quality. The assessment started with the Finnish adaptation of the *Clinical Evaluation of Language Fundamentals – Fifth edition (CELF-5; subtests Word Classes, Formulated Sentences, Recalling Sentences, approx. 20 min. assessment; Wiig et al., 2013)*, followed by the Finnish adaptation of the *Rapid Automated Naming task (RAN; Ahonen et al., 1999; approx. 15 min assessment)*. After the RAN task, the children were encouraged to take an exercise break using sports equipment in the assessment room (i.e., a trampoline or basketball). Children were seated opposite the researcher at a table while completing the CELF-5 and the RAN.

After approximately 10 minutes of break, the assessment continued with the collection of a narrative speech sample. The children were seated in a chair away from the table, opposite the researcher, allowing for natural use of gestures during the speech sample. The assessment continued with the *YTTE* reading comprehension test (Kajamies et al., 2003), which was also measured using an eye-tracking device (Desktop Mount, EyeLink1000+, SR Research Ltd., Toronto, Ontario, Canada). The reading comprehension test was conducted in the eye-tracking measurement room. The eye-tracking administration and *YTTE* took approximately 15 minutes to complete.

Then, the assessment continued with a series of oral and written language, and arithmetic assessments. The rest of the assessments were conducted at the table. A *Nonword Repetition* task was completed using an audio-recorded nonword stimulus via Bose Companion 2 III speakers. The assessment continued with the *Lukimat* nonword reading task (approx. 5 min administration), the *Lukilasse 2 Word Fluency* subtest (approx. 5 min administration; Häyrynen et al., 2013), the *Lukimat* text reading fluency task (approx. 5 min administration; Salmi et al., 2011), the *Lukilasse 2 Dictated Words and Sentences* subtest (approx. 10 min administration), and the *Lukimat* arithmetic task (fluency of addition and subtraction skills). After completing the arithmetic task, the children were offered a snack (i.e., a smoothie) break.

Then, if the child either indicated participation in English language instruction at school or other use of English as a second language (L2), the testing continued with L2 English assessments. If the child had not learned English at school but had learned English from other sources (i.e., internet, games, etc.) and wished to complete the tests, the child was allowed to do so. *TROG-2* (Bishop, 2003) was used to assess L2 language comprehension. The stimulus was presented with audio-recorded utterances via Bose Companion 2 III speakers. The *TROG-2* assessment took approximately 20 minutes. Additionally, the children completed three matrices from the *English RAN* test (objects, colors, numbers; Wolf & Denckla, 2005). Finally, the receptive L2 vocabulary task was administered in ViLLE online environment on an iPad for approximately 15 minutes using the *CLT* task (Haman et al., 2015). Lastly, a statistical learning task was conducted in the ViLLE online environment on an iPad (duration approx. 5 minutes). The families were instructed to continue the statistical learning task on three consecutive days after the study visit in the ViLLE environment.

After the completion of the task, the children received letters gradually forming a clue for a hidden key to a treasure chest. From the treasure chest, children could pick a toy as a reward for the study visit. If the study visit was conducted on the same day as the Child Development study visit at 9 years, the family went for a lunch break, after which they continued with the Child Development study visit.

Any deviations from the study protocol or events during the study visit that could affect the reliability of the data collection were noted. All families received written feedback from the study visit. If any concerns for the family or the child were observed during the study visit, feedback was given by a speech-language pathologist by a phone call after the visit.

References

- Ahonen, T., Tuovinen, S., & Leppäsaari, T. (1999). *Nopean sarjallisen nimeämisen testi*. Niilo Mäki Instituutti & Haukkarannan koulu.
- Bishop, (2003) Test for Reception of Grammar (TROG-2).
- Haman, E., Łuniewska, M., & Pomiechowska, B. (2015). Designing Cross-linguistic Lexical Tasks (CLTs) for bilingual preschool children. In S. Armon-Lotem, J. de Jong & N. Meir (Eds.). *Methods for assessing multilingual children: disentangling bilingualism from Language Impairment*. Bristol: Multilingual Matters.
- Häyrynen, T., Serenius-Sirve, S., & Korkman, M. (2013). *Lukilasse 2*. Helsinki: Hogrefe Psykologien kustannus Oy.
- Kajamies, A., Poskiparta, E., Annevirta, T., Dufva, M., & Vauras, M. (2003). YTTTE, Luetun ja kuullun ymmärtämisen ja lukemisen sujuvuuden arviointi. [YTTTE, reading and listening comprehension and reading evaluation]. Jyväskylä, Finland: OTUK.
- Salmi, P., Järvisalo, E., Eklund, K., Polet, J. & Aro, M. (2011) *LukiMat: Oppimisen arviointi*. Jyväskylä: Niilo Mäki Instituutti.
- Wiig E. H., Semel E., Secord W. A. (2013). *Clinical Evaluation of Language Fundamentals*, 5th Edn. Bloomington, MN: Pearson Psychcorp.
- Wolf & Denckla, (2005). *Rapid automatized naming test*.

5 Instruments in Data Collection / Measures

5.1 Children's Assessments

5.1.1 Social-Emotional Attention

5.1.1.1 Overlap Task at 8 Months and 2.5, 5, and 9.5 Years

Social-emotional attention was studied with an overlap task (Figure 2; Aslin & Salapatek, 1975; Kataja et al., 2020; Peltola et al., 2008). The task examined attentional disengagement from a centrally presented neutral, happy, or fearful facial expression or a scrambled-face control stimulus to a lateral distractor. The face stimuli were color images (15.4° x 10.8°) of facial expressions of two female actors on a white background. The face stimuli were adopted from the study of Peltola et al. (2008). A scrambled-face control stimulus was created by randomizing the phase component of the fearful faces of the two models. The scrambled-face picture retained the low-level physical properties of the original face images (i.e., color and amplitude spectra; following the procedure described by Halit et al., 2004) but was not identifiable as a face after the phase information of the images had been randomized. At 8 and 30 months, the distractor stimuli (15.4° x 4.3°) were black-and-white checkerboards or vertically arranged circles. At 5 years, the contrast polarity of the distractor stimulus was reversed at a frequency of 10 Hz to increase the saliency of the distractor. At 9 years, the contrast polarity of the distractor stimulus was again reversed at a frequency of 10 Hz to increase the saliency of the distractor. The distractor began to flash after the child's gaze reached it.

Figure 2. Overlap Task

At 8 months, the task comprised two sets of 24 trials with a break consisting of three 4-second animations between the sets (Kataja et al., 2020). One set used the pictures of one actor. Before every trial, the infant's gaze was captured at the center of the screen with an audio-visual animation (e.g., a barking dog cartoon). During a 4000 ms trial, the happy, fearful, or neutral face or the scrambled-face stimulus was presented in a semi-random order in the center of the screen (each six times but no more than three times in a row in one set of trials). After 1000 ms, a peripheral distractor was presented, semi-randomly, to the left or right side of the face at the angle of 13.6° for the remaining 3000 ms. The lateral stimulus was presented on the same side of the screen no more than three times in a row. The measurement consisted of 48 trials altogether (12 trials per condition).

At 30 months, the task comprised 24 trials (Kataja et al., 2022). Before every trial, the infant's gaze was captured at the center of the screen with an audio-visual animation (e.g., a barking dog cartoon). During a 4000 ms trial, the happy, fearful or neutral face or the scrambled-face stimulus was presented in a semi-random order in the center of the screen (each six times but no more than three times in a row within one set of trials). After 1000 ms, a peripheral distractor was presented, semi-randomly, to the left or right side of the face at an angle of 13.6° for the remaining 3000 ms. The lateral stimulus was presented on the same side of the screen no more than three times in a row.

At 5 years, the task comprised 24 trials (6 trials per condition; Kataja et al., 2022). Before every trial, the child's gaze was captured at the center of the screen with an audio-visual animation (e.g., a ringing alarm clock). During a 4000 ms trial, the happy, fearful or neutral face or the scrambled-face stimulus was presented in a semi-random order in the center of the screen (each six times but no more than three times in a row within one set of trials). After 1000 ms, a peripheral distractor was presented, semi-randomly, on the left or right side of the face at an angle of 13.6° for the remaining 3000 ms. The lateral stimulus was presented on the same side of the screen no more than three times in a row.

At 9 years, the task comprised 60 trials (15 trials per condition). Before every trial, the child's gaze was captured at the center of the screen with a fixation circle. During a 4000 ms trial, the happy, fearful or neutral face or the scrambled-face stimulus was presented in a semi-random order in the center of the screen (each 15 times but no more than three times in a row in one set of trials). After 1000 ms, a peripheral distractor was

presented, semi-randomly, to the left or right side of the face at an angle of 13.6° for the remaining 3000 ms. The lateral stimulus was presented on the same side of the screen no more than three times in a row.

References

- Aslin, R. N., & Salapatek, P. (1975). Saccadic localization of visual targets by the very young human infant. *Perception & Psychophysics*, *17*(3), 293–302.
- Halit, H., Csibra, G., Volein, Á., & Johnson, M. H. (2004). Face-sensitive cortical processing in early infancy. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry and Allied Disciplines*, *45*(7), 1228–1234. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7610.2004.00321.x>
- Kataja, E.-L., Eskola, E., Pelto, J., Korja, R., Pajja, S.-P., Nolvi, S., Häikiö, T., Karlsson, L., Karlsson, H., & Leppänen, J. M. (2022). The stability of early developing attentional bias for faces and fear from 8 to 30 and 60 months in the FinnBrain Birth Cohort Study. *Developmental Psychology*, *58*(12), 2264–2274. <https://doi.org/10.1037/dev0001432>
- Kataja, E.-L., Karlsson, L., Leppänen, J. M., Pelto, J., Häikiö, T., Nolvi, S., Pesonen, H., Parsons, C. E., Hyönä, J., & Karlsson, H. (2020). Maternal depressive symptoms during the pre- and postnatal periods and infant attention to emotional faces. *Child Development*, *91*, e475–e490. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.13152>
- Peltola, M. J., Leppänen, J. M., Palokangas, T., & Hietanen, J. K. (2008). Fearful faces modulate looking duration and attention disengagement in 7-month-old infants. *Developmental Science*, *11*(1), 60–68. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-7687.2007.00659.x>

5.1.1.2 Free Viewing of Paired Pictures at 2.5, 5, and 9.5 Years

Free viewing of paired faces was examined with a task created in FinnBrain with face-pair stimuli consisting of one neutral and one emotional face or a scrambled-face control stimulus

(Figure 3; Eskola et al., 2023). Before every trial, the child's gaze was captured at the center of the screen with an audio-visual animation (e.g., a pig throwing a ball up and down; hands clapping). The face stimuli were color images of a female actor posing neutral, happy, sad, fearful, and angry facial expressions adopted from the NimStim set (pictures of "Actor 1"; Tottenham et al., 2009). The scrambled-face control stimulus was created by randomizing the phase component of the fearful faces of the model. The scrambled-face control stimuli retained the low-level physical properties of the original face images (i.e., color and amplitude spectra; following the procedure described by Halit et al., 2004) but were not identifiable as a face after the phase information of the images had been randomized.

Figure 3. Free viewing of paired faces

At 30 months, the task consisted of 36 trials with face pairs presented for 5000 ms. Each pair (i.e., neutral-neutral, neutral-happy, neutral-sad, neutral-fearful, neutral-angry, and neutral-scrambled face) was presented six times in a semi-random order (no more than two times in a row).

At 5 years, the task consisted of 32 trials with face pairs presented for 4000 ms. The pairs neutral-neutral, neutral-happy, neutral-sad, neutral-fearful, and neutral-angry were presented six times, and neutral-scrambled face two times in a semi-random order (no more than two times in a row).

At 9 years, the task consisted of 32 trials with face pairs presented for 3000 ms. The pairs neutral-neutral, neutral-happy, neutral-sad, neutral-fearful, and neutral-angry were presented six times, and neutral-scrambled face two times in a semi-random order (no more than two times in a row).

References

Eskola, E., Kataja, E.-L., Pelto, J., Tuulari, J. J., Hyönä, J., Häikiö, T., Hessels, R. S., Holmberg, E., Nordenswan, E., Karlsson, H., Karlsson, L., & Korja, R. (2023). Attention biases for emotional facial expressions during a free viewing task increase between 2.5 and 5 years of age. *Developmental Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/dev0001598>

Halit, H., Csibra, G., Volein, Á, & Johnson, M. H. (2004). Face-sensitive cortical processing in early infancy. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry and Allied Disciplines*, 45(7), 1228–1234. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7610.2004.00321.x>

Tottenham, N., Tanaka, J. W., Leon, A. C., McCarry, T., Nurse, M., Hare, T. A., Marcus, D., J., Westerlund, A., Casey, B., J., & Nelson, C. (2009). The NimStim set of facial expressions: Judgments from untrained research participants. *Psychiatry Research*, 168(3), 242–249. <https://doi.org/10.1038/jid.2014.371>

5.1.1.3 Always Look at the Happy Face -Task at 5 Years

Attentional control was examined with the *Always Look at the Happy Face* task, which is a FinnBrain adaptation of the task in the study of Lagattuta and Kramer (2017). The stimuli were 12 face-pair stimuli with one positive and one negative face and four face pairs with one positive and one neutral face. Each pair was presented three times. The face stimuli were color images of four women adopted from the NimStim set (Actors 1, 2, 5, and 7; Tottenham et al., 2009). All positive faces were expressing happiness. Negative facial expressions were from three categories: anger, fear, and sadness.

The task comprised two parts. The unrestricted part was presented first, and it included free viewing of the face pairs. The researcher started the trial when the child was looking at the pre-trial audio-visual animation on the center of the screen (e.g., a top spinning). The face pairs were presented for 4000 ms on the screen. This part comprised a total of 12 trials, three of each type. Only Actor 1 was used for this part. Each pair (i.e., happy-angry, happy-fearful, happy-sad, happy-neutral) was presented three times in a semi-random order such that the same pair was presented no more than two times in a row. The instructed part was presented second. At the beginning of this part, the researcher said, “Now, I am going to show you the same pictures on my computer. This time your job is to look only at the happy faces. Don’t look at the other faces.” Again, the researcher started the trial when the child was looking at the pre-trial audio-visual animation on the center of the screen. The face pairs were presented for 4000 ms on the screen. This part comprised a total of 36 trials, nine of each type. Each pair was presented nine times in a semi-random order such that the same pair was presented no more than two times in a row.

References

- Lagattuta, K. H., & Kramer, H. J. (2017). Try to look on the bright side: Children and adults can (sometimes) override their tendency to prioritize negative faces. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 146(1), 89–101. <https://doi.org/10.1037/xge0000247>
- Tottenham, N., Tanaka, J. W., Leon, A. C., McCarry, T., Nurse, M., Hare, T. A., Marcus, D., J., Westerlund, A., Casey, B., J., & Nelson, C. (2009). The NimStim set of facial expressions: Judgments from untrained research participants. *Psychiatry Research*, 168(3), 242–249. <https://doi.org/10.1038/jid.2014.371>

5.1.2 Observed Temperament

Child temperament was observed during the visits at 8 and 30 months, and additionally during the *Forbidden Toy* task at 5 years. All tasks and behavioral episodes were video-recorded, and child (and in some cases, caregiver) behaviors were later coded based on the video recordings (see details in the section “6. Coding Protocols”).

5.1.2.1 Negative Reactivity at 8 Months, 2.5, and 5 Years

Negative reactivity was observed at 8 months during the episode of *Gentle Arm Restraint by Parent*, derived from the *Laboratory Temperament Assessment Battery Prelocomotor* (Lab-TAB; Goldsmith & Rothbart, 1999), which is a standardized battery for assessing child temperament as a reaction to varying stimuli (Planalp et al., 2017). In the *Arm Restraint* episode, the infant was sitting on a highchair, with the parent sitting very close and almost behind the infant. The infants were given a sound-making and blinking toy (Figure 4) and were allowed to play with the toy for a period of 15 to 60 seconds. Next, the toy was retracted for 30 seconds while the parent held the infant's arms to prevent the infant from playing with the toy. After another play period, the retraction was repeated. The total duration of the episode was 2 minutes, or 3 minutes including instructions from the experimenter. Afterwards, overall negative reactivity, sadness, and anger were coded based on the video recording of the episode (see details in the section "6. Coding Protocols").

Figure 4. Toys used in the Gentle Arm Restraint episode

Negative reactivity was also assessed at 2.5 years of age using the episode *Attractive Toy in a Transparent Box* from the *Preschool Laboratory Temperament Assessment Battery* (*Preschool Lab-TAB*; Goldsmith et al., 1999). During this task, the experimenter presented a set of attractive toys to the child, and the child picked up the set of toys with which they wanted to play. The experimenter placed the toys in a locked transparent plastic box and removed the correct key, giving the child a set of incorrect keys. The child was then asked to open the box. The experimenter left the room, and the child stayed in the room with the parent for four minutes. The parents were instructed not to participate in the task by helping the child but to encourage them to keep trying if they stopped attempting to open the box. After the experimenter returned to the room, the box was opened and the child was told that they received the wrong keys; subsequently, the child was allowed to play with the toys again.

Child negative reactivity was also observed and coded during the *Forbidden Toy* (executive function) task at 5 years (see details in the description of executive function tasks and in the section "6. Coding Protocols").

References

- Goldsmith, H. H., & Rothbart, M. K. (1999). *The Laboratory Temperament Assessment Battery (LAB-TAB, Prelocomotor Version, Edition 3.1)*. Madison, Wisconsin: University of Wisconsin Press.
- Goldsmith, H.H., Reilly, J., Lemery, K.S., Longley, S., & Prescott, A. (1999). *The Laboratory Temperament Assessment Battery Preschool (Version 0.)*.
- Planalp, E. M., Hulle, C. V., Gagne, J. R., & Hill Goldsmith, H. (2017). The infant version of the laboratory temperament assessment battery (Lab-TAB): Measurement properties and implications for concepts of temperament. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.00846>

5.1.2.2 Fear / Behavioral Inhibition at 8 Months and 2.5 Years

At 8 months, infant fear was assessed during the episode *Masks* from the *Lab-TAB Prelocomotor* (Goldsmith & Rothbart, 1999), where the infant was presented with four different masks in order of increasing intensity and likelihood of eliciting a fear response (Figure 5). Infants sat on a highchair at the table, on which there was a high-wall plastic booth with curtains in the middle of the booth. The experimenter showed the infant four masks (a theater mask, old man, chunky, gas mask) through the curtain, always in a fixed order and for 10 seconds each, with a 5-second interval in between each mask. Altogether, the episode lasted 1 to 1.5 minutes. After this episode, there was also a 5-minute break for the infant to calm down. The parents were again told not to interfere or soothe the infant, but as some infants reacted strongly, the experimenters were allowed to terminate the experiment and let the mother soothe the infant.

Figure 5. The four masks showed for the infant in the Masks episode, organized in the order of presentation

At 2.5 years, child behavioral inhibition was observed during the episode *Popping Bubbles* from the *Preschool Lab-TAB* (Goldsmith et al., 1999) which is designed to elicit positive reactivity and physical activity (see 5.1.2.3). Children showing very low levels of positive reactivity and activity (the lowest 15%) could be considered behaviorally inhibited and shy based on previous research.

References

- Goldsmith, H. H., & Rothbart, M. K. (1999). *The Laboratory Temperament Assessment Battery (LAB-TAB, Prelocomotor Version, Edition 3.1)*. Madison, Wisconsin: University of Wisconsin Press.
- Goldsmith, H.H., Reilly, J., Lemery, K.S., Longley, S., & Prescott, A. (1999). *The Laboratory Temperament Assessment Battery Preschool (Version 0.)*.

5.1.2.3 Positive Reactivity / Exuberance at 2.5 and 5 Years

At 2.5 years, positive reactivity was observed during the episode *Popping Bubbles* from the Preschool *Lab-TAB* (Goldsmith et al., 1999). In this episode, the experimenter blows bubbles using a bubble gun and asks the child to pop the bubbles to elicit physical activity, exuberance, and positive affect. The episode consists of two trials: in the first trial, the experimenter demonstrates how to blow the bubbles, and the child is invited to do the same. In the second trial, the experimenter blows the bubbles using the bubble gun and encourages the child to engage in the activity of chasing the bubbles and popping them. The experimenter blows bubbles three times during each trial and asks the child to pop them with their hands, feet, and finally with any part of their body.

Child positive reactivity was also observed and coded during the *Forbidden Toy* (executive function) task at 5 years (see details in the description of executive function tasks and in the section “6. Coding protocols”).

References

- Goldsmith, H.H., Reilly, J., Lemery, K.S., Longley, S., & Prescott, A. (1999). *The Laboratory Temperament Assessment Battery Preschool (Version 0.)*.

5.1.2.4 (Emerging) Self-Regulation / Effortful Control at 8 Months, 2.5, and 5 Years

At 8 months, child attentiveness/perseverance was assessed using the *Blocks* episode, where the infant was sitting on a highchair by the table, with the parent sitting slightly behind on the left side of the infant. The infant was given a set of Lego blocks to play with on an area on the table limited by a wooden screen during a 3-minute episode. The parent was instructed not to interfere except for lifting up blocks that had fallen or for preventing any potentially dangerous situation (e.g., if the infant tried to climb out of the chair). The whole episode, including instructions from the experimenter, lasted for approximately 4 minutes.

Additionally, child self-regulation by gaze aversion was later coded from the episode *Gentle Arm Restraint by the Parent*, described in 5.1.2.1 (see also section 6. Coding Protocols).

At 2.5 years, child self-regulation using gaze aversion and distraction during the negative reactivity –eliciting episode *Attractive Toy in a Transparent Box* (Goldsmith et al., 1999) was coded separately based on the recordings (see the section “5.1.2.1” for description of the task and the section “6 Coding protocols” for coding). Additionally, child self-regulation/effortful control was assessed using the tasks (e.g., *Snack Delay*) described in section 5.1.3, Executive Functions.

Child self-regulatory behaviors (e.g., distraction, regulatory vocalizations) were also observed and coded during the Forbidden Toy (executive function) task at 5 years (see details in the description of executive function tasks and in the section “6. Coding Protocols”).

References

Goldsmith, H.H., Reilly, J., Lemery, K.S., Longley, S., & Prescott, A. (1999). *The Laboratory Temperament Assessment Battery Preschool (Version 0.)*.

5.1.3 Executive Functions

5.1.3.1 *A-not-B at 8 Months*

Infant EFs were assessed using one task, a modified *A-not-B* (*AB*) procedure measuring attention, inhibitory control (IC), and working memory (WM) (e.g., Diamond, 1985; Sun et al., 2009). The task was a delayed response task, that is, it required holding and updating the hiding location in mind and

inhibiting a prepotent response. We used a modified version of this *AB* task (Nolvi et al., 2018). The task started with an introduction trial, where interesting egg-like (or alternatively, a car toy, if the infant did not show interest in the egg toys) toys were placed on the table, and the infant was allowed to play with the toys. Next, a white cup was placed on the table, and the introduction trials were conducted by hiding the toy under the cup, drawing the infant’s attention to the experimenter by clapping their hands and saying “(Infant’s name), where is the toy?”, after which the infant was allowed to find the toy. This was repeated three times.

In the actual task, the toy was hidden under two identical blue cups (L = left or R = right) in a fixed order. The delay between hiding and searching was modified: The infant reached for the location of the toy in a fixed pattern on three delay levels (0, 2, and 4 seconds, with 0 meaning no delay between clapping the hands and letting the infant search for the toy). Each delay level included six trials, and the entire *AB* procedure included 18 trials. For example, in the first delay level, the series of trials was R-L-L-R-R-L. If the infant scored correctly in at least half of the six trials, they proceeded to the next delay level. The first level was always completed unless the child was too fussy or upset to continue with the task.

Consequently, the task duration lasted from 5 to 15 minutes depending on the infant’s performance. In each trial, the infant’s reaching for a location was scored either as correct or incorrect. All reaching behaviors that were initiated within 8 seconds were considered reaching. Infant performance was scored by the experimenter and verified later by a trained coder from the video. The coding demonstrated adequate inter-rater reliability (81% agreement across trials). The maximum score in the task was 18, with higher scores reflecting better EF performance. In addition to the main scores, the parents were asked whether the

child had previous experience with hiding games, and the child's interest in the experiment toys as well as behaviors (e.g., being exceptionally fussy or shy, affecting the child's performance) during the experiment were written down. The task was terminated in cases where the infant was seemingly tired, fearful, fussy, or uninterested.

References

- Diamond, A. (1985). Development of the ability to use recall to guide action, as indicated by infants' performance on AB. *Child Development*, 56(4), 868–883
- Nolvi, S., Pesonen, H., Bridgett, D. J., Korja, R., Kataja, E.-L., Karlsson, H., & Karlsson, L. (2018). Infant Sex Moderates the Effects of Maternal Pre- and Postnatal Stress on Executive Functioning at 8 Months of Age. *Infancy*, 23(2), 194–210. <https://doi.org/10.1111/inf.1220>
- Sun, J., Mohay, H., & O'Callaghan, M. (2009). A comparison of executive function in very preterm and term infants at 8 months corrected age. *Early Human Development*, 85(4), 225–230. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earlhumdev.2008.10.00>

5.1.3.2 Spin the Pots at 2.5 Years and 5 Years

Spin the Pots (Hughes & Ensor, 2005) is a multi-location search task used as a working memory measure. In *Spin the Pots* conducted at 2.5 years of age, the child searched for six stickers hidden in eight visually distinct pots on a Lazy Susan tray. The child was informed that there were not enough stickers for all the pots and was shown which pots remained empty. In each trial, the child was instructed to choose one pot that they believed contained a sticker. Before each search, the tray was covered with an opaque scarf and rotated 180 degrees.

The task was terminated when the child found all the stickers, or when the maximum number of trials (16) was reached. The maximum score in this task was 16. Each error reduced the score by one, so the final score was 16 minus the number of incorrect trials. Higher total scores reflected better performance.

In the *Spin the Pots* for 5-year-olds, the child searched for ten stickers hidden in front of the child in 12 visually distinct pots on a Lazy Susan tray. The child was informed that there were not enough stickers for all the pots and was shown which pots remained empty. In each trial, the child was instructed to choose one pot that they believed contained a sticker. Before each search, the tray was covered with

an opaque scarf and rotated 180 degrees. The task was terminated when the child found all the stickers, or when the maximum number of trials (20) was reached. To make the task more difficult, the pots were visually more similar to each other than in the task version that was used for the 2.5-year-olds. The maximum score in this task was 20. The final score was calculated by subtracting the number of incorrect trials from 20, so higher scores indicated better performance.

References

Hughes, C., & Ensor, R. (2005). Executive Function and Theory of Mind in 2 Year Olds: A Family Affair? *Developmental Neuropsychology*, 28(2), 645–668. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15326942dn2802_5

5.1.3.3 *Snack Delay at 2.5 Years*

Snack Delay task (Kochanska et al., 2000) measures inhibitory control. In this task, the child waits for a signal (a bell to ring) before taking a preferred snack (either candy or a raisin) placed under a transparent cup. The children were instructed to keep their hands on a mat placed on the table and wait for the experimenter to ring the bell. The child was told that when the bell rang, they could eat the snack.

In the task version used in the current study, the delay before the bell rang was modified from 10 to 60 seconds in length across the six trials. First, the bell was lifted to make it visible to the child. To progressively increase the inhibitory control demands of the task, the delay between the snack and ringing the bell varied across trials, after which the bell was rung according to the following instructions:

- (1) raise the bell at 5 seconds and ring it at 10 seconds;
- (2) raise the bell at 10 seconds and ring it at 20 seconds;
- (3) raise the bell at 15 seconds and ring it at 30 seconds;
- (4) raise the bell at 7 seconds and ring it at 15 seconds;
- (5) raise the bell at 20 seconds and ring it at 40 seconds; and
- (6) raise the bell at 20 seconds, hold it for 5 seconds, and put it down, then raise it again at 40 seconds and ring it at 60 seconds.

The trials were coded on a scale from 0 to 4:

0 = “Child eats the snack before the researcher touches the bell and rings it”

1 = “Child eats the snack after the researcher touches the bell but before the bell is rung”

2 = “Child touches the cup/bell before the bell is touched”

3 = “Child touches the cup/bell after the bell is touched but before it is rung”

4 = “Child does not touch the cup or the bell before the bell has rung”.

The videos were later coded with a focus on the child’s ability to hold their hands on the mat that was placed on the table. A maximum of two extra points were given based on the child’s ability. The coding was done based on video recordings.

0 = Not able to hold hands on the mat,

1 = At least one hand on the mat during the trial,

2 = Both hands on the mat during the trial (Spinrad et al., 2007).

The maximum score in this task was 36, with higher scores indicating better performance, calculated as the sum of performance points in each trial (0-4) and hand-on-mat points (0-2) across six trials.

References

- Kochanska, G., Murray, K. T., & Harlan, E. T. (2000). Effortful control in early childhood: Continuity and change, antecedents, and implications for social development. *Developmental Psychology*, 36(2), 220–232. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0012-1649.36.2.220>
- Spinrad, T. L., Eisenberg, N., & Gaertner, B. M. (2007). Measures of Effortful Regulation for Young Children. *Infant mental health journal*, 28(6), 606–626. <https://doi.org/10.1002/imhj.20156>

5.1.3.4 Delay of Gratification at 5 Years

Delay of Gratification (Beck et al., 2011) is a delay procedure measuring inhibitory control. The task was introduced to the child as a game, in which the child received a defined number of trials (nine) to choose a smaller, immediate reward (a smaller amount of child-preferred stickers, child-preferred edible treats, or 5-cent coins), or a larger, delayed reward to be taken home (a larger amount of child-preferred

stickers, child-preferred edible treats, or 5-cent coins). In the beginning of the task, the child was presented with the stickers, treats, and coins, and was allowed to choose their preferred options for the task.

On each trial, the child was informed of what they would receive (stickers/treats/coins), and only the amount depended on their choice. The rewards varied in a standardized order (coins, stickers, coins, stickers, treats, stickers, treats, coins, treats). For immediate rewards, the child was given 0 points, and for delayed rewards, the child was given 1 point. In accordance with the child's choice, the child received the rewards either immediately, or they were put in an envelope and given to the child when leaving the visit. The maximum score in this task was 9, with a higher score indicating better performance.

References

- Beck, D. M., Schaefer, C., Pang, K., & Carlson, S. M. (2011). Executive Function in Preschool Children: Test-Retest Reliability. *Journal of Cognition and Development: Official Journal of the Cognitive Development Society*, 12(2), 169–193. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15248372.2011.563485>

5.1.3.5 EF Touch at 5 Years

EF Touch (Willoughby et al., 2017) is a computerized test battery for children utilizing a touch screen monitor for tracking children's responses to the task. During testing, the child sat at a table with the touch screen positioned on a stand directly in front of them. *EF Touch* includes several EF tasks, of which three were selected for the FinnBrain study: *Arrows* (a spatial conflict task measuring the ability to inhibit a dominant response), *Pig* (a standard go/no-go task measuring inhibitory control), and *Farmer* (a visuospatial working memory task).

Arrows included 36 trials in which the child was instructed to touch the button corresponding to the direction the arrow was pointing. Two response buttons were displayed on the screen, one on the left, and one on the right. At first, arrows were presented in spatially congruent positions (i.e., above the button toward which the arrow pointed). As the task progressed, arrows were shown in incongruent positions (i.e., arrows appeared above the opposite button to the one to which they were pointing), requiring the child to inhibit the prepotent response. The task consisted of three sets of 12 trials, including 1) congruent, 2) incongruent, and 3) mixed conditions. Only incongruent trials from the incongruent and mixed conditions required inhibitory control. The maximum accuracy score (a proportion correct) was 1. A higher score represented better performance.

Pig comprised 40 trials with varying difficulty in no-go responses. The difficulty was manipulated by varying the number of go responses that preceded each no-go response in a fixed order. Children were instructed to respond as quickly as possible by touching a large green button whenever an animal appeared on the screen (go responses), except when the animal was a pig, in which case they were required to withhold their response (no-go responses). The maximum accuracy score (a proportion correct) was 1. A higher score represented better performance.

Farmer task consisted of 36 trials, in which a four-by-four grid of squares, referred to as the “farmer’s fields”, was displayed to the child. The child was instructed to assist the farmer by remembering the sequence of fields visited by a runaway animal. During each trial, a series of fields was highlighted sequentially. Following a 1500 ms delay, the child was required to reproduce the sequence by touching the fields in the same order in which they had been highlighted (i.e., the order in which the animal had visited them). Task difficulty increased as the animal visited more fields, meaning that the sequence length expanded, with the child asked to recall longer sequences (2-4 items). The maximum accuracy score (proportion correct) was 1. A higher score represented better performance.

References

Willoughby, M. T., Kuhn, L. J., Blair, C. B., Samek, A., & List, J. A. (2017). The test-retest reliability of the latent construct of executive function depends on whether tasks are represented as formative or reflective indicators. *Child Neuropsychology: A Journal on Normal and Abnormal Development in Childhood and Adolescence*, 23(7), 822–837. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09297049.2016.1205009>

5.1.3.6 Forbidden Toy at 5 Years

The *Forbidden Toy* task was constructed based on previous, similar tasks (e.g., Lewis et al., 1989). Children were seated facing away from the table. They were told that a surprise toy (a slime machine) would be placed behind their back on the table, but that they were not allowed to look at or play with the toy until the tester returned and gave their permission. The experimenter then left the room and observed the children via a live video feed for five minutes.

On rare occasions, when children showed strong signs of distress, the task was immediately interrupted and the child was comforted.

Upon returning, the tester stood in front of the children with a neutral facial expression for five seconds, before asking whether they had looked at the toy while the tester was not present. Irrespective of their response, the children were told that it was acceptable even if they had looked and were kindly encouraged to look at and play with the toy. In addition to coding whether the child looked or did not look, the task was later coded using a behavioral coding scheme developed specifically for this dataset (see the section “6 Coding Protocols”).

References

Lewis, M., Stanger, C., & Sullivan, M. W. (1989). Deception in 3-Year-Olds. *Developmental Psychology*, 25(3), 439–443. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0012-1649.25.3.439>

5.1.3.7 Cambridge Neuropsychological Test Automated Battery (CANTAB) at 9.5 Years

Children’s executive functions at the age of 9 years were assessed using four tablet-based tasks from the *Cambridge Neuropsychological Test Automated Battery (CANTAB; Sandberg, 2011)*: *Spatial Span (SSP)* measuring visuospatial working memory, *Spatial Working Memory (SWM)* measuring retention and manipulation of visuospatial information, *Multitasking Task (MTT)* measuring cognitive

flexibility and task switching, and *Intra–Extra Dimensional Set Shift (IED)* measuring set shifting and cognitive flexibility. These tasks targeted distinct components of executive functioning: *SSP* assessed visuospatial short-term memory capacity; *SWM* measured visuospatial working memory and strategic search behavior; *MTT* assessed attentional control, rule management, and inhibitory control; and *IED* captured cognitive flexibility and attentional set shifting. Before beginning the tasks, they were introduced to the children as games of varying length, and they were advised to listen carefully to the auditory instructions provided via the iPad. Children were asked whether they knew left from right and were instructed to hold their hands on both sides of the iPad (which was positioned upright on the table in front of the child) so they could respond quickly. Prior to the *SSP* task, children were additionally advised to press gently and informed that the iPad registered their touch if the box that was pressed changed color.

Spatial Span (SSP) is a test of visuospatial working memory based on the *Corsi Block - tapping* paradigm. In this task, some of the nine white squares displayed on the screen briefly changed color in a specific sequence. The child was instructed to observe the sequence and then reproduce it by touching the squares in the same order. The sequence length increased progressively throughout the task from two to nine squares changing color, making it increasingly demanding. At each sequence length, the child was given up to three attempts. The task was terminated if all three attempts at a given sequence length were unsuccessful.

Performance was scored as the longest sequence correctly reproduced (span length), with higher scores reflecting better visuospatial short-term memory.

Spatial Working Memory (SWM) assesses the retention and manipulation of visuospatial information and places substantial demands on executive control, particularly strategy use. At the beginning of each trial, three to eight colored boxes were displayed on the screen. The child was instructed to find hidden tokens by touching the boxes, with the goal of locating one token in each box and moving them to fill an empty column shown on the right-hand side of the screen. A critical rule, explained to the child, was that the computer never hides a token in the same box more than once; therefore, once a token has been found in a box, the child was told not to revisit it. The color and spatial arrangement of the boxes varied across trials to prevent the use of stereotyped search strategies. Key outcome measures include the number of errors (i.e., revisiting boxes known to be empty or already containing a token) and a strategy score, with fewer errors and more efficient strategy use indicating better performance.

Multitasking Task (MTT) assesses the ability to use multiple, potentially conflicting sources of information to guide behaviour. On each trial, an arrow appears either on the left or the right side of the screen, pointing either left or right. The child was required to make a left or right response based on task instructions. In training phases, children learn to respond either according to the direction of the arrow or according to the side of the screen on which it appears. In the test phase, each trial is preceded by a cue indicating which rule (direction or location) should be applied. Trials were separated by short intertrial intervals, during which the game prompted the child to “touch the screen when ready to continue,” at which point a new instruction was presented. Each trial was preceded by a cue indicating which rule should be applied. In some sections, the same rule was applied consistently across trials, whereas in the final phase the rules were randomly intermixed trial by trial. Additionally, on some trials, the direction of the arrow and its spatial location were incongruent, requiring inhibitory control. Key outcome measures included the cost of switching between intermixed versus consistent rules, as well as the cost associated with incongruent versus congruent trials, with lower costs reflecting better performance.

Intra–Extra Dimensional Set Shift (IED) assesses attentional set formation, maintenance, and shifting, and is conceptually related to the *Wisconsin Card Sorting Test*. In this task, children were required to learn through feedback which stimulus is correct according to an underlying rule. After six consecutive correct responses, the rule and/or stimulus properties changed. Early stages involve simple stimuli defined by a single dimension (e.g., pink shapes differing in form), whereas later stages introduce compound stimuli consisting of two dimensions (e.g., white lines overlaid on pink shapes). Initially, rule changes require intra-dimensional shifts, where the relevant dimension remains the same, followed by extra-dimensional shifts, where attention must shift to a previously irrelevant dimension. The use of abstract stimuli, the absence of a match-to-sample component, and the reliance on novel exemplars reduce confounding learning effects. Primary outcome measures include the number of errors and

stages completed, with fewer errors and more successfully completed stages indicating better performance.

References

Sandberg, M. A. (2011). Cambridge Neuropsychological Testing Automated Battery. In *Encyclopedia of Clinical Neuropsychology* (pp. 480–482). Springer, New York, NY. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-79948-3_169

5.1.3.8 EPELI (Executive Performance in Everyday Living) at 9.5 Years

The *EPELI (Executive Performance in Everyday Living) Short Form* for children (adapted from the *EPELI* created by Seesjärvi et al., 2023, hereafter referred to as *EPELI-S*) consisted of eight everyday task scenarios (task blocks) performed in a virtual apartment environment. Each task scenario lasted up to 60 seconds and comprised 4–6 subtasks, resulting in a total of 42 subtasks across the assessment and a total duration of

approximately 30 minutes. The tasks required participants to complete multistep, goal-directed activities in a naturalistic virtual reality (VR) setting with a head-mounted display (HMD). Task-irrelevant distractors were present throughout all task blocks to ensure a consistent level of environmental distraction. Visual distractors included a moderate amount of task-irrelevant clutter distributed evenly across the virtual apartment. Auditory distractors (approximately 50 events in total), including traffic noise, dog barking, coughing, and emergency vehicle sounds, were also evenly distributed across task blocks and presented at regular intervals of approximately 10 seconds. In addition, a fly distractor was included in each task block. The behavior of the fly was programmed to ensure an even distribution across blocks, such that the fly appeared at least once during each task block and, on each occurrence, moved directly in front of the participant's field of view.

Main five outcome measures used in the FinnBrain study (*total score*, *task efficacy*, *navigation efficacy*, *controller motion*, and *total actions*) are derived from task performance and interaction data recorded during the *EPELI-S*. *Total score* reflects the total number of correctly completed subtasks across all task blocks and indexes overall task performance. *Task efficacy* captures participants' focus on task-relevant goals and is defined as the proportion of actions necessary for successful subtask completion relative to all actions performed, with higher values indicating more efficient goal-directed behavior. *Navigation efficacy* indexes the efficiency of movement within the virtual environment and is calculated as the proportion of actions required for successful subtask completion relative to all actions performed, expressed as a percentage. *Controller motion* quantifies the total angular movement of the hand controller in degrees and serves as a general indicator of motor activity during task performance; although controller motion does not directly influence task success, extreme values may reflect increased motor restlessness or neuropsychiatric

symptomatology. *Total actions* represent the total number of interactions with the virtual environment. This includes all clicks performed during task execution, interactions generated by swinging the controller to hit the drums in the children's room, and clicks made during the instruction phase of each task block. This metric indexes task-irrelevant behavior independently of overall task success. In addition, in *EPELI-S*, prospective memory performance is assessed using time-based prospective memory (TBPM), defined as the number of time-based subtasks completed within ± 10 seconds of the target time; clock checks, reflecting the number of times the in-game clock is consulted as an indicator of active time monitoring; and event-based prospective memory (EBPM), defined as the number of event-based subtasks completed within 10 seconds of the onset of the relevant cue.

References

Seesjärvi, E., Puhakka, J., Aronen, E. T., Hering, A., Zuber, S., Merzon, L., Kliegel, M., Laine, M., & Salmi, J. (2023). EPELI: A novel virtual reality task for the assessment of goal-directed behavior in real-life contexts. *Psychological Research*, 87(6), 1899–1916. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00426-022-01770-z>

5.1.3.9 Emotional Go/No-Go Task at 9.5 Years

A FinnBrain version of the *Emotional Go/No-Go* task (Gee et al., 2014; Tottenham et al., 2011) was administered using the E-Prime software on a Dell computer. The *Emotional Go/No-Go* task measures cognitive control, emotion regulation, and emotion discrimination. The task consisted of a practice block and six task blocks. Children were presented with pictures of facial expressions from the Ekman Pictures of Facial Affect database (Ekman & Friesen, 1976) and instructed to press a button when a target facial expression (go) appeared, inhibiting this response when a distractor facial expression (no-go) was presented. The expressions were happy, fearful, angry, and neutral. Neutral and emotional expressions alternated as the go stimulus, which appeared 70% of the time, establishing a prepotent tendency to respond.

Pictures were presented in a random order, at the center of the screen at a visual angle of approximately 12° . Each stimulus was presented for 500 ms, followed by a 1,000 ms fixation period during which the child could respond. The *Emotional Go/No-Go* task was administered twice to examine the presence of a parental buffering effect: once, with the researcher sitting next to the child by the table, and once with the parent also present, sitting on the other side of the child by the table. When the parent was present, they were asked to fill in a questionnaire on the iPad and not speak or interact with the child during the task. The order of the administration (parent-present vs. no-parent-present conditions) was counterbalanced between visits. The main variables from this task were mean reaction time

for hits (in response to neutral faces in the context of happy no-go faces), false alarm rate (responses to no-go faces), and hit accuracy (the difference between the number of hits in response to go-faces).

References

- Ekman, P. and Friesen, W.V. (1976) Pictures of Facial Affect. Consulting Psychologists Press, Palo Alto, CA. -
References—Scientific Research Publishing. (n.d.). Retrieved January 20, 2026, from
<https://www.scirp.org/reference/ReferencesPapers?ReferenceID=1238187>
- Gee, D. G., Gabard-Durnam, L., Telzer, E. H., Humphreys, K. L., Goff, B., Shapiro, M., Flannery, J., Lumian, D. S., Fareri, D. S., Caldera, C., & Tottenham, N. (2014). Maternal Buffering of Human Amygdala-Prefrontal Circuitry During Childhood but Not During Adolescence. *Psychological Science*, 25(11), 2067–2078. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956797614550878>
- Tottenham, N., Hare, T. A., & Casey, B. J. (2011). Behavioral assessment of emotion discrimination, emotion regulation, and cognitive control in childhood, adolescence, and adulthood. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 2(MAR), 39. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2011.00039>

5.1.4 Parent–Child Interaction

5.1.4.1 Free-Play Situations at 8 Months, 2.5, 5, and 9.5 Years

Mother–child interaction was assessed in a video-recorded free-play situations. At 8 months, the mother was given a standard set of toys and asked to play for 20 min together with her child as they usually would at home.

At 2.5 years, the parent–child play episode included a 10-min free-play period and a 5-min snack time.

First, the mother was given a standard set of toys and asked to play for 10 min together with her child as they usually would at home. After that, they were asked to have a snack (juice and biscuits) together.

At 5 years, the mother–child interaction protocol included a 15-minute free-play session, a 5-minute structured task (the Labyrinth game), and a 5-minute snack time. During free play, the mother was given a standard set of toys and asked to play with her child for 15 min as they normally would at home. After that, they had 5 min to play with the Labyrinth game. The instructions for the child were: “*By using the two knobs, you can tilt the game board and guide the ball through the maze. Try to move the ball so that it doesn’t fall into the holes.*” The parent was allowed to guide but not to participate in the play. After the game, the mother and child were asked to have a snack (juice and biscuits) together.

At 9 years, the parent and child were guided to sit at the table and were provided with an Etch A Sketch board and a printed picture of a seahorse. They were told that there was no right or wrong way to play together, and the researcher would not comment on their interactions. They were instructed to draw the picture using the board, with the parent using one knob and

the child using the other. After 5 min of interaction, the researcher returned and presented the child with two baskets of toys for them to choose from. Then the child and parent were instructed to play freely for 10 min. The researcher was in the other room for the duration of both the Etch A Sketch and the free-play interactions.

The video-recorded free-play situations were analyzed with two different coding methods: unpredictability of maternal sensory signals (Davis et al., 2017) and the Emotional Availability (EA) Scales (Biringen, 2008; Biringen et al. 1998). Coding protocols are described in section 6.1.1.

References

- Biringen, Z. (2008). *The EA Professionals and Parent Curricula*. Available at <http://www.emotionalavailability.com>.
- Biringen, Z., Robinson, J., & Emde, R.N. (1998). *The Emotional Availability Scales (3rd ed.)*, unpublished manuscript, Department of Human Development & Family Studies, Colorado State University, Fort Collins, CO.
- Davis, E. P., Stout, S. A., Molet, J., Vegetabile, B., Glynn, L. M., & Sandman, C. A. (2017). Exposure to unpredictable maternal sensory signals influences cognitive development across species. *PNAS*, *114*(39), 10390–10395. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1703444114>

5.1.5 Neurodevelopment and Cognitive Abilities

5.1.5.1 INTERGROWTH-21st Neurodevelopment Assessment (INTER-NDA) at 2.5 Years

Neurodevelopment was measured using the *INTERGROWTH-21st Neurodevelopment Assessment (INTER-NDA)* at 2.5 years of age (Murray et al., 2018). It is a standardized, psychometrically valid, international, rapid assessment for children aged 22 to 30 months. Its 37 items form six subscales: cognitive, language, fine and gross motor, and positive and negative behavior, utilizing a mixed methodological

approach including direct testing, concurrent observation, and caregiver reports. All items were administered according to the manual and the assessor scored the performance on a five-point scale using an iPad application or paper sheets. The test is administered reliably by non-specialist assessors in an assessment time of 15–20 min (Fernandes et al., 2014). Its norms are international early child development standards, rather than population-specific

references, constructed from five low-risk, international populations according to WHO prescriptive guidelines (Fernandes et al., 2020). The maximum standardized score is 100 in all domains. For all domains, except negative behaviour, higher scores reflect better outcomes; for negative behaviour, lower scores reflect less negative behaviour. *INTER-NDA* thresholds for delay in development are >10th centile for no delay, <10th centile for any delay, 3rd–10th centile for mild-to-moderate delay, and <3rd centile for severe delay. In the present study, fewer than 10 children scored below the 10th centile in each domain.

References

- Fernandes, M., Stein, A., Newton, C. R., Cheikh-Ismail, L., Kihara, M., Wulff, K., De León Quintana, E., Aranzeta, L., Soria-Frisch, A., Acedo, J., Ibanez, D., Abubakar, A., Giuliani, F., Lewis, T., Kennedy, S., Villar, J., & for the International Fetal and Newborn Growth Consortium for the 21st Century (INTERGROWTH-21st). (2014). The INTERGROWTH-21st Project Neurodevelopment Package: A novel method for the multi-dimensional assessment of neurodevelopment in pre-school age children. *PLoS ONE*, 9(11), e113360. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0113360>
- Fernandes, M., Villar, J., Stein, A., Staines Urias, E., Garza, C., Victora, C. G., Barros, F. C., Bertino, E., Purwar, M., Carvalho, M., Giuliani, F., Wulff, K., Abubakar, A. A., Kihara, M., Cheikh Ismail, L., Aranzeta, L., Albernaz, E., Kunnawar, N., Di Nicola, P., Ochieng, R., ... Kennedy, S. (2020). INTERGROWTH-21st Project international INTER-NDA standards for child development at 2 years of age: an international prospective population-based study. *BMJ open*, 10(6), e035258. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2019-035258>
- Murray, E., Fernandes, M., Newton, C. R. J., Abubakar, A., Kennedy, S. H., Villar, J., & Stein, A. (2018). Evaluation of the INTERGROWTH-21st Neurodevelopment Assessment (INTER-NDA) in 2 year-old children. *PLOS ONE*, 13(2), e0193406. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0193406>

5.1.5.2 Wechsler Preschool and Primary Scale of Intelligence – Third Edition (WPPSI-III) at 5 Years

Cognitive abilities were assessed using the Finnish version of the *Wechsler Preschool and Primary Scale of Intelligence - Third Edition (WPPSI-III)*, which is a standardized and widely used measure of cognitive ability in young children from ages 2 years and 6 months to 7 years and 3 months (Wechsler, 2009). Three subtests were administered according to the instructions of the Finnish handbook: the

Similarities task measuring conceptual knowledge, the *Block Design* task measuring visuospatial ability, and the *Matrix Reasoning* task measuring visual abstract reasoning. These subtests were chosen as corresponding subtests can be found in the follow-up measure of the present study, the *Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children – Fourth Edition (WISC-IV)*, and, for example, in the studied short version of Wechsler's test, the *Wechsler Abbreviated Scale of Intelligence II (WASI-II)* (Wechsler, 2011). Only the starting points of the tasks deviated from the manual. In *Block Design*, the practice items between items 10 and 11 were administered first to all children. If a child made a mistake in the practice items or in items 11 or 12, the items were administered in reverse order from item 10 until the child solved two items correctly in a row. In *Similarities*, the three practice items were

administered to all children. If the child gave any wrong answers in the practice items, the task was started with item 4; otherwise, the task was started with item 9.

The standardized scale scores corresponding to the raw scores of the subtests were based on Finnish norms and yielded a mean of 10 and a standard deviation of 3, reflecting standardized mean performance in the population at each age. A standardized composite score of the *Performance Intelligence Quotient (PIQ)* was estimated using the *Block Design* and *Matrix Reasoning* tasks as instructed in the handbook (Wechsler, 2009). The mean for *PIQ* is 100, and the standard deviation is 15.

References

- Wechsler, D. (2009). *Wechsler Preschool and Primary Scale of Intelligence - Third Edition (WPPSI-III)*. Helsinki: Psykologien Kustannus Oy
- Wechsler, D. (2012). *Wechsler Preschool and Primary Scale of Intelligence – Fourth Edition (WPPSI-III)*. PEearson.
- Wechsler, D. (2011). *Wechsler Abbreviated Scale of Intelligence II (WASI-II)*. NCS Pearson, Inc.

5.1.5.3 Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children – Fourth Edition (WISC-IV) at 9.5 Years

Cognitive abilities were assessed using the Finnish version of the *Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children – Fourth Edition (WISC-IV)*, which is a standardized and widely used measure of cognitive ability in children from ages 6 years to 16 years and 11 months (Wechsler, 2010). Three subtests were conducted: the *Similarities* task measuring conceptual knowledge, the *Block Design* task measuring visuospatial ability, and

the *Matrix Reasoning* task measuring visual abstract reasoning. To speed up the testing, *Similarities* and *Matrix Reasoning* were started from the 12-year-old starting point if the child got full points on the practice items. If the practice items were incorrect, the usual protocol was followed according to the *WISC-IV* handbook. The researcher marked the child's responses on a paper form.

The standardized scale scores corresponding to the raw scores of the subtests were based on Finnish norms and yielded a mean of 10 and a standard deviation of 3, reflecting standardized mean performance in the population at each age. A standardized composite score of the *Performance Reasoning Index (PRI)* was estimated using the *Block Design* and *Matrix Reasoning* tasks as instructed in the handbook (Wechsler, 2010). The mean for *PRI* is 100, and the standard deviation is 15.

References

- Wechsler, D. (2010). *Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children – Fourth Edition (WISC-IV)*. Helsinki: Psykologien Kustannus Oy

5.1.6 Oral Language

5.1.6.1 Hearing Screen at 5 and 9.5 Years

Each ear was tested separately, one at a time. The presented pure-tone sounds lasted 1–2 seconds. The child passed the screening if they heard the tones of 500, 1000, 2000, and 4000 Hz at 20 dB in both ears.

5.1.6.2 Reynell Developmental Language Scales III (RDLS III) at 5 Years

Sentence-level receptive and expressive language skills were measured using the *Reynell Developmental Language Scales III (RDLS III)*, Finnish version; Korttesmaa et al., 2001), which is a standardized and widely used measure for children between 2 and 7 years. In the *RDLS III*, receptive and expressive language are divided into 20 subtests that measure different aspects of grammatical knowledge, such as understanding complex sentences or the formulation of questions and morphological verb forms. The test was conducted and scored according to the Finnish manual.

References

Korttesmaa, K., Merikoski, H., Warma, M.-L., & Varpela, V. (2001). *Reynellin kielellisen kehityksen testi [Reynell Developmental Language Scales]*. Psykologien Kustannus Oy.

5.1.6.3 Phonology Test at 5 Years

The phonological skills of five-year-old children were assessed using the *Phonology Test* (Kunnari et al., 2012). This test is designed for evaluating and monitoring the phonological development of Finnish-speaking children aged 2–6 years, as well as for identifying phonological disorders. The test includes two principal domains: phonotactic skills (including segmental, syllabic, and word-length structures, as well as the combination of speech sounds) and paradigmatic skills (consonant and vowel inventories). The test was conducted and scored according to the manual. During the assessment, children were asked to name a series of images presented to them. For children aged 3–6 years, administration time was approximately 10–15 min. Normative data include a sample of 300 Finnish children aged from 2 years to 6 years 11 months, including some children with mild speech and language development difficulties. Percentile values have been established for raw total scores.

References

Kunnari, Savinainen-Makkonen & Saaristo-Helin (2012). *Fonologiatesti*. Jyväskylä: Niilo Mäki Instituutti

5.1.6.4 Finnish Nonword Repetition Task at 5 and 9.5 Years

At 5 years, phonological working memory and phonological processing skills were measured using a nonword repetition task created for the FinnBrain Study (Saloranta et al., 2025). A list of 18 nonwords consistent with Finnish phonotactics was created based on an experimental 90-word and 90-nonword repetition task (Renvall, n.d.). It was created using the Finnish WordMill newspaper corpus containing 22.4-million-word tokens representing common

(monomorphemic) nouns in Finnish (Laine & Virtanen, 1999). The nonwords ($n = 90$) were created from the selected real words by changing 1–3 (mean 2.2) phonemes. Then, the WordMill corpus was used to retrieve bigram frequencies of each nonword, and the average bigram frequency for each nonword candidate was calculated. This information was used to select six nonwords for each length-category (4, 6, 8 sounds), making a total of 18 nonwords that were used in the present study. Speech sounds /r/ and /s/ were not included, as they are commonly still missing from the speech-sound repertoire of Finnish 5-year-olds (Saaristo-Helin et al., 2011), and care was taken not to include complex consonant clusters to reduce articulatory demands. The nonwords were balanced in length and bigram frequency calculated from the WordMill corpus. The nonwords were either (1) four, (2) six, or (3) eight speech sounds in length. The three lengths each included nonwords with (1) high or (2) low bigram frequency.

The nonwords of different lengths and bigram frequencies were arranged randomly into two lists. Children were randomly assigned to one of the presentation orders. The auditory stimuli were recorded in an anechoic room with a Marantz Professional PMD561 recorder in WAV format, digitizing at 44.1 kHz with 16-bit resolution. Noise reduction was conducted in Audacity, and 50 ms intensity onset and offset ramps were added to the stimuli.

Participants were instructed to repeat what they heard. The stimuli were played one by one. Replay was allowed only if the participant was speaking while the stimulus was played, or if an error with the speaker occurred. If a stimulus was played more than three times, the production of the nonword was excluded from the analysis. If the child failed to comply with the instructions of the task or skipped more than five of the nonword repetitions, they were excluded from the sample.

For the 9-year-olds, a list of 30 nonwords consistent with Finnish phonotactics was created in a similar manner while increasing length. Again, the selection of stimuli was based on an experimental 90-word and 90-nonword repetition task (Renvall, n.d.). Six to eight nonwords for each length category were selected according to word length and bigram frequency, resulting in a total of 30 nonwords. The nonwords were balanced in length and bigram frequency, calculated from the WordMill corpus. The nonwords were either (1) eight, (2) twelve, (3) fourteen, or (4) fifteen to sixteen speech sounds in length. The four lengths each included nonwords with (1) high or (2) low bigram frequency.

The auditory stimuli were recorded in an anechoic room with a Marantz Professional PMD561 recorder in WAV format, digitizing at 44.1 kHz with 16-bit resolution. Noise reduction was conducted in Audacity, and 50 ms intensity onset and offset ramps were added to the stimuli. The nonwords were arranged randomly into two lists. One of the presentation orders was randomly chosen for each child.

Participants were instructed to repeat what they heard. They were presented with the stimuli one by one from speakers attached to a computer. Replay was allowed only if the participant was speaking while the stimulus was played, or if a problem with the speaker occurred. The

productions were recorded with a Sennheiser lavalier microphone. The child was excluded from the sample if they failed to follow the instructions and produce what they heard from the loudspeakers, or if their voice was inaudible or distorted by a technological glitch.

References

- Laine, M., & Virtanen, P. (1999). *WordMill lexical search program [Computer software]*. Centre for Cognitive Neuroscience, University of Turku, Finland.
- Renvall, K. (n.d.). *Experimental 90-word and 90-nonword repetition tasks* (unpublished). Department of Psychology and Speech-Language Pathology, University of Turku.
- Saaristo-Helin, K., Kunnari, S., & Savinainen-Makkonen, T. (2011). Phonological development in children learning Finnish: A review. *First Language, 31*(3), 342–363. <https://doi.org/10.1177/014272371039679>
- Saloranta, E., Yada, A., McCauley, S., Yli-Savola, A., Savo, S., Renvall, K., Eskola, E., Fernandes, M., Korja, R., Karlsson, H., Karlsson, L., & Mainela-Arnold, E. (2025). Latent Profiles of Early Language Development in a Large Finnish-Speaking Sample of the FinnBrain Birth Cohort Study. *Journal of Speech, Language, and Hearing Research, 68*, 3989–4005. https://doi.org/10.1044/2025_JSLHR-24-00767

5.1.6.5 Recordings of 20-Minute Free-Play Sessions with an Examiner at 5 Years Coded for Mean Length of Utterance (MLU) and Measure of Disfluencies

Spontaneous everyday language use was measured with mean length of utterance (MLU) during free-play with a non-familiar adult (Saloranta et al., 2025). MLUs were calculated from language samples that were audio- and video-recorded during free-play with the examiner. During the play, the examiner encouraged the child to speak, for example, by commenting on the play and by asking open-ended questions. The duration of the free-play was approximately 20 min per child. The speech samples were recorded using a Marantz recorder in WAV format, digitized at 44.1 kHz with a 16-bit resolution. The speech samples were transcribed using professional-grade headphones. The samples were transcribed and analyzed using the Systematic Analysis of Language Transcripts (Miller & Iglesias, 2020). A maximum of 150 complete and intelligible utterances per sample were included. Samples were segmented into C-units (Miller et al., 2015). Self-revisions and repeated words were excluded. MLUs were calculated by dividing the morpheme count by the number of utterances. Thus, the higher the MLU, the higher the child's morphosyntactic skills. Children's speech samples obtained from play contexts with examiners were transcribed orthographically following the transcriptions conventions of the Systematic Analysis of Language Transcripts (SALT; Miller & Iglesias, 2020). The walkthrough option of the SoundScriber program (Breck, 2010) was used to facilitate the playback of the audio files. Professional-grade headphones were used to listen to the audio files. Transcription and segmentation of utterances and morphemes were carried out by master's level Speech and Language Pathology students. Inter-rater reliability was determined by a "golden standard" who independently transcribed 10% of total transcriptions per transcriber. Reliability for MLU varied from 89 to 96 percent among the transcribers, reaching an average of 93 percent.

Speech samples from the 5-year-old play sessions were coded for fluency. Speech samples were collected from 393 children, and 325 samples were determined to be long enough, comprising at least 300 words, and these samples were included in the final analyses.

The last 300–380 words of the samples were coded for speech fluency. Unintelligible words, and isolated affirmatives and negatives such as *yes*, *no*, and *okay* were not included in the word count. Affirmatives and negatives that were followed immediately by another word or phrase were retained. Each word was defined as fluent or disfluent. Each disfluent word was further coded as a stuttering-like disfluency (SLD) or other disfluency (OD) using a classification system of disfluency types, based on the system of Ambrose and Yairi (1999) and Jansson-Verkasalo et al. (2021). Total frequency and types of disfluencies were calculated per 100 syllables. A syllable-based count was considered more appropriate than a word-based count for the Finnish language (Jansson-Verkasalo et al., 2021). SLDs included sound repetitions, syllable repetitions, part-word repetitions, monosyllabic word repetitions, prolongations, blocks, and broken words. ODs included filled pauses, multisyllabic word repetitions, self-revisions, abandoned sentences, and phrase repetitions.

Fluency coding of transcriptions was carried out by a fluency-specialized speech and language pathologist together with two master’s-level Speech and Language Pathology students. Another speech and language pathologist specialized in fluency disorders served as the “gold standard” and independently coded at least 10% of each coder’s transcripts. Point-by-point reliability was calculated separately for the location of disfluencies and the type of disfluencies. Reliability of location was 94–95%, and for type 88–93%, across the three coders.

References

- Breck, E. (2010). SoundScriber [Computer software]. <https://www.softpedia.com/get/Multimedia/Audio/Audio-Players/SoundScriber.shtml>
- Miller, J., Andriacchi, K., & Nockerts, A. (2015). *Assessing language production using SALT Software. A clinician's guide to language sample analysis* (2nd ed.). SALT Software LLC.
- Miller, J., & Iglesias, A. (2020). *Systematic Analysis of Language Transcripts (SALT) (Version 20) [Computer software]*. SALT Software, LLC.
- Saloranta, E., Yada, A., McCauley, S., Yli-Savola, A., Savo, S., Renvall, K., Eskola, E., Fernandes, M., Korja, R., Karlsson, H., Karlsson, L., & Mainela-Arnold, E. (2025). Latent Profiles of Early Language Development in a Large Finnish-Speaking Sample of the FinnBrain Birth Cohort Study. *Journal of Speech, Language, and Hearing Research*, 68, 3989–4005. https://doi.org/10.1044/2025_JSLHR-24-00767
- Jansson-Verkasalo, E., Silvén, M., Lehtiö, I., & Eggers, K. (2021). Speech disfluencies in typically developing Finnish-speaking children – preliminary results. *Clinical Linguistics & Phonetics*, 35(8), 707–726. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02699206.2020.1818287>
- Yairi, E., & Ambrose, N. G. (1999). Early childhood stuttering I: persistency and recovery rates. *Journal of Speech, Language, and Hearing Research*, 42(5), 1097–1112. <https://doi.org/10.1044/jslhr.4205.1097>

5.1.6.6 Finnish Version of the Clinical Evaluation of Language Fundamentals 5 (CELF-5) at 9.5 Years

Oral language abilities were measured using a Finnish adaptation of the *Clinical Evaluation of the Language Fundamentals – Fifth Edition (CELF-5)*; Wiig et al., 2013). *CELF-5* is a standardized assessment of language abilities for ages 5-21 years. It has good internal consistency as well as structural and content validity (Denman et al., 2017; Wiig et al., 2013). The *CELF-5* for ages 9–21 consists of nine subtests (*Word Classes, Following Directions,*

Formulated Sentences, Recalling Sentences, Understanding Spoken Paragraphs, Word Definitions, Sentence Assembly, Semantic Relationships, and Pragmatics Profile).

We measured language ability using three of the subtests: *Word Classes, Formulated Sentences, and Recalling Sentences*. *Word Classes* is a 40-item subtest that evaluates the ability to understand the relationships among words based on semantic class features (Wiig et al., 2013). In *Word Classes*, the child was instructed to choose the two pictures or orally presented words that best go together. *Formulated Sentences* is a 24-item subtest that measures the ability to integrate semantically, grammatically, and pragmatically correct sentences using given prompt word(s) (Wiig et al., 2013). The child was instructed to formulate a spoken sentence using the word(s) given so that it fits the context of a stimulus book illustration. *Recalling Sentences* is a 26-item subscale measuring the child's ability to recall and reproduce sentence structures of increasing length, and syntactic complexity (Wiig et al., 2013). The child was instructed to listen carefully and repeat the spoken sentence exactly as the tester presented it. A higher score reflects better performance on each subtest.

References

- Denman, D., Speyer, R., Munro, N., Pearce, W. M., Chen, Y. W., & Cordier, R. (2017). Psychometric Properties of Language Assessments for Children Aged 4-12 Years: A Systematic Review. *Frontiers in psychology, 8*, 1515. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.01515>
- Wiig E. H., Semel E., Secord W. A. (2013). *Clinical Evaluation of Language Fundamentals*, 5th Edn. Bloomington, MN: Pearson Psychcorp.

5.1.6.7 Rapid Automatized Naming (RAN) at 9.5 Years

The Finnish adaptation of the *Rapid Automatized Naming* test (*RAN, NSN* in Finnish; Ahonen et al., 1999) was used to evaluate rapid automatized naming skills. The *RAN* is a standardized assessment of naming speed and accuracy normed for ages 6 to 12 years. It consists of six 10-row by 5-column matrices of 50 colors, numbers, letters, objects, a combination of numbers and letters, or a combination of colors, numbers and letters. The stimuli of each matrix (colors: black, red, yellow, green, blue; numbers: 2, 6, 9, 4, 7; letters: O, A, S, T, P; objects: car, house, fish, pen, ball) are repeated within each matrix. The child is instructed to name the stimuli in each matrix as quickly and accurately as possible. For each matrix, naming speed in seconds and the number of self-corrected and uncorrected errors were coded. The naming speed can be used as a continuous sum score, where a lower score reflects more fluent naming.

References

- Ahonen, T., Tuovinen, S., & Leppäsaari, T. (1999). *Nopean sarjallisen nimeämisen testi*. Niilo Mäki Instituutti & Haukkarannan koulu.

5.1.6.8 Narrative and Conversational Language Samples at 9.5 Years

A narrative language sample from naturalistic productions was elicited using a wordless picture book, *Frog, where are you?* (Mayer, 1969). This method, including the specific book, is widely used to elicit language samples (Gutiérrez-Clellen & Simon-Cerejido, 2009; Heilmann et al., 2016). The language sample began with the presentation of the book. The

children completed a shared book-reading activity with the experimenter reading a script corresponding to the book while the children were allowed to look through the picture book. After reading the book, children were asked to retell the story in their own words. If the children had difficulties retelling the story, the researcher elicited further narration using open-ended prompts such as “What happened next?”.

The narrative language sample was followed by approximately a 10-minute semi-structured conversation about the child’s daily life, school, family, and hobbies. Finally, time pressure was added to the narrative sample to elicit disfluency in utterances with a timed word-guessing game. All narratives were video- and audio-taped for later analysis, such as T-unit length, narrative structure, words produced per minute, percent stuttering-like disfluencies, and percent typical disfluencies. MP4 video files had a frame rate of 25 FPS, a mono audio channel with bit rate of 128kbps, and an audio sample rate of 32,000 Hz. Audio was recorded with a Sennheiser AVX lavalier microphone and saved in WAV format with a 1,411 kbps bit rate.

References

- Gutiérrez-Clellen, V. F., & Simon-Cerejido, G. (2009). Using language sampling in clinical assessments with bilingual children: challenges and future directions. *Seminars in speech and language, 30*(4), 234–245. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0029-1241722>
- Heilmann, J. J., Rojas, R., Iglesias, A., & Miller, J. F. (2016). Clinical impact of wordless picture storybooks on bilingual narrative language production: A comparison of the 'Frog' stories. *International journal of language & communication disorders, 51*(3), 339–345. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1460-6984.12201>
- Mayer, M. (1969). *Frog, where are you?* New York, NY: Dial.

5.1.6.9 L2 English Assessments: Test for Reception of Grammar, Second Edition (TROG-2) at 9.5 Years

Understanding of L2 English grammatical contrasts was evaluated using the *Test for Reception of Grammar, Second Edition* (TROG-2; Bishop, 2003). TROG-2 is an oral English language assessment tool for individuals aged 4 years to adulthood. The test consists of 20 grammatical constructs (prepositions, inflections, function words, relative clauses, etc.) each evaluated four times. Auditory stimuli were recorded, and children listened to them on a Dell Latitude 5520 laptop and through Bose Companion 2 III speakers and chose the best-fitting picture from four pictures in the stimulus book by pointing. TROG-2 is a standardized test, but it is not standardized as an L2 measurement or for the Finnish population, and due to that, standardized scores were not collected.

References

- Bishop, D. V. M. (2003). *Test for Reception of Grammar (TROG-2)*. London: Pearson.

5.1.6.10 L2 English Assessments: English Version of the Rapid Automated Naming Test at 9 Years

The English version of the *Rapid Automated Naming* test (RAN; Wolf & Denckla, 2005) was used to evaluate the ability to quickly name series of familiar items in English. The test measures word fluency and consists of six matrices of items, but due to the L2 evaluation, only three were used (objects, colors, and numbers). Children were instructed to name items as quickly and accurately as possible. All children completed a trial of naming all items at once to ensure familiarity with the items before timing. Accuracy (error rate) and the time required to name all items were recorded.

References

Wolf, M., & Denckla, M. B. (2005). *RAN/RAS: Rapid Automated Naming and Rapid Alternating Stimulus Tests*. Pro-Ed.

5.1.6.11 L2 English Assessments: Adaptation the Cross Linguistic Lexical Tasks (CLT)

Receptive vocabulary in English was measured using an adaptation of the American English version of the *Cross Linguistic Lexical Tasks* (CLT; Haman et al., 2015). The task was conducted on the online ViLLE platform via an iPad. The test consisted of 32 items. Children heard a target word and had to choose the correct one of four pictures.

References

Haman, E., Łuniewska, M., & Pomiechowska, B. (2015). Designing Cross-linguistic Lexical Tasks (CLTs) for bilingual preschool children. In S. Armon-Lotem, J. de Jong & N. Meir (Eds.). *Methods for assessing multilingual children: disentangling bilingualism from Language Impairment*. Bristol: Multilingual Matters.

5.1.7 Written Language

5.1.7.1 Lukilasse 2: Word Fluency and Dictated Words and Sentences at 9.5 Years

Word-level reading fluency was measured using the *Word Fluency* subtest from the standardized Finnish reading and writing test *Lukilasse 2* (Häyrynen et al., 2013). The child was instructed to read a list of Finnish words out loud as quickly and accurately as possible and to correct any mistakes they made. In the list, the words were short at the beginning, and they became longer toward the end. The time limit was 2 minutes. The

total score of the task was the number of correctly read words. In addition, the number of attempted, incorrect, and skipped words was coded as separate variables.

Writing accuracy was measured with the *Dictated Words and Sentences* subtest of *Lukilasse 2* (Häyrinen et al., 2013). The child was instructed to write the words and sentences with a pencil on paper. The child was allowed to use an eraser if they noticed any mistakes. The child scored 2 points for every correctly written word. Only one point was deducted if the compound word was written in two parts.

References

Häyrinen, T., Serenius-Sirve, S., & Korkman, M. (2013). *Lukilasse 2*. Helsinki: Hogrefe Psykologien kustannus Oy.

5.1.7.2 Non-Word Reading Task at 9.5 Years

Word-level reading fluency was measured using a 45-second reading task of a non-word list (Salmi et al., 2011). The non-words were based on Finnish phonotactics. The child was instructed to read the words out loud as quickly and accurately as possible and to correct any mistakes they made. In the list, the words were short at the beginning, and they became longer toward the end. The numbers of attempted, correct, incorrect, and skipped words within the 45-second time limit were recorded.

References

Salmi, P., Järvisalo, E., Eklund, K., Polet, J. & Aro, M. (2011) *LukiMat: Oppimisen arviointi*. Jyväskylä: Niilo Mäki Instituutti.

5.1.7.3 Lukimat: Text Level Reading Fluency at 9.5 Years

Text level reading fluency was measured using a Finnish text, “Gerbiili” (The Gerbil), from *LukiMat: Oppimisen arviointi* (Salmi et al., 2011). The child was instructed to read the text (253 words) as quickly and accurately as possible and to correct any mistakes they made. The number of attempted, correct, incorrect, and skipped words within the 90-second time limit was calculated.

References

Salmi, P., Järvisalo, E., Eklund, K., Polet, J. & Aro, M. (2011) *LukiMat: Oppimisen arviointi*. Jyväskylä: Niilo Mäki Instituutti.

5.1.7.4 YTTE: Reading Comprehension and Eye-tracking of Reading at 9.5 Years

Reading comprehension was measured using the text “Delfiini etsii kalaherkkuja” (“Dolphin Searches for Fish Treats”) taken from *YTTE* (Kajamies et al., 2003). *YTTE* is a standardized test assessing listening and reading comprehension (as well as reading fluency) of Finnish 2nd- and 3rd-grade children. It includes both narrative and expository texts, both simple and more complex. Simple texts have a single

theme, while complex texts include a thematic switch halfway through the text. The test also includes normative data from 210–230 pupils.

The dolphin text selected for this particular task was a complex expository text aimed at measuring reading comprehension at grade 3. The text consisted of 146 words, and it was presented on one screen using a double-spaced proportional Calibri font with a font size of 17. Children were instructed to read it silently at their own pace while their eye movements were recorded. The eye movements were recorded using an EyeLink1000+ eye tracker (SR Research Ltd, Toronto, Ontario, Canada). A nine-point calibration procedure was used before measurement. The maximum error in gaze detection in the validation phase was set to 1.0 degrees. A sampling frequency of 500 Hz was used. The text was presented on a 19” CRT monitor with 1,920 x 1,080 resolution and 144 Hz refresh rate. Prior to reading the text, the participant fixated on a target at the upper left corner of the monitor, after which the experimenter initiated the text screen. Prior to reading the experimental text, the participant read a short practice text, followed by two forced-choice questions (taken from *KUMMI 1*, Aro, 2002) to familiarize them with the eye-tracking procedure. Raw data consisted of x and y coordinates of the gaze on the screen, and many variables will be created based on this information, for example, gaze duration on individual words.

Reading the text was followed by three types of comprehension questions, which the participant answered orally: free recall, cued recall, and a recognition task, in the respective order. For free recall, the children were instructed to recall everything they could from the text. For cued recall, the children answered six open-ended questions about the text (e.g., “In which ways does the dolphin hunt for fishes in the sea?”). For the recognition task, the children were presented with six statements, and they had to state whether the sentence was correct or incorrect based on the text (e.g., “Dolphin does not like eating octopuses.” Y/N). During the answering of the questions, the participant did not see the text. Furthermore, their eye movements were not recorded during this part of the task. The answers were scored according to the test manual. The manual includes information on which of the six skill levels (1–2 = weak, 3–4 = intermediate, 5–6 = good) the participant performed in free recall and cued recall.

References

- Aro, T. (2002). *KUMMI 1. Arviointi, opetus ja kuntoutusmateriaaleja. Luetun ymmärtämisen teoriaa ja harjoituksia*. [KUMMI 1. Assessing, teaching and rehabilitation materials. Theory and exercises for reading comprehension.] Jyväskylä: Niilo Mäki Instituutti.
- Kajamies, A., Poskiparta, E., Annevirta, T., Dufva, M., & Vauras, M. (2003). *YTTE, Luetun ja kuullun ymmärtämisen ja lukemisen sujuvuuden arviointi*. [YTTE, reading and listening comprehension and reading evaluation]. Jyväskylä, Finland: OTUK.

5.1.7.5 2-Minute Addition Fluency Test at 9.5 Years

In the addition fluency task (Koponen & Mononen, 2010), children were asked to calculate as many single-digit additions (e.g., $1 + 3 = _;$ $9 + 5 = _$) as possible in 2-minutes' time. One point was given for each correct answer, and the sum of correct answers within the time limit (maximum 120) was recorded. In addition, the numbers of attempted, incorrect, and missing answers (items which the child had skipped) were coded as separate variables. The task form included a front page and two test sheets. The front page had two examples and two practice items. The two test sheets had three columns with 20 items on each.

Reference

- Koponen, T., & Mononen, R. (2010). *The 2-Minute Addition Fluency Test*. Unpublished task

5.1.7.6 2-Minute Subtraction Fluency Test

In the subtraction fluency task (Koponen & Mononen, 2010), children were asked to calculate as many subtractions (e.g., $5 - 2 = _;$ $12 - 8 = _$) as possible within a 2-minute time limit. Altogether 120 items, with a minuend below 20 and a single-digit subtrahend, were presented. One point was given for each correct answer, and the sum of correct answers within the time limit was recorded (maximum 120). In addition, the numbers of attempted, incorrect, and skipped items were coded. The task included a front page and two test sheets. The front page had two examples and two practice items, and the two test sheets had three columns with 20 items on each.

Reference

- Koponen, T., & Mononen, R. (2010). *The 2-Minute Subtraction Fluency Test*. Unpublished task

5.2 Children's Reports

5.2.1 Child's Questionnaires at 9.5 Years

Children filled in electronic questionnaires during the 9-year study visit. The questionnaire items were completed within the Research Electronic Data Capture (REDCap; <https://project-redcap.org/>) platform within the UTU network. They were allowed to read the questions by themselves or to listen to an audio version of each question in the REDCap.

5.2.1.1 Multisource Assessment of Children's Social Competence (MASCs)

Child's social competence in social environments was evaluated by self-report using the *Multisource Assessment of Children's Social Competence (MASCs)* (Junttila et al., 2006). The *MASCs* measures a child's behavior in different social contexts and has 15 items that are scored

on four response options, ranging from “never”, “rarely”, “frequently”, to “very frequently.” The *MASCS* has two main dimensions: prosocial and antisocial aspects of social behavior. These main dimensions are further divided into four sub-dimensions: cooperating skills and empathy (forming the prosocial dimension) and impulsivity and disruptiveness (forming the antisocial dimension).

Reference

Junttila, N., Voeten, M., Kaukiainen, A., & Vauras, M. (2006). Multisource assessment of children’s social competence. *Educational and Psychological Measurement, 66*(5), 874–895.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0013164405285546>

5.2.1.2 Emotion Regulation Strategies Questionnaire (FEEL-KJ-2)

Child’s emotion regulation strategies were measured by the *Emotion Regulation Strategies Questionnaire (FEEL-KJ-2)*; Cracco et al., 2015), which measures adaptive and maladaptive emotion regulation strategies in response to different emotions. In this study, only the 30-item measure of fear was used. The adaptive strategies consist of behaviors such as problem solving, distraction, forgetting, acceptance, humour enhancement, cognitive problem solving, and reevaluation. The maladaptive strategies consist of giving up, withdrawal, rumination, self-devaluation, and aggressive actions. The items were rated on a five-point scale, ranging from “almost never”, “rarely”, “sometimes”, “often”, to “almost always”, with higher scores indicating a higher level of adaptive or maladaptive emotion regulation strategies.

Reference

Cracco, E., Van Durme, K., & Braet, C. (2015). Validation of the FEEL-KJ: An Instrument to Measure Emotion Regulation Strategies in Children and Adolescents. *PLoS ONE, 10*(9), e0137080.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0137080>

5.2.1.3 Security Scale

The *Security Scale* (Kerns et al., 1996) was developed to assess children's perceptions of security in parent-child relationships in middle childhood and early adolescence. Items on the Security Scale tap the following: (a) the degree to which children believe a particular attachment figure is responsive and available; (b) children's tendency to rely on the attachment figure in times of stress; and (c) children's reported ease and interest in communicating with the attachment figure. The measure is composed of 15 items that are rated on a 4-point scale using Harter's (1982) "Some kids... Other kids..." format. Each item is scored on a 4-point scale, with higher scores indicating a more secure attachment.

Reference

Kerns, K. A., Klepac, L., & Cole, A. (1996). *Security Scale*. APA PsycTests. <https://doi.org/10.1037/t17560-000>

5.2.1.4 Questionnaire of Unpredictability in Childhood (QUIC)

The *Questionnaire of Unpredictability in Childhood (QUIC)*; Glynn et al., 2019) is a series of questions that respondents endorse as applying to their lives in childhood. Examples include “I experienced changes in my custody arrangement”, “At least one of my parents regularly checked that I did my homework”, and “At least one of my parents was disorganized.” The

measure comprises 38 items that are endorsed as either “yes” or “no”. The final scale consists of five subscales: Parental Involvement, Parental Predictability, Parental Environment, Physical Environment, and Safety and Security, with a higher score indicating greater exposure to unpredictability in the environment until 12 years of age. This measure was used as a self-report during the study visit at 9.5 years.

References

Glynn, L. M., Stern, H. S., & Howland, M. A. (2019). Measuring novel antecedents of mental illness: the Questionnaire of Unpredictability in Childhood. *Neuropsychopharmacology*, *44*, 876–882. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41386-018-0280-9>

5.2.1.5 Usage of Digital Games

Children’s use of digital games was assessed with 10 questions created by the study group that measured their previous use of VR glasses, the devices they typically play on (e.g., computer, PlayStation, mobile phone), and how many days per week and hours per day they spend playing. They were also asked how many years they have been regularly playing digital games.

5.2.1.6 Highly Sensitive Child Scale (HSC-C)

Child temperament trait of Environmental Sensitivity was assessed using the *Highly Sensitive Child Scale (HSC-C)*; Pluess et al., 2018) which is a short 12-item version designed to assess children and adolescents' (9 to 18 years) sensitivity to the environment. Each item was scored on a 7-point scale ranging from “not at all” to “very much”. The items form three subscales: *Low Sensory Threshold*, *Aesthetic Sensitivity*, and *Ease of Excitation*, which can be summed to one score to reflect the child’s overall environmental sensitivity.

Reference

Pluess, M., Assary, E., Lionetti, F., Lester, K. J., Krapohl, E., Aron, E. N., & Aron, A. (2018). Environmental sensitivity in children: Development of the Highly Sensitive Child Scale and identification of sensitivity groups. *Developmental Psychology*, *54*(1), 51–70. <https://doi.org/10.1037/dev0000406>

5.2.1.7 Self-Efficacy in Reading and Math

Self-efficacy has been found to be an important predictor of various learning-related outcomes. Reading and math self-efficacy were measured with 12 items assessing children’s confidence in mastering everyday reading and math tasks (e.g., “How confident you are that you can read a long book?”; Peura et al., 2006). These items were based on Bandura’s (2006) original research on the development of self-efficacy. Each item was scored on a 7-point scale ranging from “I am absolutely confident that I can’t” to “I am absolutely confident that I can”.

Reference

Bandura, A. (2006). Guide for constructing self-efficacy scales. In F. Pajares & T. Urdan (Eds.), *Self-efficacy beliefs of adolescents* (Vol. 5, pp. 307-337). Information Age Publishing

Peura, P., Aro, T., Räikkönen, E., Viholainen, H., Aro, M. (2022). Children’s Academic Self-efficacy in Reading and Reading Development—From Theory to Practice. In: Khine, M.S., Nielsen, T. (eds) *Academic Self-efficacy in Education*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-8240-7_8

5.2.1.8 Achievement Emotions Questionnaire-Elementary School (AEQ-ES)

Reading- and math-related emotions were measured by the *Achievement Emotions Questionnaire-Elementary School (AEQ-ES)*; Lichtenfeld et al., 2012). The *AEQ-ES* assesses students' enjoyment, anxiety, and boredom pertaining to three types of academic settings (i.e., attending class, doing homework, and taking tests and exams). Scale construction was based on Pekrun's (2006) control-value theory of achievement emotions. A total of 16 items were used in this study to measure children's enjoyment and anxiety in math and reading. The answers were scored on a 5-point scale ranging from "totally disagree" to "totally agree", and higher sum scores indicated higher enjoyment or anxiety.

References

- Lichtenfeld, S., Pekrun, R., Stupnisky, R.H., Reiss, K., & Murayama, K. (2012). Measuring students' emotions in the early years: The Achievement Emotions Questionnaire-Elementary School (AEQ-ES). *Learning and Individual Differences, 22*(2), 190-201. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2011.04.009>
- Pekrun, R. (2006). The control-value theory of achievement emotions: Assumptions, corollaries, and implications for educational research and practice. *Educational Psychology Review, 18*, 315–341. doi:10.1007/s10648-006-9029-9

5.2.1.9 Health Behaviour in School-Aged Children (HBSC)

Children's well-being at school was measured by the *Health Behaviour in School-aged Children* survey (HBSC; Kämpfi et al., 2012). The measure consists of 12 questions that form four scales measuring: a) emotional engagement with school, b) quality of student relations, c) workload, and d) student-teacher relations in the school environment. The items were scored on a 5-point scale ranging from "totally disagree" to "totally agree", with higher sum scores indicating higher school well-being.

Reference

- Kämpfi, K., Välimaa, R., Ojala, K., Tynjälä, J., Hapasalo, I. & Kannas, L. (2012). *Koulukokemusten kansainvälistä vertailua 2010 sekä muutokset Suomessa ja Pohjoismaissa 1994-2010: WHO-Koululaistutkimus (HBSC-Study)*. Opetushallitus, Terveyden edistämisen tutkimuskeskus, Jyväskylän yliopisto. Koulutuksen seurantaraportit; 2012, 8. <https://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-13-5245-4>

5.2.1.10 Peer Network and Dyadic Loneliness Scale (PNDL)

The *Peer Network and Dyadic Loneliness (PNDL)*; Hoza et al., 2000) Scale is designed to assess children's loneliness at multiple levels of peer relationships. Specifically, this scale measures loneliness associated with a lack of involvement in a social network and the absence of a close dyadic friendship. The measure consists of 10 questions that are rated on a 4-point scale using "Some kids...Other kids..." format, constructing factors for social and emotional loneliness. Higher sum scores in these factors indicate a higher level of social or emotional loneliness.

Reference

- Hoza, B., Bukowski, W. M., & Beery, S. (2000). Assessing Peer Network and Dyadic Loneliness. *Journal of Clinical Child Psychology, 29*(1), 119–128. https://doi-org.ezproxy.utu.fi:2443/10.1207/S15374424jccp2901_12

5.2.1.11 Revised Olweus Bully/Victim Questionnaire (OBVQ)

The *Revised Olweus Bully/Victim Questionnaire (OBVQ)* (Olweus, 1996) assesses perpetration and victimization related to specific forms of bullying (i.e., verbal, exclusion, physical, spreading false rumors, having personal items stolen/damaged, or cyberbullying). The measure consists of 18 questions on victimization or bullying other students, as well as how often that happens, ranging from “not at all”, “once or twice”, “two or three times a month”, “once a week”, or “several times a week”. We also asked whom the child has told about bullying and whether the bullying has stopped, decreased, or increased after that. The measure is mainly used as a categorized variable showing how often the child has been victimized or has acted as a bully.

Reference

Olweus, D. (2006). *Revised Olweus Bully/Victim Questionnaire (OBVQ)* [Database record]. APA PsycTests. <https://doi.org/10.1037/t09634-000>

5.2.1.12 Short Mood and Feelings Questionnaire (SMFQ)

The *Short Mood and Feelings Questionnaire (SMFQ)* (Costello & Angold, 1988) is a screening tool for depression in children and adolescents, and it consists of phrases regarding how a child has been feeling or acting in the past two weeks. The six questions were scored using three options ranging from “1 = true”, “2 = sometimes true”, or “3 = not true”. Lower sum scores on the *SMFQ* suggest more severe depressive symptoms. The 6-item *SMFQ* has been validated in the Finnish population (Talja et al., 2022). The *SMFQ* and the *SCARED* (reversed, described in 5.2.1.13) can be summed to create a total symptom scale.

References

Costello, E. J., and Angold, A. (1988). Scales to assess child and adolescent depression: checklists, screens, and nets. *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 27(6), 726–737.

Talja T, Rantanen A, Koivisto A-M, Fröjd S, Ikonen R, Joronen K. (2022). Early identification of depressive symptoms in school-aged children: Psychometric properties and validation of a new short version of Short Mood & Feelings Questionnaire. *Scandinavian Journal of Caring Sciences*, 36, 393–403. <https://doi.org/10.1111/scs.13042>

5.2.1.13 Screen for Child Anxiety Related Disorders (SCARED)

The *Screen for Child Anxiety Related Disorders (SCARED)* (Birmaher et al., 1999) is intended for youth aged 9–18 years old, and is a useful measure for generalized anxiety disorder, social anxiety disorder, phobic disorders, and school anxiety problems. The measure consists of five questions, and each question measures the frequency or intensity of symptoms or behaviors. This assessment has been found to be both a valid and reliable measure of general anxiety symptoms in research settings. The answers were scored using three options ranging from “1 = never or almost never”, “2 = sometimes or to some extent”, or “3 = often or always”. Higher sum scores on the *SCARED* suggest more severe anxiety symptoms. The *SMFQ* (described in 5.2.1.12) and *SCARED* (reversed) can be summed to create a total symptom scale.

Reference

Birmaher, B., Brent, D. A., Chiapetta, L., Bridge J., Monga S., & Baugher, M. (1999). Psychometric Properties of the Screen for Child Anxiety Related Emotional Disorders (SCARED): a replication study. *The Journal of*

the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry's, 38(10), 1230-6. doi: [10.1097/00004583-199910000-00011](https://doi.org/10.1097/00004583-199910000-00011)

5.2.1.14 Health-Related Quality of Life in Children and Adolescents, KINDL^R

The *Health-Related Quality of Life in Children and Adolescents* (KINDL^R; Ravens-Sieberer & Bullinger, 1998a, 1998b) is a generic instrument for assessing health-related quality of life in children and adolescents aged 3 years and older. The measure consists of four questions measuring the feeling of sickness, such as stomach ache or headache. The answers are coded “yes = 2”, “no = 1”, and summed together, with higher sum scores indicating more somatic problems.

Reference

- Ravens-Sieberer, U. & Bullinger, M. (1998a). Assessing health related quality of life in chronically ill children with the German KINDL: first psychometric and content-analytical results. *Quality of Life Research*, Vol. 4, No 7
- Ravens-Sieberer, U. & Bullinger, M. (1998b). News from the KINDL-Questionnaire – A new version for adolescents. *Quality of Life Research*, 7, 653.
(<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1023/B:QURE.0000004424.99048.86#preview>)

5.2.1.15 Pediatric Pain Screening Tool (PPST)

The *Pediatric Pain Screening Tool (PPST)*; Simons et al., 2015) is a 9-item screening tool designed to identify factors associated with adverse outcomes among children and youth who present with pain complaints. The answers were coded “yes = 1”, “no = 0”, and summed together, with higher scores indicating more psychosomatic problems.

Reference

- Simons, L. E., Smith, A., Ibagon, C., Coakley, R., Logan, D. E., Schechter, N., Borsook, D., & Hill, J.C. (2015). Pediatric Pain Screening Tool: rapid identification of risk in youth with pain complaints. *Pain*. 156(8), 1511-1518. doi: [10.1097/j.pain.000000000000199](https://doi.org/10.1097/j.pain.000000000000199). PMID: 25906349; PMCID: PMC4504741.

5.2.1.16 Digital Media Use

Children reported their digital media use on typical weekdays and weekends. They were asked how much they use mobile phones, watch TV, use a computer or laptop, or play games (i.e., PlayStation or Xbox). The answers were coded on a scale: “not at all”, “30 min”, “1 h”, “2 h”, “3 h”, “4 h”, “5 h”, and “6 h or more”.

5.2.1.17 Hobbies

Children reported whether they had any hobbies (sport or other). They also reported how many times a week they participated in their hobby. Answers ranged from “once a week” to “5 times a week or more”.

5.2.1.18 Friends

Children were asked how many close friends they have. The answer options were “none”, “one”, and “two or more”.

Children were also asked whether they feel lonely. The answer options were “not at all”, “sometimes”, and “often”.

5.2.1.19 Chronic Sleep Reduction Questionnaire (CSRQ)

Child’s sleep was measured using the *Chronic Sleep Reduction Questionnaire (CSRQ)* (Dewald et al., 2012), an assessment tool that measures symptoms of chronic sleep reduction and therefore accounts for sleep need and sleep debt. The 20-item *CSRQ* consists of four scales: *Shortage of Sleep* (six items), *Irritation* (five items), *Loss of Energy* (five items), and *Sleepiness* (four items), with reference to the previous 2 weeks. Only the *Loss of Energy* scale was used in this study.

Reference

Dewald, J.F., Short, M. A., Gradisar, M., Oort, F. J., & Meijer, A. M. (2012). The Chronic Sleep Reduction Questionnaire (CSRQ): a cross-cultural comparison and validation in Dutch and Australian adolescents. *Journal of Sleep Research, 21*(5), 584–94. doi: [10.1111/j.1365-2869.2012.00999.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2869.2012.00999.x). Epub 2012 Feb 14. PMID: 22329363.

5.3 Parental Questionnaires About the Child

Parents had the option to complete the questionnaires either in paper form sent by mail or electronically sent by e-mail until the child reached five years of age. After this point, at the 9-year follow-up assessments, parents completed the questionnaires in the Research Electronic Data Capture (REDCap, <https://project-redcap.org/>) platform within the UTU network. The links to the REDCap questionnaires were sent to the parents by e-mail directly from REDCap.

5.3.1 Mental Health

5.3.1.1 Brief Infant-Toddler Social and Emotional Assessment (BITSEA) at 2 Years

The *Brief Infant-Toddler Social and Emotional Assessment (BITSEA)* is a brief 42-item version of the Infant-Toddler Social Emotional Assessment, created for screening socio-emotional problems and competencies among 12–36-month-olds in pediatric settings (Alakortes et al., 2015; Briggs-Gowan et al., 2004). The questionnaire includes dimensions measuring internalizing and externalizing symptoms, dysregulation problems, maladaptive behaviors, and socio-emotional competence. Parents provided responses to statements using a 3-point Likert scale (0 = not true/rarely, 1 = somewhat true/sometimes, 2 = very true/often). The questionnaire comprised 31 items measuring socioemotional problems and 11 items measuring competencies.

References

Alakortes, J., Fyrstén, J., Carter, A. S., Moilanen, I. K., & Ebeling, H. E. (2015). Finnish mothers’ and fathers’ reports of their boys and girls by using the Brief Infant-Toddler Social and Emotional Assessment (BITSEA). *Infant Behavior and Development, 39*, 136–147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infbeh.2015.02.016>

Briggs-Gowan, M. J., Carter, A. S., Irwin, J. R., Wachtel, K., & Cicchetti, D. V. (2004). The Brief Infant-Toddler Social and Emotional Assessment: Screening for social-emotional problems and delays in competence. *Journal of Pediatric Psychology, 29*(2), 143–155. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jpepsy/jsh017>

5.3.1.2 Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ) at 4, 5, and 9 years

The behavioral symptoms were assessed using the *Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ)* (Goodman, 2001), completed by parents at the child's age of 4 and 5 years and by parents and teachers at 9.5 years. The *SDQ* is a widely used and validated tool for screening of socio-emotional problems and competencies of 3- to 16-year-olds. Parents were asked to evaluate the child's behavior over the last six months. The questionnaire included 25 questions, and the answer options were "not true", "somewhat true", and "certainly true". Item examples include: "Considerate of other people's feelings", "Restless, overactive, cannot stay still for long", and "Often complaining of headaches, stomach-aches or sickness". The questionnaire forms the main scale of total difficulties, which is further divided into subscales of *Emotional Symptoms*, *Conduct Problems*, *Hyperactivity/Inattention*, *Peer Relationship Problems*, and *Prosocial Behavior*. Higher scores reflect more problems, except for Prosocial Behavior, where higher scores reflect higher prosociality.

Reference

Goodman, R. (2001). Psychometric properties of the strengths and difficulties questionnaire. *American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 40 (11), 1337–1345. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00004583-200111000-00015>

5.3.1.3 Child Behavior Checklist (CBCL) for Parents at 5 and 9.5 Years

Child's social and emotional problems were measured using the Finnish version of the *Child Behavior Checklist (CBCL)* (Achenbach, 2001), completed by parents when the child was 5 years old (version for 1.5–5-year-olds) and 9.5 years old (version for ages 6–18-year-olds). The *CBCL* questionnaire at age 5 consists of 99 items, and at 9.5 years of 113 items. The answer options were "not true", "somewhat or sometimes true", and "very true or often true".

In both versions, the measure forms two broad categories: *Internalizing and Externalizing Problems*, as well as *Total Problem Scale*. In addition, in the version for children aged 1.5–5 years, seven syndrome scales are available (*Emotionally Reactive*, *Anxious/Depressed*, *Somatic Complaints*, *Withdrawn*, *Sleep Problems*, *Attention Problems*, and *Aggressive Behavior*). In the version for children aged 6–18 years, eight syndrome scales are available (*Anxious/Depressed*, *Withdrawn/Depressed*, *Somatic Complaints*, *Social Problems*, *Thought Problems*, *Attention Problems*, *Rule-Breaking Behavior*, and *Aggressive Behavior*).

In addition, DSM-oriented scales can be calculated for both versions of the questionnaire. In *CBCL* assessments, syndrome scales are typically used to provide a detailed symptom profile, broadband scales to summarize internalizing and externalizing problem levels, and DSM-oriented scales to align symptom patterns with diagnostic domains. Interpretation is generally based on T-scores, where values ≥ 65 indicate borderline and ≥ 70 clinical-range elevations.

Reference

Achenbach, T. M., & Rescorla, L. A. (2001). Manual for the ASEBA School-Age Forms & Profiles. Burlington, VT: University of Vermont, Research Center for Children, Youth, and Families. <https://www.nctsn.org/measures/child-behavior-checklist-ages-6-18>

5.3.2 Social-Emotional Development

5.3.2.1 Multisource Assessment of Children's Social Competence (MASCs) at 5 and 9 years

Child's social competence in social environments was evaluated using the *Multisource Assessment of Children's Social Competence (MASCs)*; Junttila et al., 2006), completed by parents when the child was 5 years old and by parents, a teacher, and the child herself/himself at 9.5 years. The *MASCs* measures a child's behavior in different social contexts and includes 15 items scored on four response options ranging from "never", "rarely", "frequently", to "very frequently." The *MASCs* has two main dimensions: prosocial and antisocial aspects of social behavior. These main dimensions are further divided into four subdimensions: *Cooperating Skills* and *Empathy* (forming the prosocial dimension) and *Impulsivity* and *Disruptiveness* (forming the antisocial dimension).

Reference

Junttila, N., Voeten, M., Kaukiainen, A., & Vauras, M. (2006). Multisource assessment of children's social competence. *Educational and Psychological Measurement, 66*(5), 874–895.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0013164405285546>

5.3.3 Temperament and Executive Functions

5.3.3.1 Infant Behavior Questionnaire Revised IBQ-R at 6 and 12 Months

Parent-reported temperament information was gathered from participants in the whole cohort using the Finnish version of the Infant Behavior Questionnaire-Revised Short Form (IBQ-R SF; Gartstein & Rothbart, 2003; Putnam et al., 2014) at 6 and 12 months. The IBQ-R is a widely used and validated measure for assessing infant temperament, utilizing items that can be rated by parents as objectively as possible without requiring comparison to other children. Both parents participating in the study were asked to respond to 91 items and assess their infant's behavior across a range of everyday situations during the previous week, using a 7-point scale ranging from "never" to "always". The questionnaire comprises three main dimensions, under which there are 14 subscales: *Negative Reactivity* (contains subscales *Sadness, Distress to Limitations, Fear, and Falling Reactivity*), *Orienting/Regulation* (contains subscales *Low Intensity Pleasure, Cuddliness, Duration of Orienting, and Soothability*), and *Positive Reactivity/Surgency* (contains subscales of *Smiling/Laughter, Vocal Reactivity, High Intensity Pleasure, Activity Level, Approach, and Perceptual Sensitivity*).

Reference

Gartstein, M. A., & Rothbart, M. K. (2003). Studying infant temperament via the Revised Infant Behavior Questionnaire. *Infant Behavior and Development, 26*(1), 64–86.
[https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0163-6383\(02\)00169-8](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0163-6383(02)00169-8); Finnish translation: Professor Katri Rääkkönen-Talvitie and the Developmental Psychology Research Group, University of Helsinki, Finland
Putnam, S. P., Helbig, A. L., Gartstein, M. A., Rothbart, M. K. & Leerkes, E. (2014). Development and Assessment of Short and Very Short Forms of the Infant Behavior Questionnaire-Revised. *Journal of Personality Assessment, 96*, 445–458.

5.3.3.2 Early Childhood Behavior Questionnaire Short Form ECBQ at 2 Years

Child temperament at 24 months was assessed using the *Early Childhood Behavior Questionnaire-Short Form (ECBQ-SF)*; Putnam et al., 2006), which is a validated and widely used measure for the assessment of toddler temperament. Both parents were asked to respond to 107 items assessing the child's behavior in everyday situations during the past two weeks and rate them on a scale from 1 to 7 ("never" to "always"). The *ECBQ* consists of 19 subscales that fall under three main dimensions: *Negative Reactivity* (consisting of subscales *Discomfort, Fear, Sadness, Frustration, Soothability, Motor Activation, Perceptual Sensitivity, and Shyness*), *Positive Reactivity/Surgency/Extraversion* (consisting of subscales *Impulsivity, Activity Level, High Intensity Pleasure, Sociability, and Approach*), and *Effortful Control* (consisting of subscales *Inhibitory Control, Low Intensity Pleasure, Cuddliness, Attentional Focusing, and Attentional Shifting*).

Reference

Putnam, S. P., Gartstein, M. A., & Rothbart, M. K. (2006). Measurement of fine-grained aspects of toddler temperament: The Early Childhood Behavior Questionnaire. *Infant Behavior and Development, 29*(3), 386–401. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infbeh.2006.01.004>; Finnish translation: Professor Katri Räikkönen-Talvitie and the Developmental Psychology Research Group, University of Helsinki, Finland

5.3.3.3 Children's Behavior Questionnaire CBQ 36 at 4 and 5 Years

At 4 and 5 years of age, child temperament was assessed by both parents using the *Children's Behavior Questionnaire Very Short Form and Short Form (CBQ VSF/SF)*; Rothbart et al., 2001). The very short form of the scale was administered to the whole cohort at 5 years of age, and the short form to the parents of children who participated in the visit at 5 years of age. Additionally, the *Effortful Control* scale from the very short form was administered to all children at 4 years of age. In this scale, the parents rate their children's behavior in everyday situations based on the past six months on a scale from 1 to 7 ("never" to "always"). The very short form of the *CBQ* includes 36 items and comprises the three main dimensions: *Negative Reactivity, Positive Reactivity/Surgency/Extraversion* and *Effortful Control*. The short form additionally enables the assessment of 13 fine-grained subdimensions that fall under the main dimensions: *Anger, Discomfort, Fear, Sadness, and Soothability* (reversed) comprising the dimension of *Negative Reactivity*; *Activity Level, High Intensity Pleasure, Impulsivity, and Shyness* comprising the dimension of *Positive Reactivity/Surgency/Extraversion*; and *Attention Focusing, Inhibitory Control, Low Intensity Pleasure, and Perceptual Sensitivity* comprising the dimension of *Effortful Control*.

Reference

Rothbart, M. K., Ahadi, S. A., Hershey, K. L., & Fisher, P. (2001). Investigations of temperament at three to seven years: The Children's Behavior Questionnaire. *Child Development, 72*(5), 1394–1408. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8624.00355>; Finnish translation: Professor Katri Räikkönen-Talvitie and the Developmental Psychology Research Group, University of Helsinki, Finland

5.3.3.4 Early Adolescent Temperament Questionnaire - Revised (EATQ-R) at 9.5 Years

Temperament at 9.5 years was assessed using the parents' reports of the *Early Adolescent Temperament Questionnaire - Revised Short Form (EATQ-R SF)*; Capaldi & Rothbart, 1992).

The *EATQ-R* is designed to assess temperament and self-regulation via an adaptation of scales used in studies of children and adults aged 9–15 years. The short form consists of 62 items scored on a scale from 1 to 7 (“almost never true” to “almost always true”). The scale can be used to construct 10 subscales: *Activation Control*, *Affiliation*, *Attention*, *Fear*, *Frustration*, *High Intensity Pleasure/Surgency*, *Inhibitory Control*, *Pleasure Sensitivity*, *Perceptual Sensitivity*, *Shyness*, and further, 3 or 4 main dimensions: *Negative Reactivity*, *Positive Reactivity*, *Effortful Control* (and *Affiliativeness*).

Reference

Capaldi, D. M., & Rothbart, M. K. (1992). Development and Validation of an Early Adolescent Temperament Measure. *The Journal of Early Adolescence*, 12(2), 153-173. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0272431692012002002> (Original work published 1992); Finnish translation: Professor Katri Räikkönen-Talvitie and the Developmental Psychology Research Group, University of Helsinki, Finland

5.3.3.5 Highly Sensitive Child Scale Parent Version (HSC-P) at 9.5 Years

Child environmental sensitivity was assessed using the *Highly Sensitive Child Scale-Parent Report (HSC-P)*; Pluess et al., 2018) which is the short 12-item version designed to assess children’s and adolescents’ sensitivity to the environment. Each item was scored on a 7-point scale ranging from “not at all” to “very much”. The items form three subscales: *Low Sensory Threshold*, *Aesthetic Sensitivity*, and *Ease of Excitation*, which can be summed to create one score reflecting Overall Environmental Sensitivity.

Reference

Pluess, M., Assary, E., Lionetti, F., Lester, K. J., Krapohl, E., Aron, E. N., & Aron, A. (2018). Environmental sensitivity in children: Development of the Highly Sensitive Child Scale and identification of sensitivity groups. *Developmental Psychology*, 54(1), 51–70. <https://doi.org/10.1037/dev0000406>

5.3.3.6 Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function, Second Edition, Parent Form (BRIEF2) at 5 and 9.5 Years

The *Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function* questionnaire, second edition (*BRIEF2*), was developed to assess everyday behavioral manifestations of children’s (ages 5–18) everyday behaviors related to goal-directed behavior and executive functions (Gioia et al., 2002; Hendrickson & McCrimmon, 2018). Parents completed the *BRIEF2* measure (Gioia et al., 2015) when the child was 5 and 9.5 years old. It includes 63 items concerning a child’s difficulties in specific behaviors. The answers were scored on a 3-point scale — “never”, “sometimes”, or “often” — with higher scores indicating more severe executive functioning problems. The questionnaire forms the scales of *Behavioral Regulation*, *Emotional Regulation*, *Cognitive Regulation*, and the *Global Executive Index*.

Reference

Gioia, G. A., Isquith, P. K., Guy, S. C., & Kenworthy, L. (2015). *Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function, Second Edition (BRIEF®2) Parent Form* [Assessment instrument]. PAR.

- Gioia, G. A., Isquith, P. K., Retzlaff, P. D., & Espy, K. A. (2002). Confirmatory Factor Analysis of the Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function (BRIEF) in a Clinical Sample. *Child Neuropsychology*, 8(4), 249–257. <https://doi-org.ezproxy.utu.fi:2443/10.1076/chin.8.4.249.13513>
- Hendrickson, N. K., & McCrimmon, A. W. (2018). Test Review: Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function®, Second Edition (BRIEF®2) by Gioia, G. A., Isquith, P. K., Guy, S. C., & Kenworthy, L. *Canadian Journal of School Psychology*, 34(1), 73-78. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0829573518797762> (Original work published 2019)

5.3.4 Speech and Language

5.3.4.1 *MacArthur-Bates Communicative Development Inventories, Words and Gestures (CDI-WG) at 14 months*

At 14 months, we used quantitative measures of child vocabulary and gesture as assessed by the *MacArthur-Bates Communicative Development Inventories (MCDI; Fenson et al., 1994; Lyytinen, 1999)*, *Words and Gestures (CDI-WG)*. The CDI is completed by a caregiver, typically a parent. The *CDI-WG* for infants contains one section for *Actions and Gestures* with five subcategories: *First Communicative Gestures, Games and Routines, Actions with Objects, Pretending to be a Parent, and Imitating Other Adult Actions*. For first communicative gestures, the reporter indicates whether the gesture in question is used often, sometimes, or not at all by the infant, whereas for the remaining subcategories the reporter indicates whether the gesture or action is used or not.

From the *CDI-WG* at 14 months, we also used the receptive vocabulary measure, which contains a comprehensive list of common words. The reporter checks whether the infant is perceived to understand the word (*Receptive Vocabulary*) or understand *and* use the word (*Expressive Vocabulary*), or not.

Reference

- Fenson, L., Dale, P. S., Reznick, J. S., Bates, E., Thal, D. J., Pethick, S. J., Tomasello, M., Mervis, C. B., & Stiles, J. (1994). Variability in early communicative development. *Monographs of the Society for Research in Child Development*, 59(5). <https://doi.org/10.2307/1166093>. i–185.
- Lyytinen, P. (1999). *Varhaisen kommunikaation ja kielen kehityksen arviointimenetelmä. A Method for Assessing Early Communication and Language*. Child Research Center of the University of Jyväskylä and the Niilo Mäki Institute.

5.3.4.2 *MacArthur-Bates Communicative Development Inventories, Words and Word Combinations (CDI-WS) at 2.5 Years*

At 30 months, we used additional measures of word use and word combination as assessed by the *MacArthur-Bates Communicative Development Inventories, Words and Word Combinations (CDI-WS; Fenson et al., 1994; Lyytinen, 1999)*.

The CDI-version for toddlers (*CDI-WS*) also contains a checklist of words in different semantic categories for reporting which words the child understands and produces (*Expressive Vocabulary*). From the *CDI-WS*, we used the checklist of words for assessing *Expressive Vocabulary*, as well as the number of morphemes in the three longest reported phrases used by the toddler to calculate Maximal Utterance Length (M3L). Additionally, the

instrument contains checklists for assessing the development of morphology and syntax, where the reporter chooses from the alternatives “not yet”, “sometimes”, or “often” for items representing different morphological skills (e.g., verb inflections, plurals, possessive form).

Reference

- Fenson, L., Dale, P. S., Reznick, J. S., Bates, E., Thal, D. J., Pethick, S. J., Tomasello, M., Mervis, C. B., & Stiles, J. (1994). Variability in early communicative development. *Monographs of the Society for Research in Child Development*, 59(5). <https://doi.org/10.2307/1166093>. i–185.
- Lyytinen, P. (1999). *Varhaisen kommunikaation ja kielen kehityksen arviointimenetelmä. A Method for Assessing Early Communication and Language*. Child Research Center of the University of Jyväskylä and the Niilo Mäki Institute.

5.3.4.3 Child’s Past Health History and Language Development at 5 Years

This questionnaire includes home-grown questions about the child's past health history, language development, language development interventions, and information on speech fluency.

5.3.4.4 Children’s Communication Checklist Second Edition (CCC-2) at 9.5 Years

The *Children’s Communication Checklist Second Edition (CCC-2; Bishop et al., 2003; Finnish adaptation; Bishop, 2015)* is a standardized questionnaire designed to evaluate children’s communication skills and vulnerabilities in pragmatic language development. The CCC-2 is completed by a caregiver, typically a parent. The questionnaire consists of 70 questions across 10 domains: *Speech, Syntax, Semantics, Coherence, Inappropriate Initiation, Stereotyped Language, Use of Context, Nonverbal Communication, Social Relations, and Interests*.

The first four scales assess language structure, vocabulary, and discourse. The following four scales evaluate pragmatic aspects of communication. The last two scales assess behaviors that are often areas of weaknesses in children with autism spectrum disorder. For each scale, there are five items describing difficulties in communication and two items describing communication strengths. Each question is rated on a 4-point scale ranging from “0 = less than once a week (or never)” to “3 = several times (more than twice) a day (or always)”. The CCC-2 was scored according to the manual.

References

- Bishop D. V. M. (2003). *The Children's Communication Checklist: CCC-2 Manual. 2nd edition*. London: The Psychological Corporation.
- Bishop DVM. (2015). The Children's Communication Checklist: CCC-2. *Lasten Kommunikointitaitojen Kysely, toinen painos* (Yliherva, A., Loukusa, S. and Väisänen, R. (trans.) Helsinki: Hogrefe Psychologien Kustannus Oy. (Original work published in 2003).

5.3.4.5 Child’s Past Health History, Language Development, and Second Language Exposure at 9.5 Years

Home grown questions about the child's past health history, language development, language-development interventions, information on speech fluency, parental education level, and

multilingual context (strongest language, languages learned later, language exposure at home and school, language used in different contexts, and media exposure — questions about language use) were asked as follows:

A) Child's immediate family

1. Parent(s)' profession, educational level, L1 language, L2 language(s),
2. Sibling's biological sex, educational level, L1 language, L2 language(s).

B) Basic information about the mother's health during pregnancy and child's health

1. Duration of pregnancy, child's birth weight, dichotomous (yes/no) questions about complications during labor
2. Dichotomous questions about feeding difficulties during childhood, hearing problems, vision problems, family history of hearing or vision impairment, childhood ear infections, physical trauma, head trauma, surgical procedures, medication use, and diagnosis of ADHD/ADD or autism.

C) Speech, language, and learning

1. Questions about the age of first words and word combinations, family history of language development difficulties, parental concern regarding child's language development, any referrals to speech and language pathology assessment, and support received in daycare or at school.
2. Language and learning support within the immediate family, speech-language therapy, individualized education, and learning difficulties
3. Questions about speech fluency included the occurrence of speech disfluency and the occurrence of secondary symptoms of disfluency

D) Multilingual context

1. Strongest language, languages learned later, language exposure at home and school, and language used in different contexts.

5.3.5 Child's Health

5.3.5.1 *The Reports of Child's Medication at 9.5 Years*

Parents reported whether the child had regular medications, for what purpose the medication was used, and whether the child had taken any medication before the study visit.

5.3.5.2 *Brief Infant Sleep Questionnaire (BISQ) at 6 Months and 1 Year*

Mothers reported their perceptions of their infants' sleep and sleep difficulties at 6 months and 1 year using the *Brief Infant Sleep Questionnaire (BISQ)*, which was developed to screen infant sleep quality for both research and clinical purposes and has been shown to be significantly correlated with actigraphy and sleep diary-based measures (Sadeh, 2004). The *BISQ* consists of the following ten sleep-related items reported by a parent:

- 1) nighttime sleep duration,
- 2) daytime sleep duration,

- 3) number of night awakenings per night,
- 4) duration of wakefulness during the nighttime,
- 5) sleep-onset time for the night,
- 6) settling time for the nighttime sleep,
- 7) method of falling asleep (e.g., “while feeding” or “in bed alone”),
- 8) sleeping arrangement (e.g., “infant crib in a separate room”, or “in parents’ bed”),
- 9) preferred body position while sleeping, and
- 10) parental perception of the infant’s sleep as problematic.

Items 1–6 are open-ended, whereas for items 7-10 response options are provided. The data includes all items described above.

References

Sadeh, A. (2004). A brief screening questionnaire for infant sleep problems: validation and findings for an Internet sample. *Pediatrics*, 113(6): 570-7. DOI: 10.1542/peds.113.6.e570

5.3.5.3 Children’s Bedtimes at 2, 4, 5, and 9.5 Years

Mothers reported their children's bedtimes at two, four, five, and nine years by answering four questions. The questions assessed

- 1) the time at which the child falls asleep on weekdays/when attending childcare/school,
- 2) the time at which the child falls asleep on weekends/when not attending childcare/school,
- 3) the time at which the child wakes up on weekdays/when attending childcare/school, and
- 4) the time at which the child wakes up on weekends/when not attending childcare/school.

Responses were given on a 15-point scale with half-hour time intervals, ranging from 7:00 p.m. to 2:00 a.m. for bedtime and from 5:00 a.m. to 12:00 p.m. for wake-up time. The questions were originally used in the Health Behaviour in School-Aged Children – A WHO Cross-National Study and were adopted from Tynjälä et al. (1993).

References

Tynjälä, J., Kannas, L., & Välimaa, R. (1993). How young Europeans sleep. *Health Education Research*, 8(1), 69–80. <https://doi.org/10.1093/her/8.1.69>

5.3.5.4 Sleep Disturbance Scale for Children (SDSC) at 2, 4, 5, and 9.5 Years

Mothers reported their perceptions of their children’s sleep and sleep difficulties at two, four, five, and nine years using the *Sleep Disturbance Scale for Children (SDSC)* questionnaire, which was developed as an overall measure of sleep disturbances for use in research and clinical purposes (Bruni et al., 1996). Internal consistency and test-retest reliability of the questionnaire are high. The *SDSC* originally consists of 26 Likert-type items from which a total score and six subscales can be calculated. For all items, response options are provided.

The subscales represent some of the most common sleep difficulties in childhood: *Disorders of Initiating and Maintaining Sleep (DIMS)*, *Sleep Breathing Disorders (SBD)*, *Disorders of Arousal (DA)*, *Sleep-Wake Transition Disorders (SWTD)*, *Disorders of Excessive Somnolence (DES)*, and *Sleep Hyperhydrosis (SHY)*. For the FinnBrain adaptation, the items from the *DIMS*

and the *SBD* subscales were included at two, five, and nine years, whereas at four years, only the items from the *DIMS* were included. Across all four age points, an item measuring daytime somnolence (from the *DES* subscale) was included in the FinnBrain adaptation.

References

Bruni, O., Ottaviano, S., Guidetti, V., Romoli, M., Innocenzi, M., Cortesi, F., & Giannotti, F. (1996). The Sleep Disturbance Scale for Children (SDSC). Construction and validation of an instrument to evaluate sleep disturbances in childhood and adolescence. *Journal of sleep research*, 5(4), 251–261. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2869.1996.00251.x>

5.3.6 Learning and School Environment

5.3.6.1 Homework Situations at 9.5 Years

The parents reported how often the child has homework in math, reading, and writing (Salminen et al., 2021-2023). The answer options were “not at all”, “rarely”, “a couple of times a week”, “several days a week”, and “once a day/daily”. Parents also reported how long the child spends doing homework during the day and how long, on average, parents help with the homework “0–15 min”, “15–30 min”, “30–45 min”, “45–60 min”, and “more than 60 min”.

References

Salminen, J., Lerkkanen, M.-K. & Torppa, M. (2021–2023). Interaction, Development & Learning (VUOKKO) -study. Early School Years. Unpublished data. University of Jyväskylä, Finland.

5.3.6.2 Task Value in Homework Situations at 9.5 Years

Task value in homework situations was examined with a questionnaire modified from the *Task Value Scale* (Aunola et al., 2006). Parents reported the child’s opinions and emotions when doing homework in four items, such as “my child enjoys doing math...”, “my child is anxious about doing math...”, “my child enjoys reading...”, and “my child is anxious about reading...” The answer options were: “never”, “rarely”, “sometimes”, “often”, and “always”.

References

Aunola, K., Leskinen, E. and Nurmi, J.-E. (2006), Developmental dynamics between mathematical performance, task motivation, and teachers' goals during the transition to primary school. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 76, 21–40. <https://doi.org/10.1348/000709905X51608>

5.3.6.3 Behavioral Strategy Rating Scale (BSRS) at 9.5 Years

Parents reported their child’s behavior when doing math, reading, and writing tasks using the *Behavioral Strategy Rating Scale (BSRS)* (Aunola et al., 2000; Zhang et al., 2011). The questions were: “Does the child easily start doing something else when homework becomes difficult? Does the child actively try to cope with difficult tasks? Does the child easily give up trying? Does the child show activity or persistence while working on homework? If a task doesn’t go well, does the child start doing random things instead?” Answers were rated on a 5-point scale ranging from “not at all” to “very much/soon”.

References

Aunola, K., Nurmi, J.-E., Parrila, R., & Onatsu-Arvilommi, T. (2000). *Behavioral Strategy Rating Scale*.

University of Jyväskylä

Zhang, X., Nurmi, J.E., Kiuru, N., Lerkkanen, M.-K. & Aunola, K. (2011). A teacher-report measure of children's task-avoidant behavior: A validation study of the Behavioral Strategy Rating Scale, *Learning and Individual Differences*, 21(6), 690-698. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2011.09.007>.

5.3.6.4 Parents' Homework-Related Affect at 9.5 Years

Parents reported their emotions/affect when monitoring and helping their child with homework, i.e., “Do you feel satisfaction, helplessness, joy, or stress? Answers were rated on a 5-point scale ranging from “not at all” to “very much”. The questions were adopted from a study by Silinskas et al. (2015).

References

Silinskas, G., Kiuru, N., Aunola, K., Lerkkanen, M.-K., & Nurmi, J.-E. (2015). The developmental dynamics of children's academic performance and mothers' homework-related affect and practices. *Developmental Psychology*, 51(4), 419–433. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0038908>

5.3.6.5 Parental Monitoring and Assistance in Homework Situations at 9.5 Years

Parents were asked in five items how they monitor and assist their child's homework. They reported, i.e., whether they make sure that the homework is done and whether they assist in math- or reading-related tasks. The answers were rated on a 5-point scale ranging from “never”, “rarely”, “sometimes”, “often”, to “always”. The questions were adopted from a study by Silinskas et al. (2012).

References

Silinskas, G., Niemi, P., Lerkkanen, M.-K., & Nurmi, J.-E. (2012). Children's poor academic performance evokes parental homework assistance—but does it help? *International Journal of Behavioral Development*, 37(1), 44-56. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0165025412456146>

5.3.6.6 Parental Involvement in Their Child's Homework at 9.5 Years

The questionnaire was modified from the short version of the *Learning Climate Questionnaire* (Black & Deci, 2000; Silinskas et al., 2015; Tunkkari et al., 2021). Parents were asked how they act and feel in homework situations. The measure has eight items that are scored on a 5-point scale ranging from “never”, “not much”, “sometimes”, “almost always”, to “always”. The measure forms two factors: *Psychological Control* and *Autonomy Support* in homework situations.

References

Black, A.E. & Deci, E.L. (2000). The effects of instructors' autonomy support and students' autonomous motivation on learning organic chemistry: A self-determination theory perspective. *Science Education*, 84, 740–756. [https://doi.org/10.1002/1098-237X\(200011\)84:6<740::AID-SCE4>3.0.CO;2-3](https://doi.org/10.1002/1098-237X(200011)84:6<740::AID-SCE4>3.0.CO;2-3)

Silinskas, G., Kiuru, N., Aunola, K., Lerkkanen, M.-K., & Nurmi, J.-E. (2015). The developmental dynamics of children's academic performance and mothers' homework-related affect and practices. *Developmental Psychology*, 51(4), 419–433. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0038908>

Tunkkari, M., Aunola, K., Hirvonen, R., Silinskas, G., & Kiuru, N. (2021). The interplay between maternal homework involvement, task-avoidance, and academic achievement among adolescents. *Journal of Family Psychology*, 35(7), 863-874.

5.3.6.7 *The Child's Bullying Victimization or Acting as a Bully at School 9.5 Years*

Parents reported whether their child had been victimized or had been bullying others at school. The answer options were “not at all”, “once or twice”, “two or three times a month”, “once a week”, “several times a week”, and “I don’t know”.

5.3.6.8 *The Child's School Absences at 9.5 Years*

Parents reported the amount of their child’s school absences during the last year and the reasons for the absences (i.e., vacation with family, infections, stomach-ache, headache, other health issues, tiredness, indoor air problems at school, feelings of discomfort at school, bullying victimization at school, peer relationship problems, learning difficulties or problems in concentrating, stressful situation in family, and COVID quarantine). Answer options ranged from “not at all”, “1 day”, “2–3 days”, “4–5 days”, “6–7 days”, to “more than 7 days”.

5.3.7 Digital Environment

5.3.7.1 *The Child's Digital Media Use at the Child Ages of 2, 4, and 9.5 Years*

Digital media usage was evaluated using self-constructed measures at the ages of 2 and 4 years, and at the age of 9 years using a measure modified from the questionnaire of Przybylski et al. (2017). Parents reported how often the child usually spends watching movies, playing games, using social media, doing schoolwork, or producing content on a computer, tablet, mobile phone, or other digital devices. The answers were rated using the categories: “hardly ever”, “rarely / 1-2 times per month”, “1–2 times per week”, “almost every day”, “more than 2 hours every day”, and “I don’t know”.

References

Przybylski, A. K., & Weinstein, N. (2017). A Large-Scale Test of the Goldilocks Hypothesis: Quantifying the Relations Between Digital-Screen Use and the Mental Well-Being of Adolescents. *Psychological Science*, 28(2), 204–215. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956797616678438>

5.4 Parental Questionnaires

Parents had the option to complete the questionnaires either in a paper form sent by mail, or electronically sent by e-mail until the child reached five years of age. After this point, at the 9-year follow-up assessments, parents filled in the questionnaires in the Research Electronic Data Capture (REDCap, <https://project-redcap.org/>) platform within the UTU network. The links to the REDCap questionnaires were sent to the parents by e-mail directly from REDCap.

5.4.1 Mental Health

5.4.1.1 *Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS) at Gestational Weeks 14, 24, and 34 and at a Child's Age of 3 and 6 Months and 1, 2, 4, 5, and 9.5 Years*

Depressive symptoms were measured by the *Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS)*; Cox et al., 1987). Parents described their symptoms during the past seven days. The *EPDS* is

a widely used screening instrument that consists of 10 items scored from 0 to 3, and higher total scores indicate higher levels of depression.

References

Cox, J. L., Holden, J. M., & Sagovsky, R. (1987). Detection of postnatal depression. *British Journal of Psychiatry*, *150*(6), 782–786. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.150.6.782>

5.4.1.2 Symptom Checklist-90 (SCL-90) at Gestational Weeks 14, 24, and 34 and at a Child's Age of 3 and 6 Months and 2, 4, 5, and 9.5 Years

Mothers' anxiety symptoms were measured using the *Symptom Checklist-90 (SCL-90;* Derogatis et al., 1973). The anxiety subscale of the questionnaire has 10 items scored from 0 to 5, with higher scores reflecting higher levels of anxiety symptoms.

References

Derogatis, L. R., Lipman, R. S., & Covi, L. (1973). SCL-90: An outpatient psychiatric rating scale—Preliminary report. *Psychopharmacology Bulletin*, *9*(1), 13–28.

5.4.1.3 The Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISK) at a Child's age of 5 and 9.5 Years

The parent's resilience was assessed using the short version of the *Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale 2 (CD-RISC-2;* Connor & Davidson, 2003), which is a self-report instrument for measuring an individual's ability to navigate and cope with adverse situations. This short version comprises 2 items, with the answers scored on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from “not true at all”, “rarely true”, “sometimes true”, “often true”, to “true nearly all the time”, whereby higher scores indicate greater resilience.

References

Connor, K. M., & J. R. T. Davidson (2003). Development of a new resilience scale: The Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC). *Depression and Anxiety*, *18* (2), 76–82. <https://doi.org/10.1002/da.10113>.

5.4.1.4 Parental Burnout Assessment (PBA) at a Child's Age of 9.5 Years

Parental burnout is an exhaustion caused by excessive chronic stress related to the parenting role. Parental burnout was measured using the *Parental Burnout Assessment (PBA;* Aunola et al., 2021) which includes 23 items measuring the guardian's burden and stress associated with the role of being a parent. The 3-point Likert scale assess how often they had such stress, ranging from “daily”, “once or twice a week”, or “more seldom / never”.

References

Aunola, K., Sorkkila, M., Tolvanen, A., Tassoul, A., Mikolajczak, M., & Roskam, I. (2021). Development and validation of the Brief Parental Burnout Scale (BPBS). *Psychological Assessment*, *33*(11),1125–1137. doi: 10.1037/pas0001064. Epub 2021 Sep 13. PMID: 34516161.

5.4.2 Social-Emotional

5.4.2.1 Revised Dyadic Adjustment Scale (RDAS) at Gestational Week 34 and at a Child's Age of 6 Months and 1, 2, 4, 5, and 9.5 Years

Parental relationship satisfaction was measured by the *Revised Dyadic Adjustment Scale (RDAS)*; Busby et al., 1995) questionnaire, which is a frequently used instrument to measure relationship adjustment. The measure consists of 14 items that are scored on a 6-point Likert scale (except for one 5-point item), and the answer options are “always agree”, “almost always agree”, “occasionally agree”, “frequently disagree”, “almost always disagree”, and “always disagree”. The measure forms a *Total Sum of Dyadic Adjustment* and three factors: *Satisfaction*, *Cohesion*, and *Consensus*. Higher scores indicate lower relationship satisfaction.

References

Busby, D. M., Christensen, C., Crane, D. R., & Larson, J. H., (1995). A Revision of the dyadic adjustment scale for use with distressed and nondistressed couples: Construct hierarchy and multidimensional scales. *Journal of Marital and Family Therapy*, 21, 289–308. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1752-0606.1995.tb00163.x>.

5.4.3 Parent's Current Health and Environment

5.4.3.1 Socioeconomic Status (SES) at Gestational Week 14 and at the Child Ages of 5 and 9 Years

Parent reported their socioeconomic situation, and the following questions were asked:

- 1) Marital status,
- 2) Living arrangements and family structure,
- 3) Educational level,
- 4) Employment status,
- 5) Income level and wealth, and
- 6) Profession.

Parents also reported their satisfaction with their economic situation, relationship satisfaction, and physical and mental health.

5.4.3.2 Life Events at Gestational Week 34 and at the Child Age of 6 Months and 1, 2, 4, 5, and 9.5 Years

Life events were assessed via a modified version of the *Life Events Checklist (LEC)*; Gray et al., 2004), which has been shown to have adequate psychometric properties for use in nonclinical populations. The questionnaire includes 17 events (16 events at the 6-month measurement, as the event “Birth of the sibling” was omitted). Parents reported whether there had been major changes in their life during the past four years (i.e., moving to a new home, divorce of the parents, health problems, or changes in employment status). The parents reported whether each event had occurred or not, when it happened, and how difficult or empowering the event was. The response options were scored on a 5-point scale: the change was “very empowering”, “somewhat empowering”, “neutral”, “somewhat difficult”, or “very difficult”.

References

Gray, M. J., Litz, B. T., Hsu, J. L., & Lombardo, T. W. (2004). Psychometric Properties of the Life Events Checklist. *Assessment, 11*(4), 330-341. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1073191104269954> (Original work published 2004).

5.4.3.3 The World Health Organization Quality of Life (WHOQOL-8) at the Child's Age of 5 and 9.5 Years

The *Quality of Life (WHOQOL-8)* assessment was developed by the World Health Organization (WHO), and it aims to assess individuals' perceptions of their quality of life, health, and life events. The questionnaire consists of eight questions, and the answers were given on the 5-point Likert scale, where the options ranged from “very satisfied” to “very unsatisfied”. Higher scores indicated higher quality of life.

References

The World Health Organization quality of life assessment (WHOQOL) (1995). Position paper from the World Health Organization. *Social Science & Medicine, 41*(10), 1403–1409. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-9536\(95\)00112-K](https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-9536(95)00112-K).

5.4.3.4 Substance Use at Gestational Week 14 and 34 and at the Child Ages of 3 Months and 9.5 Years

Parents reported their substance use (i.e., tobacco, electronic cigarettes, snus, alcohol, cannabis, prescription medicines without a doctor's prescription, or narcotics or other intoxicating substances) during the past 3 or 12 months.

5.4.3.5 The Alcohol Use Disorders Identification Test (AUDIT) at the Child Age of 9.5 Years

The *Alcohol Use Disorders Identification Test (AUDIT)* is a screening tool developed by the World Health Organization (WHO) to identify hazardous and harmful alcohol consumption, including possible alcohol dependence. It consists of 10 items covering alcohol consumption (frequency and quantity), drinking behavior and symptoms of dependence, alcohol-related problems, and consequences.

References

AUDIT: The Alcohol Use Disorders Identification Test — Guidelines for Use in Primary Health Care (2nd edition) — this is the official WHO manual on how AUDIT is intended to be used. You can download the PDF directly from WHO. World Health Organization <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/WHO-MSD-MSB-01.6a>

5.4.4 Parent's Childhood Environment

5.4.4.1 The Questionnaire of Unpredictability in Childhood (QUIC) at the Child's Age of 9.5 Years

The *Questionnaire of Unpredictability in Childhood (QUIC)*; Glynn et al., 2019) is a series of questions that respondents endorse as applying to their lives in childhood. Examples include “I experienced changes in my custody arrangement”, “At least one of my parents regularly checked that I did my homework”, and “At least one of my parents was disorganized.” The measure comprises 38 items, which are endorsed as either “yes” or “no”. The final scale

consists of five subscales: *Parental Involvement*, *Parental Predictability*, *Parental Environment*, *Physical Environment*, and *Safety and Security*, with a higher score indicating greater exposure to unpredictability in the environment prior to 18 years of age.

References

Glynn, L. M., Stern, H. S., & Howland, M. A. (2019). Measuring novel antecedents of mental illness: the Questionnaire of Unpredictability in Childhood. *Neuropsychopharmacology*, *44*, 876–882.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41386-018-0280-9>

5.4.4.2 The Trauma and Distress Scale (TADS) at Gestational Week 14

The *Trauma and Distress Scale (TADS)*; Salokangas et al., 2016) was used to assess parental childhood maltreatment. The measure has 43 items rated on a Likert scale ranging from 0 = never, 1 = very seldom, 2 = sometimes, 3 = often, and 4 = extremely often. The sum scores of the answers form a total score and five subscales: *Emotional Neglect*, *Emotional Abuse*, *Physical Neglect*, *Physical Abuse*, and *Sexual Abuse*. TADS can be used in different ways: 1) age-group-specific scoring (0–6y, 7–12y, or 13–18y) or 2) by using the highest scores across different age points.

Reference

Salokangas, R. K. R., Schultze-Lutter, F., Patterson, P., von Reventlow, H. G., Heinimaa, M., From, T., ... Tuominen, L. (2016). Psychometric properties of the Trauma and Distress Scale, TADS, in an adult community sample in Finland. *European Journal of Psychotraumatology*, *7*(1).
<https://doi.org/10.3402/ejpt.v7.30062>

5.5 Teacher Questionnaires at 9.5 Years

The participating schools were selected according to the children participating in this study. Parental consent was obtained during the recruitment process, and the parents provided information about the child's school, class, and the teacher's name. Research consents were also obtained from all participating municipalities and the heads of the schools. The participation rate of teachers was about 33% lower than that of the rest of the cohort because consent was not possible to obtain from all the municipalities, and some families had moved away from the original area included in the study. However, the teachers' response rate was 79%.

The questionnaires were completed in the Research Electronic Data Capture (REDCap, <https://project-redcap.org/>) platform within the UTU network. The links to the REDCap questionnaires were sent to the teachers by e-mail directly from REDCap. Teachers evaluated the child's school performance, support received at school, and the child's behavior in group settings.

5.5.1 Multisource Assessment of Children's Social Competence, MASCS (Teacher version)

Teachers evaluated the child's social competence in the school environment using the *Multisource Assessment of Children's Social Competence (MASCS)*; Junttila et al., 2006). The MASCS measures a child's behavior in social contexts and has 15 items that are scored on

four response options ranging from “never”, “rarely”, “frequently”, to “very frequently.” The *MASCs* has two main dimensions: *Prosocial* and *Antisocial* aspects of social behavior. These main dimensions are further divided into four sub-dimensions: *Cooperating Skills* and *Empathy* (forming the prosocial dimension) and *Impulsivity* and *Disruptiveness* (forming the antisocial dimension).

References

Junttila, N., Voeten, M., Kaukiainen, A., & Vauras, M. (2006). Multisource assessment of children’s social competence. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 66(5), 874–895.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0013164405285546>

5.5.2 Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire, SDQ (Teacher version)

The behavioral symptoms were assessed using the teacher version of the *Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ)*; Goodman, 2001). The *SDQ* is a widely used and validated tool for the screening of socio-emotional problems and competencies of 3- to 16-year-olds. The teachers evaluated the child’s behavior during the school year with the questionnaire, which included 25 items, and the response options were "not true", "somewhat true", and "certainly true". Item examples include: “Considerate of other people's feelings”, “Restless, overactive, cannot stay still for long”, and “Often complaining of headaches, stomach-aches or sickness”. The questionnaire forms the *Main Scale of Total Difficulties*, which is further divided into subscales *Emotional Symptoms*, *Conduct Problems*, *Hyperactivity/Inattention*, *Peer Relationship Problems*, as well as *Prosocial Behavior*. Higher scores reflect more problems, except for *Prosocial Behavior*, where higher scores reflect higher prosociality.

References

Goodman, R., (2001). Psychometric properties of the strengths and difficulties questionnaire. *Journal of American Academy of Child Adolescent Psychiatry*, 40 (11), 1337–1345.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/00004583-200111000-00015>

5.5.3 The Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function Second Edition, BRIEF2 (Teacher Form)

The *Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function, Second Edition (BRIEF2)*; Gioia et al., 2018) questionnaire was developed to assess everyday behavioral manifestations of children's (ages 5-18) everyday behaviors related to goal-directed behavior and executive functions. Teachers completed the *BRIEF2* measure (Gioia et al., 2015) which includes 63 items concerning a child’s problems in specific behaviors. The answers are scored on a 3-point scale (“never”, “sometimes”, or “often”), with higher scores indicating more severe executive functioning problems. The questionnaire forms the scales of *Behavioral Regulation*, *Emotional Regulation*, *Cognitive Regulation*, and the *Global Executive Index*.

References

Gioia, G. A., Isquith, P. K., Guy, S. C., & Kenworthy, L. (2015). *Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function, Second Edition (BRIEF®2) Teacher Form* [Assessment instrument]. PAR.

Gioia, G. A., Isquith, P. K., Retzlaff, P. D., & Espy, K. A. (2002). Confirmatory Factor Analysis of the Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function (BRIEF) in a Clinical Sample. *Child Neuropsychology*, 8(4), 249–257. <https://doi-org.ezproxy.utu.fi/2443/10.1076/chin.8.4.249.13513>

5.5.4 Child's School Performance and Received Support

Teacher reported the child's school performance and support received at school.

A) Basic information:

1. Date, school, name of the teacher, and class
2. How well and how long the teacher has known the child
3. Whether the child has repeated a grade
4. The child's mother tongue
5. The teacher's role in the class

B) Learning environment:

1. The length of the child's compulsory education
2. The child's level of three-tier support (General support, Intensified support, or Special support)
3. The structure of the class
4. The number of students in the class and their age distribution
5. The number of different teachers in the class
6. Whether co-teaching is being utilized
7. The length of the child's school days
8. The use of digital tools and learning environments in teaching

C) The child's school performance in comparison with peers:

1. Overall school performance
2. Reading fluency
3. Spelling
4. Writing
5. Reading comprehension
6. Foreign language
7. Math (arithmetic skills)
8. Math (applied)
9. Use of digital tools
10. Information retrieval in digital environments
11. Sports
12. Crafts / technical crafts
13. Visual art
14. Music

D) The child's learning objectives:

1. General education
2. Teaching emphasizes core contents

3. Individualized subjects
4. Learning is organized by functional areas

E) Support the child receives at school:

1. Differentiation (learning contents, materials, homework)
2. Student welfare services (school social worker, psychologist, pediatrician)
3. Remedial teaching
4. Part-time special needs education
5. Full-time special needs education
6. Grade-independent teaching
7. Classroom assistant

Teacher further reported the focus of the support:

1. Reading difficulties
2. Writing difficulties
3. Mathematical difficulties
4. Problems with concentration
5. Problems in executive functions
6. Behavioral problems
7. Mental health problems

Teacher also reported how many times per week and for how many months during the school year the child has received support, as well as whether the support has been sufficient for the child.

6 Coding Protocols

6.1 Parent–Child Interaction Coding

Recordings of parent–child interactions were coded with two methods: the *Emotional Availability Scales* (Biringen, 2008) and coding for maternal sensory signals, from which *Entropy Score* was calculated.

References

Biringen, Z. (2008). *The EA Professionals and Parent Curricula*. Available at www.emotionalavailability.com.

6.1.1 Coding of Emotional Availability Scales

The *Emotional Availability (EA) Scales* measure the quality of emotional interactions within the dyad. The adult scales of sensitivity, structuring, non-intrusiveness, and non-hostility were used to assess parental behaviors. The child scales of child responsiveness and involvement were used to assess child behaviors. Each scale reflects a distinct quality of caregiving. In the *EA* framework, a parent’s ability to interact with a child is viewed dyadically; that is, the quality of the interaction is evaluated based on the child’s reactions (Biringen, 1998). This means that the mother cannot “look good” without the child being emotionally responsive.

EA is based on attachment theory and has been shown to correlate with attachment security (McConnell et al., 2020), but it expands the focus on the dyadic and emotional aspects of the interaction (Biringen et al., 2014). In the fourth edition of the *EA* scale, each dimension is scored on a 7-point scale to produce a direct score describing the overall quality of the interaction. Scores from 1–2 on all six scales are considered highly problematic, scores from 2.5–3.5 indicate detachment in the relationship, and scores from 4–5 indicate complicated *EA*. Scores from 5.5–7 indicate an emotionally available and healthy *EA* mother–infant relationship (Biringen, 2008). Coders for *EA* completed authorized online training and were certified to use the method (www.emotionalavailability.com).

Altogether, 192 interaction recordings were analyzed at 8 months, 397 at 30 months, and 467 at five years. At 9 years, 524 interaction codings were conducted, and coding is ongoing (348/524 recordings have been coded as of February 4, 2026). Videos were coded by blinded coders who received the training directly from Biringen. There were two coders at 8 months, three coders at 30 months, four coders at 5 years, and four coders at 9 years.

Reliability checks were conducted for approximately 10% of the recordings. Differences were negotiated between the coders, and consensus ratings were used for subsequent analyses. Interclass correlations demonstrated good to excellent interrater agreement across scales:

- At 8 months, intraclass correlation coefficient for sensitivity was .80, for structuring .72, for nonintrusiveness .85, for nonhostility .70, for responsiveness .78 and for involvement .90.
- At 30 months, reliability checks were conducted for a total of 57 recordings (14.4 % of all recordings). Intraclass correlation coefficient for sensitivity ranged from .83 to .91, for structuring from .84 to .91, for nonintrusiveness from .84 to .90, for nonhostility from .70 to .85, for responsiveness from .87 to .92, and for involvement from .83 to .95.
- At 5 years, reliability checks were conducted for a total of 54 recordings (11.6 % of all the recordings). Intraclass correlation coefficient for sensitivity was .83, for structuring .82, for nonintrusiveness .68, for nonhostility .66, for responsiveness .77 and for involvement .78.
- From the 9 year assessment, 348 of 524 recordings have been coded, and initial reliability coding has been completed for 22 tapes. Intraclass correlation coefficient for sensitivity was .88, for structuring .76, for nonintrusiveness .74, for nonhostility .81, for responsiveness .84 and for involvement .87, respectively.

References

- Biringen, Z. (2008). The EA Professionals and Parent Curricula. Available at <http://www.emotionalavailability.com> .
- Biringen, Z., Derscheid, D., Vliegen, N., Closson, L., & Easterbrooks, M. A. (2014). Emotional availability (EA): Theoretical background, empirical research using the EA scales, and clinical applications. *Developmental Review*, 34(2), 114–167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dr.2014.01.002>
- Biringen, Z., Robinson, J., & Emde, R. N. (1998). The Emotional Availability Scales (3rd ed.), unpublished manuscript, Department of Human Development & Family Studies.
- McConnell, M., Closson, L., Morse, B., Wurster, H., Flykt, M., Sarche, M., & Biringen, Z. (2020). The "EA brief": A single session of parent feedback and coaching to improve emotional attachment and emotional availability (EA). *Infant mental health journal*, 41(6), 783–792. <https://doi.org/10.1002/imhj.21867>

6.1.2 Coding of Maternal Sensory Signals (Unpredictability of Caregiving)

The maternal sensory signals (i.e., auditory, tactile, and visual) were coded from 10-minute sequences of mother-child play episodes continuously on a moment-to-moment basis using The Observer XT 11 software (Noldus). Coding was conducted by trained, double-blinded coders, who were blind to all other information about the study participants. Tactile signals included all physical contact between the mother and child (e.g., touching, holding). Auditory signals encompassed all maternal vocalizations (e.g., laughing, vocal sounds, talking). Visual signals referred to all instances in which the mother manipulated a toy or object while the child was visually attending. (Davis et al., 2017). Altogether, 180 videos were analyzed at 8 months, 394 at 30 months, 410 at 5 years, and 377 at 9 years. Inter-rater agreement was calculated for 10% of the videotapes and was 86% at 8-months measurement, 84% at 30-months measurement, 84% at 5-years measurement, and 85% at 9-years measurement.

The coding approach focused on the conditional probabilities of transitions between different combinations of maternal visual, tactile, and auditory sensory signals (Davis et al., 2017). For example, auditory and visual input were coded when the mother simultaneously spoke to her child while showing a toy to them. If she then additionally touched the child, all three sensory inputs (auditory, visual, and tactile) were provided at once, and this would be considered a transition to a different combination of sensory signals provided by the mother. Transitions between the eight possible combinations of maternal sensory signals (based on the presence or absence of each of the three types of sensory input) were modeled as changes in the state of a discrete-state Markov process (Vegetabile et al., 2019). The entropy rate of this process was then used as a measure of the unpredictability of maternal sensory signals.

Highly predictable maternal sensory signals mean that one signal or combination of signals consistently follows another (e.g., touch is always followed by speech and visual input); the maternal signals would be considered highly predictable for the child, indicating a low entropy rate. In contrast, if the probability of one maternal signal following another is random, the maternal signals would be considered highly unpredictable, indicating a high entropy rate. The entropy rate can range from 0 to 2.807, higher values indicating more unpredictable maternal sensory signals and caregiving behavior. For more detailed

information and materials, see Davis et al. (2017) and <https://contecenter.uci.edu/shared-resources/>.

References

- Davis, E. P., Stout, S. A., Molet, J., Vegetabile, B., Glynn, L. M., Sandman, C. A., Heins, K., Stern, H., & Baram, T. Z. (2017). Exposure to unpredictable maternal sensory signals influences cognitive development across species. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, *114*(39), 10390–10395. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1703444114>
- Vegetabile, B. G., Stout-Oswald, S. A., Davis, E. P., Baram, T. Z., & Stern, H. S. (2019). Estimating the entropy rate of finite Markov chains with application to behavior studies. *Journal of Educational and Behavioral Statistics*, *44*(3), 282-308.

6.2 Child Temperament

The coding of temperament episodes was conducted retrospectively on the video recordings collected during the visits, using a single camera positioned to capture child facial and bodily signals. The coding was based on the Lab-TAB prelocomotor (Goldsmith & Rothbart, 1999) and preschool (Goldsmith et al., 1999) manual, the AFFEX scheme, and intense training received by the main coder in other laboratories that had previously used the same temperament episodes and coding systems. Coding was carried out on site by trained graduate and postgraduate students (2–4 coders, depending on the episode) who received extensive training for coding, first practicing on 6-8 training videos per each episode with the goal of reaching certain reliability level (80% correct for each behavioral indicator) before coding independently. In addition, inter-rater reliability was monitored regularly, and in case of low reliability, continuous training was provided. During reliability sessions, coders were able to ask questions and discuss challenging codes. In unclear situations, the responsible researcher decided on the final coding.

Inter-rater reliability was assessed on 10% of the full sample participating in the visits and was determined using Cohen's Kappa and inter-rater correlations where applicable. The reliability-coded recordings were randomly selected based on the fixed order of visits (every 10th video). In all temperament observation episodes, an additional assessment of caregiver behavior/interference was conducted (0 = very inefficient parent behavior, does not follow instructions, 1 = parent mildly deviates from instructions, and 2 = parent behaves as instructed). Child baseline behavior was also coded before each visit (1 = tired/drowsy, 2 = alert/calm, 3 = alert/active, 4 = fussy, 5 = crying).

References

- Goldsmith, H. H., and M. K. Rothbart. 1999. The Laboratory Temperament Assessment Battery (LAB-TAB, Prelocomotor Version, Edition 3.1). Madison, Wisconsin: University of Wisconsin Press.
- Goldsmith, H.H., Reilly, J., Lemery, K.S., Longley, S., & Prescott, A. (1999). The Laboratory Temperament Assessment Battery Preschool (Version 0.).

6.2.1 Negative Reactivity at 8 Months and 2.5 Years

Overall negative reactivity was assessed using the *Gentle Arm Restraint by the Parent* episode, in which the infant is presented with an interesting toy. After the infant has started to

play with the toy, the mother gently holds the infant's arms for two 30-second trials, preventing the infant from reaching the toy. Both 30-second trials were coded in 5-second epochs. The total duration of the episode was 2 minutes, or 3 min including instructions from the experimenter. The following behaviors were coded: intensity of struggle (0-4); intensity of facial anger (0-3); intensity of facial sadness (0-3); presence of bodily sadness (0-1); and intensity of distress vocalizations (0-5). Inter-rater reliability for the coding was adequate (Cohen's $K = 0.62-0.79$).

At 2.5 years, negative reactivity was coded using the *Attractive Toy in a Transparent Box* episode. The following indicators were coded: intensity of anger expression (0-3); presence of bodily anger (0-3); intensity of frustration (0-3); presence of protest vocalizations (0-3); intensity of sadness expression (0-3); and presence of bodily sadness (0-1). Inter-rater reliability across the indicators was adequate (Cohen's $K = 0.76-0.79$, with inter-rater correlations = 0.42-1.00).

6.2.2 Fear/Behavioral Inhibition at 8 and 2.5 Years

Fear was assessed during the *Masks* episode, a fear-eliciting task in which the infant is presented with four different masks in order of increasing intensity and likelihood of eliciting a fear response. The following behaviors in response to each mask were coded: smiling (0-3); intensity of escape behaviors (0-3); intensity of facial fear (0-3); intensity of bodily fear (0-3); and intensity of distress vocalizations (0-5). The episode demonstrated good inter-rater reliability (Cohen's $K = 0.73-0.83$).

Behavioral inhibition was coded using positive reactivity in the *Popping Bubbles* episode described in Section 6.2.3, identifying the lower 15% of children based on their positive reactivity/exuberance behaviors.

6.2.3 Positive Reactivity/Exuberance at 2.5 Years

Positive reactivity/exuberance was observed during the *Popping Bubbles* episode, in which the experimenter blows bubbles using a bubble gun and asks the child to pop the bubbles with different body parts to elicit activity and excitement. For coding, the first trial was divided into two coding epochs: one in which the child observed the bubbles, and the second in which the child attempted to blow the bubbles themselves. For the second trial, one 15-second coding epoch began at the moment the experimenter activated the bubble gun for the first, fourth, and seventh time. Three indicators were coded during these epochs: intensity of smiling (0-3), laughter (0 = no, 1 = yes) and vigour of approach/activity (0-1 in the first trial and 0-3 in the second trial). Inter-rater reliability across the indicators was high (Cohen's $K = 0.80-0.87$).

6.2.4 Self-Regulation/Effortful Control at 8 Months and 2.5 Years

Task orientation/attentiveness was assessed using the *Blocks* episode, in which the infant is given a set of blocks to play with and manipulate during a 3-minute episode with minimal

caregiver involvement. The entire episode, including instructions from the experimenter, lasted approximately 4 min and was coded in 10-second epochs, divided into three one-minute sets. The following behaviors were coded: manipulation of blocks (0–3), intensity of facial interest (0–2), and duration of looking (0–3). The episode demonstrated adequate inter-rater reliability (Cohen's $K = 0.72$ – 0.79).

The *Arm Restraint* episode was also used to assess self-regulation via gaze aversion, one of the earliest observable forms of self-regulation in infancy. Gaze aversion was coded as the number of seconds the infant spent looking away from the toy, either around the room or toward the parent, during the episodes. We used a sum score of total gaze aversion in seconds within each 5-second epoch (0–5). The epochs were the same as those used for the assessment of negative reactivity. Because gaze aversion was coded on a continuous scale, reliability was assessed using correlations only, which were adequate (inter-rater $r = 0.78$ – 0.95).

At 2.5 years, child self-regulatory behaviors during the *Attractive Toy in a Transparent Box* episode were coded using two indicators: (social) gaze aversion and distraction. Gaze aversion was coded as the number of seconds the child looked away from the toys/the box during each 10-second epoch (forming a scale from 0 to 10). Social gaze aversion was coded as the number of seconds the child looked toward or attended to the caregiver, rather than the toys/the box (0–10). Distraction was coded as “1” in any epoch in which the child was clearly disengaging from the task, e.g., by beginning to play with other objects in the room, exploring items in the room, or moving away from the camera.

6.2.5 Reactivity and Self-Regulatory Behaviors at 5 Years (Forbidden Toy Coding Scheme)

A behavioral coding scheme for the *Forbidden Toy* episode was developed, separating behaviors into three categories: looking at the toy (e.g. head turning, peeking), emotional reactivity (e.g., positive or negative facial expressions and vocalizations), and self-regulatory behaviors (e.g., bodily movements or vocalizations). Based on the video recordings, psychology students coded the children's behavior during the task, with inter-rater reliability checks conducted on 10% of the data. Reliability coding is still ongoing at the time of the publication of this document.

6.3 Preprocessing of Eye Tracking Data in Social Emotional Attention Tasks

The raw data from the eye-tracking measurements include timestamps and locations of the targets on the screen, and the x- and y-coordinates of participants' gaze position (500 samples per second). There are numerous ways to analyse the data. Here, we describe two preprocessing procedures that have been used in previously published articles to ensure sufficient data quality.

6.3.1 Disengagement in Overlap Task

The disengagement variable describes whether the participant disengages their gaze from the central stimulus to the lateral distractor during the 1,000 ms following the distractor's appearance (Kataja et al., 2022). The disengagement variable was calculated using only valid trial data. The trial data from the overlap task, including timestamps for the onset times of central and lateral pictures and the x- and y-coordinates of participants' gaze position (500 samples per second) were stored as text files and analyzed using a library of MATLAB functions (MathWorks, Natick, MA; Leppänen et al., 2015).

The following criteria were used to ensure the quality of the trials, and these parameters were set a priori based on prior studies using the same methodology and analytic approach (Leppänen et al., 2015). First, trials were required to show sufficient looking at the central stimulus (70%) during a time interval that started at the onset of the trial, that is, the appearance of the face or nonface stimulus on the screen, and extended to the end of the analysis period. The analysis period ended either when gaze disengagement from the central to the lateral stimulus occurred or, if no gaze disengagement was observed, 1,000 ms after the appearance of the lateral distractor. Second, trials needed to contain a sufficient number of valid samples in the gaze data, with no gaps longer than 200ms. Gaps in the data were extrapolated by the analysis script by carrying the last recorded sample forward, but if the gap exceeded 200 ms, the trial was flagged as invalid and excluded. Third, if disengagement occurred during the trial, the exact timing of the eye movement from the central to the lateral stimulus was required to be known for the trial to be included. Thus, if the eye movement occurred during a period of missing or extrapolated gaze data, the trial was rejected.

References

- Kataja, E.-L., Eskola, E., Pelto, J., Korja, R., Paija, S.-P., Nolvi, S., Häikiö, T., Karlsson, L., Karlsson, H., & Leppänen, J. M. (2022). The stability of early developing attentional bias for faces and fear from 8 to 30 and 60 months in the FinnBrain Birth Cohort Study. *Developmental Psychology*.
- Leppänen, J. M., Forssman, L., Kaatiala, J., Yrttiaho, S., & Wass, S. (2015). Widely applicable MATLAB routines for automated analysis of saccadic reaction times. *Behavior Research Methods*, 47(2), 538–548. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-014-0473-z>

6.3.2 Data Quality in Free Viewing of Paired Pictures

Fixations during the free viewing of paired pictures were identified using an algorithm called "Identification by Two-Means Clustering" (I2MC; Hessels et al., 2017), which is designed for data with a wide range of noise levels and periods of data loss due to poorly cooperating participants. Because latency to the first fixation on the target has been used as one key variable (Eskola et al., 2023), only trials in which the child fixated on the center of the screen at the beginning of the trial were considered valid. That is, only the trials with a fixation on the center of the screen occurring between 0 ms and 150 ms were included. Saccadic reaction times shorter than 150 ms after the stimulus appearance were assumed to be predictive (Kenward et al., 2017); therefore, only saccadic shifts from the central stimulus to a peripheral target occurring after 150 ms from the stimulus onset were included in the preprocessed dataset.

References

- Eskola, E., Kataja, E.-L., Pelto, J., Tuulari, J. J., Hyönä, J., Häikiö, T., Hessels, R. S., Holmberg, E., Nordenswan, E., Karlsson, H., Karlsson, L., & Korja, R. (2023). Attention biases for emotional facial expressions during a free viewing task increase between 2.5 and 5 years of age. *Developmental Psychology*, 59(11), 2065–2079. <https://doi.org/10.1037/dev0001598>
- Hessels, R. S., Niehorster, D. C., Kemner, C., & Hooge, I. T. C. (2017). Noise-robust fixation detection in eye movement data: Identification by two-means clustering (I2MC). *Behavior Research Methods*, 49, 1802–1823. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-016-0822-1>
- Kenward, B., Koch, F. S., Forssman, L., Brehm, J., Tidemann, I., Sundqvist, A., Marciszko, C., Hermansen, T. K., Heimann, M., & Gredebäck, G. (2017). Saccadic reaction times in infants and adults: Spatiotemporal factors, gender, and interlaboratory variation. *Developmental Psychology*, 53(9), 1750–1764. <https://doi.org/10.1037/dev0000338>

6.4 Child Phonology

At 8 months and 2.5 years, the parent–infant interaction videos were used to evaluate children’s spontaneous productions for phonological skills.

The 8-month-old videos were used to assess volubility, quality of vocalizations, and babbling level (using the *Mean Babbling Level*). The 30-month-old videos were used to code the size of the phoneme inventory, the quantity of phonemes, and the occurrence of consonant clusters and heterosyllabic clusters. The percentage of incorrect or unintelligible words was also determined.

Transcription was conducted according to a manual developed specifically for this study. A phonetic Finnish transcription system was used, in which each symbol corresponds to an International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA) symbol. Using 10-minute segments of the parent-child interaction, both parent and child utterances were transcribed from the video recordings. Segments of the child’s speech excluded from analysis were marked in the transcription.

All videos were coded by trained, blinded transcribers using professional grade headphones. Transcriptions were carried out by speech and language pathologists and master’s-level students in speech and language pathology. Inter-rater reliability was assessed by a gold-standard transcriber, who independently transcribed 10% of randomly selected samples from each transcriber.

6.5 Mean Length of Utterance at 5 Years

Mean Length of Utterance at 5 years was calculated using transcriptions of children’s speech during a 20-minute free-play session. The transcriptions were carried out by two speech and language pathologists and eight master's-level students majoring in speech and language pathology. Prior to working with the data, the students were trained in C-segmentation and morpheme segmentation. Inter-rater reliability was assessed by a gold-standard transcriber, who independently transcribed 10 % of the randomly selected samples from each transcriber.

Segmentation of the utterances was conducted following the C-segmentation protocol (Miller et al., 2015). C-segmentation is designed to segment utterances typical of spoken language, as opposed to sentences in written formal language. Following the description in the SALT manual (Miller et al., 2015), we defined C-units as independent clauses with their relevant modifiers. C-units may be complete without a verb (e.g., when answering a question “Yes.”) in contrast to normative linguistic definitions of a clause in which the base of a clause is a verb (Gelderen, 2013). One conversational turn may include several C-units. Parallel clauses were treated as separate C-units, whereas subordinate and relative clauses sharing a subject with the main clause were treated as one. Statements, questions, and exclamations were marked using their appropriate punctuation. Interrupted utterances and utterances abandoned by the speaker were excluded from the analysis. Self-revisions, repetitions, and filled pauses were excluded from C-units by placing them inside mazes, for example: “(Ja sit ja sit) ja sit puu kaatu” ([And then and then] And then the tree fell.).

Finnish is an agglutinative language with a rich morpho-syntax (Karlsson, 2015). It has a free word order due to a morphological case system, which expresses linguistic functions without relying on additional prepositions or fixed word order. Words are formed by adding obligatory morphological suffixes to word roots. Nouns decline into 15 different cases, each marked by its own case suffix. Verbs conjugate into four temporal structures, seven personal structures, and four modal structures, each with its own morphological suffix. Word roots in the Finnish language may vary due to consonant gradation, for example: *vesi* – *vettä* – *veteen* – *vedessä* (water - some water – to the water - in the water; Kiparsky, 2001). Finnish is a transparent language, meaning that each speech sound corresponds to a single written letter, with the exception of /ŋ/, which is written as *-nk-* and /ŋ:/, written as *-ng-*.

Spoken informal dialects of South-Western Finnish are characterized by omission of the final speech sound(s) (Lyytikäinen et al., 2013). The omission of the last speech sound(s) sometimes leads to omission of morphological segments as a consequence. Missing speech sounds or morphological segments were not imputed during transcription but instead transcribed as heard. Words uttered by the participants were segmented into morphemes following the rules based on the Finnish descriptive grammar (Hakulinen et al., 2008). Morphemes were separated using a forward slash (/) in accordance with SALT conventions. Nouns and verbs followed different set of segmentation rules.

References

- Gelderen, E. V. (2013). *Clause Structure* (1st ed.). Cambridge University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139084628>
- Hakulinen, A., Korhonen, R., Koivisto, V., Heinonen, T. R., & Alho, I. (2008). *Iso suomen kielioppi*. Helsinki: Suomalaisen Kirjallisuuden Seura. Online version, read 19.8.2024. Available: <http://scripta.kotus.fi/visk>
URN:ISBN:978-952-5446-35-7.
- Karlsson, F. (2015). *Finnish: An Essential Grammar* (0 ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315743233>
- Kiparsky, P. (2001). Structural case in Finnish. *Lingua*, 111(4–7), 315–376. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0024-3841\(00\)00035-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0024-3841(00)00035-8)
- Lyytikäinen, E., Rekunen, J., & Yli-Paavola, J. (2013). *Suomen murrekirja*. Gaudeamus.
- Miller, J., Andriacchi, K., & Nockerts, A. (2015). *Assessing Language Production using SALT Software. A Clinician’s guide to Language Sample Analysis*. Second edition. SALT Software LLC, Middleton, WI.

6.6 Nonword Repetition

All nonword repetition tasks were transcribed using professional studio-grade headphones. Two transcribers coded the productions phoneme-by-phoneme, calculating both the number of correct phonemes per nonword and the number of correctly produced nonwords per participant. A nonword was considered correctly produced even if the child added extra phonemes before or/and after the target form (e.g., “oikainen” --> “poikainen”). If the child failed to comply with the task instructions or skipped more than five of the nonword repetitions, they were excluded from the sample. In total, three children out of 393 were excluded from the 5-year-old sample, and five participants out of 520 were excluded from the 9-year-old sample.

The productions included in the analysis were divided between two transcribers for coding. The transcribers for 5-year-old measurements were a phonetician and a psychologist, whereas two speech-language pathology students transcribed the productions of the 9-year-olds. Inter-rater reliability was established through cross-checking: For the 5-year-olds' measurements, the productions of 78 participants (20% of the total sample) were re-coded. Point-by-point reliabilities for the phoneme-level variable were 86% for transcriber 1 and 78% for transcriber 2. For the 9-year-olds, the productions of 60 participants (11.7% of the total sample) were re-coded. Point-by-point reliabilities for the phoneme-level variable were 95% for transcriber 1 and 86% for transcriber 2. For the item-level variable, the reliabilities were 96% for transcriber 1 and 92% for transcriber 2.

7 Future of the Study and the Update Plan

The next data collection in this study will be conducted between 2024 and 2027, when the participating children are in 5th grade of the elementary school. This data collection will include measures of children’s learning and mental health, as well as their home, school, and digital environments. The metadata for this dataset will be published after the data collection has been completed.